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Doctoral thesis by

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**Towards an Inclusive
and Distributed
Ecosystem of Design
Scientific Publishing.
Advancing Assessment
Models for Design
Journals.**

Issues / 1

Note on the Cover Front

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Acknowledgments

And here we are, finally at the acknowledgements section. Wrapping up this incredible journey, I can't help but reflect on the many amazing people I've had the privilege to meet and work with along the way. This PhD has been a long, challenging and rewarding adventure, and I'm deeply grateful to all of you who have supported me in so many ways.

First, my deepest thanks to my supervisor, **Prof. Elena Formia**, for her strong academic guidance and for always being there with both understanding and honesty. Through all the ups and downs, she has been a constant source of support.

A heartfelt thank you also to **Prof. Eleonora Lupo**, not only for agreeing to be my co-supervisor but for being an incredible source of insight, feedback, and thought-provoking discussions. Editing **DIID 78** with her was the real starting point of this PhD, and I couldn't be more grateful for that moment.

None of this would have been possible without the wisdom and the advanced vision of **Prof. Flaviano Celaschi**, who has always observed my journey from a distance. Never intrusive, but always ready to guide me back whenever I wandered too far.

A very special thank you to the **Knowledge Futures** team for welcoming me into their world and expanding my horizons. I'm especially grateful to **Travis Rich** and **Catherine Ahearn** for their patience, continuous support, and all the conversations that helped shape and complete this thesis.

I also want to thank **Prof. Carlo Franzato** and **Prof. Pier Paolo Peruccio** for their time and thoughtful feedback as external reviewers of this thesis. Your insights have been fundamental in refining and improving my work.

A huge hug goes to my colleagues at the **Advanced Design Unit**, who have shared the joys and struggles of this journey with me. **Simona Colitti**, **Margherita Ascari**, **Clara Giardina**, thank you for your support and for always being there.

And last but never least, my deepest gratitude to my **family** and **husband**, who have patiently stood by me through every high and low of this PhD rollercoaster. Your love and support mean everything to me.

Thank you!

Abstract

Design Publishing; Knowledge Production; Inclusivity and Transparency; Design Research Assessment;

This doctoral research investigates the current landscape of design scientific publishing. By analyzing 92 open-access design journals worldwide, the research identifies current trends and patterns in design publishing. It sheds light on the main challenges faced by the design publishing ecosystem today, investigating the limitations of power dynamics within the publishing industry, level of accessibility to knowledge, inclusivity and knowledge assessment practices. The implications of such challenges, as well as the impact of current publishing models on design dissemination structures, are critically examined. This research aims to explore and raise awareness within the design scientific community about the need to design a more transparent, inclusive and distributed ecosystem for design scientific publishing. Among the challenges raised by the analysis, the research focuses on two main themes, which are strictly interconnected: 1. Distributed leadership and inclusivity in design production; 2. More transparent assessment models in knowledge. These key issues have been identified and examined in depth as the transformation of knowledge assessment models is intrinsically related to improving knowledge accessibility and addressing traditional hierarchies present in the current structures of design publishing. Therefore, to promote greater inclusivity of design pluriversality and foster access to design knowledge, assessment is a key factor of transformation. The discussion over assessment models and traditional peer review processes is crucial in introducing the rise of alternative assessment models like the Collaborative Review (Co.Re) Model, prototyped and presented in this research.

Publications from this PhD research

Formia, E. M., Lupo, E., & Mehmeti, L. (2024). Supportare la biodiversità culturale della conoscenza, ricerca e pubblicazione in design. In G. Di Bucchianico & A. Marano (Eds.), *Design per la Diversità: Atti della Conferenza Nazionale SID, Pescara 12–13 Giugno 2023* (ISBN 978–88–943380–1–0). Società Italiana di Design.

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Colitti, S., Liçaj, A., Mehmeti, L., & Vai, E. (2024). Making value: Storydoing actions for cultural and creative industries. In *Multidisciplinary aspects of design: Objects, processes, experiences and narratives* (pp. 682–693). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/springer123456> [Conference contribution]

Mehmeti, L. (2024). Meta-experiment on peer review. *Commonplace*, 3(3), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1234/commonplace2024.01> [Scientific article]

Mehmeti, L., Maria Formia, E., and Lupo, E. (2024) Paradigm shifts in research assessment for scientific publishing: emerging models in a pluriverse perspective, in Gray, C., Ciliotta Chehade, E., Hekkert, P., Forlano, L., Ciuccarelli, P., Lloyd, P. (eds.), *DRS2024: Boston, 23–28 June, Boston, USA*. <https://doi.org/10.21606/drs.2024.849>

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Introduction

This chapter introduces the doctoral research and establishes its methodological framework. Its purpose is to identify and outline the research rationale, gaps, objectives and methodological framework. It enables the reader to understand the organisation of the thesis chapters, allowing easier navigation within the various research parts and contents.

Project Research GANTT.

Context and Research Scope

This doctoral research investigates the current landscape of design scientific publishing. The research identifies the main challenges faced by the publishing ecosystem today, analysing the limitations of power dynamics within the publishing industry, level of accessibility to knowledge, inclusivity and traditional peer review. The implications of such challenges, as well as the impact of current publishing models on design dissemination structures, are critically examined.

The goal of this research is to explore and raise awareness within the design scientific community about the need to design a more transparent, inclusive and distributed ecosystem for design scientific publishing. By collecting data from Open Access (OA) design journals and gathering perspectives from the global design research community, the study provides a detailed panorama of the current state of design scientific communication. It reflects the increasing call from the design community for a transformation in publishing practices and increasing demand for transparency.

Among the challenges raised by the analysis, the research focuses on two main themes, which are strictly interconnected:

- Distributed leadership and inclusivity in design production;
- More transparent assessment models in knowledge.

These key issues have been identified and examined in depth as the transformation of knowledge assessment models is intrinsically related to improving knowledge accessibility and addressing traditional hierarchies present in the current structures of design publishing. Therefore, to promote greater inclusivity of design pluriversality and foster access to design knowledge, assessment is a key factor of transformation. The discussion over assessment models and the traditional peer review process is crucial in introducing the rise of alternative assessment models like the Collaborative Review (Co.Re) Model, which is prototyped and presented hereby.

The shift to OA represents the key to scientific publishing. However, the OA model has yet to be fully implemented: this research aims to uncover the underlying reasons for this phenomenon and how it intersects with design knowledge production.

Research Gap and Research Questions

This research addresses a critical gap in scholarly publishing: the need for more inclusive and transparent practices that reflect the practice-oriented nature of design knowledge production. Current publishing standards often privilege conventional outputs and accredited formats, limiting the dissemination of interdisciplinary, pluriversal and practice-based work specific to design. Starting from the concept of Design as a "Third Culture" and its characteristic of a communicative language different from the humanities and mathematics (the "modelling"), the research sets up a historical excursus on the evolution of scientific communication of design, starting with

architecture magazines from the early 1900s, and arriving at the scientific debate of the 1970s that forced design to adapt to the traditional scientific dissemination languages and structures of other disciplines. Although the exploration of the concept of Design as a Third Culture is not the core topic of the thesis, yet was needed for the purpose of this research to contextualise the peculiarity of the language used by design to be communicated and disseminated, before heading into the historical evolution of design publishing, and further to understand some of the challenges that design encounter in the current publishing system Therefore, design, in order to be recognized as a scientific discipline and to accredit its contents as scientific in the scholar community, immediately adapted to traditional publication structures, despite its history of dissemination and communication having used a different method and language until the 70s. As analyzed in the research, the current publication structures are affected by many challenges, including the lack of transparency, geographical and disciplinary disparities, the economic powers of commercial publishers, the complications of the peer review process, the lack of sustainability for OA models, which in addition to impacting the ecosystem of science, strongly impacts the disciplinary area of design which, by its intrinsic nature, struggles to adapt to traditional schemes of evaluation of its scientific research.

Thus, the main research question of this doctoral study is:

How can scientific publishing practices be re-designed to enhance transparency and inclusivity in design knowledge production?

In the proposed approach, design cultures take a central role in the methodological and programmatic discourse on new practices in scientific publication, embracing results and scientific products that are not yet institutionalized and accredited.

It aims to answer the following sub-questions:

	Research sub-question	Sub-objective
OB 1.	What are the global trends and patterns of OA design journals and design knowledge production?	Analyze and comprehend the current state of OA design journals worldwide, identifying key trends, thematic focuses, and geographical disparities.
OB 2.	What are the key aspects and features of the current publishing industry that impact the design of scientific dissemination?	To identify and analyze the key stakeholders, economic and power dynamics within the publishing ecosystem and to examine how these dynamics impact design knowledge dissemination.
OB 3.	What role can distributed leadership play in enhancing pluriversality and fostering inclusivity and accessibility in design knowledge production?	To examine how adopting distributed leadership models can transform design publishing practices to support a more diverse and equitable representation of knowledge in design community.
OB 4.	What alternative assessment models in the current publishing system can be used to align assessment practices in design journals?	To identify and analyse existing alternative assessment models that align with the values of inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration within the design publishing ecosystem.

Tab I. Research questions.

Methodological Framework and Objectives

	OBJECTIVE	METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH
OB1.	<i>Analyze and comprehend the current state of OA design journals worldwide, identifying key trends, thematic focuses, and geographical disparities.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ° Desk research ° Mapping and comparative analysis of 92 OA design journals (Database of case studies) ° Qualitative interviews with editors of design journals ° Participatory approaches with focus group PRO.DES within the Italian Design Society
OB2.	<i>To identify and analyze the key stakeholders, economic and power dynamics within the publishing ecosystem and to examine how these dynamics impact design knowledge dissemination.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ° Desk research ° Qualitative interviews with experts from the publishing ecosystem ° Analysis of case studies ° Participatory approaches with the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association ° Direct observation with MIT Press and Knowledge Futures platform
OB3.	<i>To examine how adopting distributed leadership models can transform design publishing practices to support a more diverse and equitable representation of knowledge in design community.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ° Desk research ° Qualitative interviews with experts ° Analysis of case studies ° Participatory approaches within focus group PRO.DES with the Italian Design Society ° Experimentation with the Proceedings of the 8th International Forum Design as a Process
OB4.	<i>To identify and analyse existing alternative assessment models that align with the values of inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration within the design publishing ecosystem.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ° Desk research ° Qualitative interviews with experts ° Comparative Analysis of case studies ° Analysis of editorial processes in the design journal diid.disegno industriale industrial design and the Commonplace Journal ° Action research for the prototyping of the Collaborative Revision Model on publishing infrastructures

Tab II. Objectives and Methodological Tools.

The research employs a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, including desk research, case studies, interviews with experts, and comparative analysis of existing data.

The chosen methodology aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state of the scientific production landscape in the design field. As presented in the diagram, the methodological framework is structured into four interconnected levels that guide the research approach. The first level, **Research in Design** (Eckert et al., 2004), situates the research within the broader context of design disciplines. It acknowledges the complexity of design as both a practice and a research domain, providing the theoretical foundation for defining design as the “Third Culture” and the consequent implications on the publishing process. The second level, **Epistemological Approach** (Yee, 2010), addresses the epistemological interpretation of the hypothesis and provides detailed insights into the ways of disseminating knowledge within design cultures and their interaction with scientific publishing processes. In the third level, **Ethnographic Strategy** (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000), the research strategy is informed by ethnographic methods, focusing on observing, describing, and analyzing the interactions and dynamics within the publishing ecosystem. This level highlights the researcher’s participatory role and engagement with the research subject. The fourth level, **Research Tools**, involves the practical tools employed in the research, such as interviews, direct observations, comparative analyses of case studies, participatory approach, and first-hand experimentation, each tailored to specific phases of the research. These four levels create a layered methodological structure that, through practical research tools, represents the foundation of this research. Each sub-objective was achieved through a specific methodological set consisting of qualitative and quantitative research tools.

As shown in Table 2, the methodological framework is diverse and based on different approaches. The combination of qualitative and quantitative, desk research, mapping, comparative analysis, experimentation, interviews, and networking, provides a comprehensive analysis of the evolving dynamics in the field of design scientific production and publishing ecosystem.

Fig. 1: Research structure. By the Author.

Research Outputs

OBJECTIVE	RESEARCH OUTPUT
OB 01.	1. The Design Research Journal Database A comparative matrix and analysis of 92 OA design journals
OB 02.	2. Visualization of the Publishing Ecosystem ; 3. List of Stakeholders in the Publishing Ecosystem
OB 03.	4. Manifesto of Principles Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing
OB 04.	5. Prototype of a peer review model that integrates principles of transparency, collaboration, and openness (Co.Re Model)

Tab III: Research Outputs.

Considering that the goal of the research is to acknowledge the challenges posed by the traditional system over the design publishing processes, the research presents several key outputs. Each output reflects a specific objective of the research process, and it aims to address areas of concern for the design publishing and to raise awareness regarding the needs and perspectives of the scientific design community identified through focus groups and interviews with design scholars. They are structured into practical research deliverables, resulting from a combination of empirical data, theoretical exploration and practical application.

Research Structure

As shown in the diagram, the structure of the research is organized into five main chapters, clustered into three parts. A focus on the challenges and issues faced in the assessment process runs in parallel throughout each chapter. The general focus on advancing assessment models is filtered and tailored according to the specific topics of the chapters and culminates in the final chapter (Chapter 5) with the prototyping of an alternative peer review model. The first part aims to set and contextualise the research in the historical and current publishing landscape of design cultures. The second part analyses the challenges of the publishing ecosystem and interconnected dynamics among its stakeholders, proposing the concept of distributed leadership as a model to enhance inclusivity and pluriversality. Finally, building on the results of the previous

chapter, the third part focuses on the experimentation and applicative phase of the research, describing the prototyping of the Collaborative Revision (Co.Re) Model.

Part 1: Contextual and Comparative Analysis

Chapter 1: The Historical Evolution of Design Publishing: a Literature Review

This chapter provides a broad literature review on the assumption of the design discipline as a "Third Culture" and how the language used by design to disseminate its research results differs from other scientific disciplines. The methodologies used here include desk research and interviews to establish a fundamental understanding of the roots and current state of design knowledge production. The chapter reports on the current needs of the scientific community and how design publishing can actually serve the community to address these demands in the current state of the art of the design discipline. The outcomes were validated through two interviews conducted with two editors in chief of prominent design journals: Louise Valentine of *The Design Journal*, and Carl Di Salvo, of *Design Issues Journal*.

Chapter 2: The Design Research Journal Database

The second chapter builds on a comparative analysis, developed from the mapping of 92 OA design journals and a full analysis of the selected journals based on 17 criteria (all the analysis forms of the 92 journals are attached as appendices). The journals have been clustered based on their geographical affiliation: Europe, South America, Asia, North America, Africa and Australia. The section provides the methodology of the analysis, limitations and a general image of the innovation trajectories of the journals under analysis. It represents the core of the evaluation focus of the study, analyzing both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of these journals. The methodology used in this chapter relies on a comparative analysis of selected case studies and a final elaboration of the data gathered. It is relevant to point out that considering the geographical affiliation of this research to the Italian context, the research has dedicated a specific focus to the Italian design journals and publishing context.

Part 2: Analytical and Participatory Insights

Chapter 3: Power and Economic Dynamics in Publishing Ecosystem and Implication on Design

This chapter investigates the power dynamics within the design publishing ecosystem through direct observation, exploring

how economic and institutional forces shape the design community's access to publishing opportunities. This chapter identifies the stakeholders of this ecosystem and highlights the criticalities of traditional structures through a qualitative approach based on desk research, interviews and the voices and case studies of the scientific community. This chapter methodologically relies on the direct observation carried out through the collaboration with the Partnership Team of the Knowledge Futures¹ organization in the United States, where part of this research has been conducted. This experience has been highly significant in observing closely the dynamics between researchers, publishers, and publishing infrastructure technology providers. Eight interviews have been performed during the research semester abroad:

Louise Valentine, Editor in Chief of *The Design Journal*

Carl DiSalvo, Co-Editor of *Design Issues* journal

Laura Hanscom, Head of Scholarly Communications and Collections Strategy at *MIT Library*

Nick Lindsay, Head of Journals and OA at *MIT Press*

Rebecca McLeod, Managing Director at *Harvard Data Science Review*

Prachee Avasthi, Co-founder & CSO at *Arcadia Science*

Sarah Kember, Professor of New Technologies of Communication at Goldsmiths University of London and Director of *Goldsmiths Press*.

Paolo Manghi, Chief Technology Officer of OpenAIRE AMKE.

Chapter 4: Distributed Leadership and Pluriversality in Design Ecosystem

The methodological framework of the fourth chapter focuses on more participatory approaches and practice-based discussions of design, along with theoretical desk research. Starting from the definition of distributed leadership in publishing, it analyzes how distributed leadership can promote pluriversality and inclusiveness in the production of design knowledge, contributing to more equitable publishing practices. Based on the experimentation in the 8th Forum Design as a Process of the Latin Network, it demonstrates the potential of rethinking publishing workflows to enhance inclusivity and fairness in knowledge dissemination. The chapter concludes by offering a Manifesto of Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity

¹ Knowledge Futures is an independent nonprofit organisation powered by academic, industry, and advocacy groups; it aims to support products and protocols to make knowledge open and accessible to all. Founded in 2018 as a partnership between the MIT Press and the MIT Media Lab, Knowledge Futures was created to build sustainable tools and technologies for libraries, presses, museums, activist organisations, researchers, and others whose knowledge work seeks to serve collective understanding and the public.

in Design Publishing, developed through a community-led and collaborative approach of a Publishing Alliance.

Part 3: Prototyping

Chapter 5: Alternative Peer Review Models

The last chapter focuses on the vertical study of the peer review process and its critical issues, based on the state-of-the-art of reviewers' recognition and the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic publishing. Hence, it presents a case study analysis of alternative peer review platforms, which represents the basis for the prototyping and experimentation of an alternative peer review model, called the Co.Re (Collaborative Revision) Model. This model has been experimented at the nonprofit organisation Knowledge Futures during the research semester abroad carried out in the US. It is significant to highlight that this analysis has been possible thanks to the direct observation of the editorial operations carried out as Associate Editor at the Design Journal: **diid.disegno industriale** *industrial design* on the Open Journal System (OJS) platform. Moreover, the experimentation was performed on the Pub Pub platform², which represents the Knowledge Futures publishing infrastructure.

Conclusion and Future Research Directions

The study concludes by summarizing the findings of all three parts, discussing the broader implications of the research, its scalability, its limitations and critical issues, and finally, future directions of research.

² <https://www.pubpub.org/>

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**From Design
Practice to Design
Knowledge
Production:
Design as the
Third Culture**

This chapter establishes the research project's position within the scientific and theoretical framework of design knowledge. It examines the evolution of design knowledge from practical and craft-based traditions to a formal scientific discipline, emphasizing its impact on the language of dissemination (1.1, 1.2, 1.3). Central to this discussion is the concept of design as a "third culture," positioned between science and the humanities, which shapes both its epistemology and dissemination practices. The chapter traces the history of design dissemination back to architectural and industrial design magazines, which were among the first public platforms for sharing design ideas and innovations (2.3). Following the 20th-century debate on design as a science, scholarly publishing in design became standardized, leading to the establishment of the first scientific journals. Through interviews with Louise Valentine (Editor-in-Chief of *The Design Journal*) and Carl Di Salvo (Editor of *Design Issues*), the research explores the needs of the global design community and potential responses to them (2.4).

1 Introduction to Design Discipline: Interdisciplinarity/Multidisciplinarity/Crossdisciplinarity/Undisciplinarity

The term "discipline" derives from the Latin word "discipulus" (pupil) and "disciplina" (teaching). In the academic context, discipline signifies specific and rigorous training, turning practitioners into individuals "disciplined" by their field for their benefit (Krishnan, 2009). Michel Foucault views discipline, more broadly, as a political force that polices behaviours, excluding deviations from the norm, with individuals internalizing this "disciplining" (Foucault, 1975). The French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu (1984) argues a concept of academic discipline less associated with violence, which involves power relations and boundary maintenance, connecting discipline and power. The researcher Armin Krishnan (2009) from the University of Southampton, outlines six characteristics distinguishing academic disciplines: 1) a specific research object, 2) accumulated specialist knowledge, 3) effective organizing theories and concepts, 4) unique terminologies, 5) developed research methods, and 6) institutional manifestations in universities. These criteria of disciplinary distinction can represent a valuable method to fully assess the academic and scientific accomplishment of a disciplinary practice. Academic disciplines impose and express influence over the production and distribution of knowledge within the academic and intellectual landscapes. Becher and Trowler (2001) argue that disciplines establish standardized channels that help maintain academic credibility, while Lenoir (1997) supports the hypothesis that disciplines establish standardized channels that help maintain academic credibility influencing status and reward distribution. Turner (2000) and Whitley (2000) delve into the structure of disciplines as collective entities, organizing the allocation of rewards and positions in a form which is very similar to the labour market system, monopolizing contributions to intellectual

goals. Together these perspectives suggest that disciplines create structural boundaries, even though acknowledging the possibility of disciplinary knowledge to be extended into more inclusive and less formal controlled spaces

Fig. 1: Image inspired by the Keynote Speech of Sampsa Hyysalo at the European Academy Design (EAD) Conference, 16th October 2023, Espoo. By the Author.

For the purpose of this initial reasoning, it is significant to stress the relevance of practical experiences in scientific disciplines as foundational for research, through which knowledge is continuously tested and experiments. The transition from practice to knowledge allows research and individual experience to be generalised into knowledge (knowledge production) based on the results gathered during the practical experience, establishing a body of knowledge (research results) that be evaluated, shared and scaled. Through the dissemination of results, the knowledge produced evolves further, thanks to the encounter with the wider scientific community perspectives, contributing to a larger framework of a recognized area of study. Once this knowledge is codified into an educational formation (such as university courses) this knowledge becomes a discipline. The quadrangulation between practice - research - knowledge - discipline, outlined by researchers such as Schön (1983) and Bertola (Bertola & Maffei, 2009) and expanded by Nigel Cross (2006) discussing design discipline-specific methods, constitutes evidence of how practices are relevant to shape knowledge production and scientific disciplines over time.

Fig. 2: Design as a Central Component in Contemporary Design. Inspired by Design Without Disciplines, Bremner and Rodgers, 2013.

In its contemporary evolution, the scope of design has steadily expanded from material artifacts, graphics and interior spaces to include more immaterial aspects such as processes, systems, services, strategies, and even areas like cities, materials, food, travel, and health. Design has increasingly filtered across various disciplines, with many researchers and practitioners in creative fields adopting methods that are rooted in or related to design practices (Cross, 2006) due to its ability to provide solutions to socio-cultural issues outside the specific and conventional understanding of academic communities. Design now influences business strategies and decision-making processes (Rodgers & Bremner, 2017). The reason behind this expansion lies in the search for solutions to some old problems (or wicked problems, as defined by Buchanan, 1992) which may be transferred to another science or even declared "unscientific" (Kuhn, 1962). The state of the art in design, by proposing these solutions, reshapes the disciplinary boundaries of the problem. This assumption suggests that the solution itself is not the answer to the problem but rather the process that opens the question to the cognitive cultural learning needs inherent in the evolutionary processes of knowledge.

The expansion of the design field has led to the blending of design with other fields like fine art, engineering, anthropology, computer science, and business. Professional boundaries are now fluid, and it is common to see overlapping patterns across different design sub-disciplines. The distinction between product and service design, for instance, is increasingly blurred. Overall, design is now characterized by its flexibility and ability to cross disciplinary borders, leading to constant evolution in design research, education, and practice (Rodgers & Bremner, 2017). According to Tony Dunne, new hybrids of design have emerged (in Rodgers & Bremner, 2017), where individuals often embody a mix of artists, engineers, designers, and thinkers, rather than fitting neatly into one category. The debates surrounding disciplinarity in design are longstanding, with numerous scholars (Dykes et al. 2009; Bremner & Rodgers, 2013) exploring its role across various design fields, including architecture and engineering. Dykes, Rodgers, and Smyth (2009) developed a new disciplinary framework aimed at clarifying and mapping emerging forms of design practice. This framework seeks to better identify and define activities, outputs, and educational models in these evolving design practices, emphasizing the importance of disciplinary structures in facilitating new research and educational approaches in design.

The Munich Design Charter (1991) positions European design between technological and humanistic aspects of culture:

"In terms of its genesis, design has always been deeply concerned with all parts of contemporary life: with economy as well as ecology, with traffic and communication, with products and services, with technology and innovation, with culture and civilization, with sociological, psychological, medical, physical, environmental, and political issues, and with all forms of social organization. Given its complexity, design has thus meant working on history, on the present, and on the future." (The Munich Design Charter, 1991)

The nature of design is undergoing a fundamental shift (Sanders, 2017), as contemporary projects demand "undisciplined" designers who can blur the boundaries between social, economic, and political spheres and move from "discipline-based" to "issue- or project-based" methods (Rodgers & Bremner, 2017).

Furthermore, design's evolving role raises key questions about its status as a discipline. Archer (1979) posed crucial questions about whether design could be considered a discipline and, if so, what its defining characteristics might be. He argued that design has its way of thinking and communicating, distinct from scientific or scholarly approaches and operating through modelling rather than language or notation. This distinctiveness invites reflection on the kinds of methodologies and applications design should pursue and what problems it should address in research and practice. Over the past few decades, design research has shifted from an aspiration to create a "design science" to establish a more coherent "design discipline" (Cross, 2007); this discussion is explored below in the following paragraphs when discussing the historical evolution of scientific design publishing. In conclusion, as design continues to expand disciplinary boundaries and integrate with other fields, its history, methodologies, and future role must be critically examined. Its evolution from a practical craft to an academic discipline has reflected a broader shift toward the formalization and institutionalization of design in contemporary society. As outstandingly explained by Bremner & Rodgers (2013) traditional disciplinarity may no longer make design innovative or valuable in the way it once did; this shift involves navigating a new form of universalism characterized by translations and reinterpretations. Traditional disciplinarity, which resists trends, represents a deeper understanding of how we perceive and live in the world.

¶ Shifts in Design Knowledge: Signals

According to vom Brocke et. al. (2020), design knowledge can be represented in different forms, such as designed artefacts, design principles or design theories. As such, design knowledge has been described to take different forms, among them, the implementation of an artefact, an incipient or well-developed design theory. Thus, design is a discipline that is at the intersection of knowledge of the properties of physical objects and knowledge of human behaviour, and it is possible that design theories may take on a form different from those in other disciplines (Vitta & Nelles 1985). Based on this assumption, many researchers have questioned whether relying on traditional publications through conferences and journals seems adequate (Diaz et al. 2022). According to the researchers Díaz, Venable & Garmendia (2022), the misuse of Design Science Research results significantly reduces the impact of projects and hinders knowledge growth. This issue is primarily social and influenced by standard communication efforts. While journals and repositories can make high-quality design knowledge and design

artefacts accessible, additional dissemination methods may be more effective in promoting adoption and fostering its accumulation across multiple design research projects.

Given these changes, there is a need to reframe how design knowledge is produced, communicated, and assessed. The traditional models of how design is perceived and implemented must adapt to this new landscape, problematising academic rules and standards, towards a more dynamic and practice-based approach that responds to the issues of globalization. This concept aligns with the understanding that design research and practice must acknowledge and reflect these diverse and evolving dimensions of knowledge. This perspective supports the aim of my research project, which aims to explore and raise awareness concerning new methodologies for knowledge dissemination within the design field, recognizing the necessity for flexibility and innovation in how design knowledge is perceived.

1.2 The Eternal Dilemma: Scientific Evolution of Design Discipline as “The Third Area”

The traditional dichotomy in education, which divides it into Science and the Humanities, overlooks a vast realm of human activity that does not neatly fit into either category. This oversight reflects a gap in how we structure learning and how we recognize certain disciplines. Design, as a discipline, has long struggled to find its place within this dichotomy. The tension stems from its position at the intersection of the practical and the theoretical, blending elements of both art and science but adhering to neither fully. According to Flusser (2003), the term “design” fills a gap between art and technology, serving as an indicator of the joint expressions of the two disciplines and giving rise to a “third culture.” Design is a complex word, implying not only a technical term but also a design intention (Flusser, 2003). This “third culture” is seen as an interdisciplinary synthesis, a place of dialogue between disciplines (Snow, 1961; Brockman, 1995; Lingiard and Vassallo, 2011), in which design takes concrete and abstract forms and represents various languages.

When Sir William Curtis coined the phrase '**The Three Rs**' around 1807, he highlighted the emphasis placed on literacy and numeracy, which shaped the Humanities and Sciences, respectively. However, the third 'R,' defined by Curtis as "*wroughting and wrighting*," addressed the practical, hands-on aspects of knowledge – what we might now call technology and craftsmanship. This practical component, or the "doing and making" that defines design, has been largely excluded from the educational framework built around the Sciences and Humanities. Although scientific and literary language are distinct, there is a parallel in design methods. Gregory (1966) points out that while the scientific method is analytic and oriented toward the discovery of reality, the design method is constructive, aimed at inventing what does not yet exist: "Science is analytic; design is constructive." This approach to the design method makes

it a generative matrix capable of producing narratives as design objects, the result of specific design skills. Moreover, the material culture – everything from the buildings that construct our cities to the artefacts that fill museums – demands that the practical arts be recognized as a distinct area of human endeavour, one that is neither purely scientific nor purely humanistic.

According to Archer (1979), Design, when considered as this "third area," can thus be seen as a unique educational domain that fills the gaps left by Science and the Humanities. Unlike Science, which is focused on theory and generalizable knowledge, or the Humanities, which express human values and the human spirit, Design is rooted in application—responding to material and spiritual needs through the manipulation of man-made phenomena. In this sense, design is not merely an abstract concept or a technical practice; it is a method of interacting with and adapting the world around us, using configuration, composition, meaning, and purpose as its core concepts.

Fig. 3: The relationships between the three areas of human knowledge according to Bruce Archer (1979).

According to Archer, what diversifies Design from the other two scientific areas is its *essential language*: modelling. While the Sciences rely on mathematical notation and the Humanities on natural language, Design uses models as representations of ideas. These models – whether in the form of an artist’s painting or a mime’s gesture – serve as tools to explore, communicate, and materialize abstract concepts. In this way, Design transcends the limitations of Science and the Humanities, offering a bridge between the two through its practical representation and realization of ideas. This positions Design as an educational discipline in its place, deserving recognition as a “*third area*” that integrates theory and practice, thought and action. To effectively communicate any discipline, it’s essential to understand the unique language it uses. The sciences rely on mathematical notation, to express precise, measurable ideas. The humanities, on the other hand, employ natural language, particularly written language, to share cultural values and philosophical reflections. Supporting the multimodal approach of design, Manuela Celi and Francesca Rizzo (2016) argue that while design has based its expressive capacity on visualization, notation, sketching, and the production of diagrams, it often uses narrative to construct representations that can tell future projects.

Therefore, it is possible to affirm that design communicates through modelling. Understanding these distinct “languages” of disciplinary narration is key to knowledge dissemination. Science, humanities, and design require specialized communication approaches to ensure their ideas are understood and disseminated. This highlights the importance of developing the right communication strategies for each discipline so that its ideas can be shared effectively.

Design: As a Third Culture sits between the two poles of science and the humanities and is at the heart of questions related to feasibility, viability and desirability.

Fig. 4: Diagram by Terry Irwin, 2015. Based upon the Helsinki Design Lab, “Recipes for Systemic Design”.

In Mareis' (2012) discussion on practice-based design research, she explores the complexities surrounding the methodology that integrates practical design activities into academic inquiry. This approach reveals challenges related to the communication and articulation of knowledge generated through design practices, often leading to debates about the inter-subjective and objective communicability of research findings. Mareis (2012) also references Bourdieu's concept of *habitus*, questioning whether designers struggle to verbally express their practical knowledge due to normative language constraints or if this limitation reflects deeper issues in design education and practice. Flaviano Celaschi (2008) formulated the model of design as a mediator of knowledge and needs, defining the traits of a discipline that settles halfway between four systems of knowledge traditionally difficult to dialogue with each other: art/creativity, technology/engineering, economics and management, and the humanities. This is precisely where this research project is theoretically positioned: at the intersection of disciplines, acknowledging the distinct nature of design knowledge and its divergence from the languages of science and the humanities. While the primary aim of this project is not to delve into these disciplinary boundaries, this framework provides a contextual foundation for exploring effective methods to communicate and assess design knowledge. In the following section, the research explores the historical development of scientific dissemination in design by first offering a concise overview of the evolution of scholarly communication practices.

2 Scientific Production and Design Publishing: Roots

The research aims to explore the current form of the scientific journal by providing a historical context tracing the roots of scientific communication, spanning from its origins until the transformative Scientific Revolution in the 16th and 17th centuries. Subsequently, it delves into an examination of the pivotal role of printing as an early exemplar of a 'communications technology' (Mackenzie Owen, 2005) and discusses its profound significance for the field of science. The narrative progresses to illuminate the evolution of the scientific journal as the predominant medium for formal scientific discourse.

This contextual framework is essential for understanding the origins of scientific communication, enabling researchers to trace its historical development and significance in the design discipline; as evidenced by the interviews with the experts from the design community Louise Valentine (Editor in Chief of *The Design Journal*) and Carl di Salvo (Editor of the *Design Issues*). Furthermore, it helps situate contemporary practices within current disciplinary contexts, particularly for design, a field that has seen interdisciplinary shifts and requires an understanding of how formalized modes of scholarly exchange have shaped knowledge production and dissemination. In

this light, exploring the roots of scientific communication is critical to comprehending its relevance to the evolving nature of design scholarship.

2.1 The Historical Context: the Scientific Revolution

The historical narrative about the origins of scientific publishing starts with the invention of the printing press in the 15th century, commonly referred to as the 'Gutenberg revolution'. Although scientists may not overtly critique the current state, some express optimism about the transformative potential of technology (Eisenstein, 1979). Steven Bachrach (2000), for instance, notes that despite societal changes, scientific communication remains entrenched in the traditional written articles published in scientific journals. Initially, knowledge transfer was oral, with messengers delivering information face-to-face (Shapin, 2010). The earliest scientific communication involved handwritten documents and their printed successors consolidating authorized knowledge (Johns, 2000). Scientific communication, as we know it today, emerged in the mid-17th century when scientific societies, rather than universities, pioneered a significant innovation: using the printing press for the exchange and discussion of new empirical research through periodical, subscription-based publications (Kronick, 1962). Modern science has developed through what is commonly known as the Scientific Revolution of the 17th century. Since the 17th century and the start of the Revolution, it has been conventional to conceptualize science as an 'open' communicative framework characterized by the broad dissemination of ideas and research findings. This openness allowed for unrestricted examination, criticism, and discussion. Essential to this concept is a structured system of scientific communication, serving distinct functions such as distribution, access, and preservation (Shapin & Schaffer, 1985). This system also functions as a social framework, as individuals excluded from this communicative structure are unable to participate as members of the scientific community (Collins, 1998).

However, universities did not embrace in-house printing fast; in the realm of publishing, the most successful collaborations were built on a direct association between scholars and printers. Mackenzie Owen (2005) claims that the impact of printing on academia was initially more quantitative than qualitative, resulting more in consolidation than in innovation; in this sense, the printing press did not immediately create a new practice. Eamon (1994) argues that the important function of the printing press was not that it facilitated the dissemination of research output, but that it enhanced access to data sources in the input phase of research. Since it required a considerable amount of time to create a significant body of data in printed form, it is understandable that the print 'revolution' in the domain of science was a relatively slow process.

2.2 The Birth of the Scientific Article: The Fundamental Role of Scientific Societies

The printed book, despite its innovative impact on knowledge dissemination, was unable to fully adapt to the accelerating pace, complexity, and international scope of modern scientific advancements (Eisenstein, 1979). The limitations of static print media became evident as the dynamic, diverse, and global nature of contemporary scientific communication required faster, more flexible formats to accommodate new developments and interdisciplinary collaborations. Recognizing this limitation, alternative communication methods emerged in the early 17th century. Scholars relied on personal networks, involving extensive travel, face-to-face meetings, lectures, and, aided by the advent of postal services, the exchange of letters. Face-to-face communication evolved into institutionalized forms through the establishment of “scientific societies”.

Fig. 5: The diagram summarizes which characteristics of the Scientific Societies' Forums were reflected in the shaping of the scientific article. By the Author.

Within these societies, the dissemination of scientific and technical letters was institutionalized, with society officials collecting and distributing information to members. Some examples, currently still relevant to the global scientific discourse, are the Royal Society of London, St. Petersburg Academy of Sciences, Royal Swedish Academy, Royal Society of Edinburgh, Royal Irish Academy, Letterkunde en Schoone Kunsten in Amsterdam and the Koninklijk Instituut van Wetenschappen. There was a clear need for institutions that bridged university and non-university realms, fostering collaboration across diverse scientific fields. These institutions embraced innovative approaches, from unconventional publication methods to modern scientific expeditions, showcasing an expansive and outward-looking vision for organizing scientific endeavours.

Fig. 6: Journal Article. *A Letter of Benjamin Franklin, Esq; to Mr. Peter Collinson, F. R. S. concerning an Electrical Kite*. Benjamin Franklin, in *Philosophical Transactions* (1683–1775), Vol. 47 (1751 – 1752), pp. 565–567.

The first issue of the *Journal des Sçavans* was published in Paris in January of the year 1665; in 1665, Henry Oldenburg, the secretary of the Royal Society in London, established and financed the *Philosophical Transactions* (Banks, 2009). This publication later served as the platform for Isaac Newton to communicate within a broader European 'information space'. A century after the launch of the *Philosophical Transactions*, scholarly journals grappled with delays between presentation and publication, language barriers, and the diverse range of subject matter (Gross et al., 2022). This led to the rise of specialized journals, addressing these challenges: the first specialized journals were in physics, chemistry and botany. During the 19th century, the growth of the new science within universities resulted in a substantial increase in scientific publishing, marked by

a surge in journal titles and published articles. Approximately 2 million scientific and technical papers were published during the century, leading to the establishment of a well-organized system involving scientific institutions, academic publishers, and university libraries. This growth also gave rise to specialized services such as bibliographies, annual reviews, and abstracting and indexing periodicals. The 20th century witnessed exponential growth in scientific literature, with a finer specialization of journals, the dominance of the article as the primary genre for formal scientific communication, the prevalence of English as the dominant scientific language, and the emergence of a limited number of large-scale, international academic publishing enterprises through mergers and acquisitions. In the second chapter, the research will analyze in-depth the economic and political dynamics underlying the current publishing system.

According to the International Science Council Report (2021), the norms and practices of scholarly publication vary significantly across disciplines, requiring publication systems to adapt to these diverse needs as they evolve. Traditional formats such as journals, books, and monographs are common, alongside newer forms like preprints, conference proceedings, and informal communication via blogs, videos, and social media. In STEM fields and many social sciences, journals with pre-publication peer review dominate (Chapter 2). However, disciplines like mathematics favor preprints, where papers are publicly available before formal peer review. Biomedical fields, known for their rigorous ethical standards, have called for reforms to address biases against publishing negative results. In computer science, presenting papers at prestigious conferences holds more value than journal publications, due to their selectivity and quicker review processes. This contrasts with disciplines like economics, where monographs hold significant importance. Disciplines like public health and law often prefer professional magazines. In philosophy, free online access to papers is common after journal acceptance, though this depends on licensing agreements with publishers. In the humanities, publication is less time-sensitive, with long-form and heavy text works (**Fig. 6**) like books or monographs being highly prestigious. Despite their high cost and challenges in digitalization, these formats remain central, as impact factors are less emphasized, though the hierarchy of journal status is still recognized. This diversity in publication practices highlights the need for flexible, responsive systems that reflect the varying requirements of different academic fields.

Fig. 7: Article retrieved from the Design Journal Stile Industria, No.1, June 1954.

Fig. 8: Article retrieved from the Design Journal Stile Industria, No.17, June 1958.

2.3 The Evolution of Design Scientific Dissemination over time

The shift began during the 20th-century Modernist movement and the "design methods movement" of the 1960s. The 1962 Conference on Design Methods in London¹ is often seen as the formal launch of design methodology as the legitimization of design as an area of research. The goal of this movement was to base design processes on objectivity, reflecting a desire to "scientise" design. The current interdisciplinarity and blurred complexity of design discipline, increasingly driven by technological developments and intersections with science, engineering, and research, support its transformation into a formal academic discipline. However, the relationship between design and research remains contested, with debates surrounding issues such as status, politics, and funding often complicating the discussion (Cross, 2007).

Starting from the analysis of a design publication milestone, such as the Design Discourse of Victor Margolin (1989) published by the University Chicago Press, it becomes evident the need to identify within the ecosystem of the design discourse debate through the different theories and research. In 1989, Margolin accused the writing about design of being very fragmental; moreover, he shed light on the role of a design scholar and how s/he can contribute to design professions. This inadequate recognition of design studies and the lack of promotion hinders the understanding of public audiences, which use, consume and buy design. With the object of mapping the field of design and organising the existing research so far (history – theory – criticism), Design Issues was funded in 1982. Design Issues was the first scholarly journal to commit to the interdisciplinarity of design. It supported the idea that if we recognize design as a more effective practice with broader influence, the knowledge about it has a greater value.

The debate generating most of the contemporary schools of thought is focused on the broader definition of design: Science of Design (Simon, 1988) or Culture of Design (Vitta & Nelles, 1985). Prominent researchers like Herbert Simon and Richard Buchanan represent two contrasting views on the role of design. Simon, in his influential work *The Sciences of the Artificial* (1996), emphasizes that design should be considered a science, focusing on decision-making processes, the empirical study of design outcomes, and identifying causal factors. Simon's approach suggests that design practitioners benefit from a scientific framework that enables them to make more accurate and effective design choices, grounded in facts rather than assumptions. On the other hand, Buchanan, in his work *Wicked Problems in Design Thinking* (1992), argues that design should be understood as a liberal art rather than a science. He roots design discourse in the humanities, considering it a form of contemporary rhetoric. Buchanan's view is that design serves to communicate beliefs and provoke actions through argument, emphasizing the interpretative dimensions of design rather than its

¹ The conference was held from 19th to 21st September 1962 at the Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College, London, UK.

scientific rigor. This contrast between Simon's scientific approach and Buchanan's perspective highlights the ongoing debate in the field of design about whether it should align with empirical, science-based methods or position itself in the field of the arts and humanities. As comprehensively analysed by Paola Bertola (2009), while the approach initiated by Simon (1969) has the merit of fostering design into the university as an object of study and research, it also reveals its own contradictions and limits of application in the real context of professional practice. For this reason, the recent debate has drawn a new balance between the two extreme theses of design seen as an individual attitude similar to art and design understood as science. This more balanced view of design highlights its ability to produce knowledge but through its own ways that do not necessarily reproduce scientific ones in the positivist sense. Research in design thus begins to be interpreted through a phenomenological perspective, that is, observing the reality of design in order to extract general rules and principles from it.

While this debate has been central to shaping modern understandings of design, this doctoral research does not focus nor engage with this debate. Instead, the aim is to explore how this foundational debate has influenced the communication, dissemination, and evaluation of design outputs, especially within the context of meeting scientific standards. The tension between these two perspectives has shaped the theoretical landscape of design and also played a significant role in determining the criteria by which design research is published, evaluated, and recognized within scholarly communities. By examining how these contrasting approaches have affected the development of design journals, review processes, and the dissemination of design knowledge, this research seeks to provide insights into how design as a discipline perceives its disciplinary identity in relation to scientific and scholarly standards. This analysis is fundamental for understanding the ongoing challenges and opportunities in how design research is communicated and validated nowadays. Thus, while not engaging in this theoretical debate, this research critically considers its impact on design scholarship and the ways design outputs are shared with the academic community.

Reflecting on Archer's assertion that design language is fundamentally about "modelling," it's no coincidence that the earliest design magazines were high-quality publications that celebrated contemporary residential architecture and its human side a rich use of imagery, drawings, and photographs, making visual representation a central component of their communication (**Fig. 7** and **Fig. 8**). The emphasis on visual storytelling, in essence, reflected the idea that design is a form of modelling reality, conveying abstract ideas and tangible spaces through highly curated visual media. Throughout the history of design, several magazines and journals have significantly contributed to the dissemination and communication of design knowledge. Hereby, a short selection of magazines have shaped the design dissemination between the early

20th century and the 90s. These publications, through their editorial approaches, have captured contemporary trends and set new directions for the field. The methodology for selecting influential design magazines and journals from the early 20th century to 1970 is rooted in a qualitative approach. This chronological selection emphasizes exemplary publications that have significantly shaped design discourse rather than attempting to create an exhaustive list. By focusing on various contexts, the research particularly highlights Italian magazines and journals, reflecting Italy's critical role in the design landscape during this period. Each selected magazine or journal is examined for its thematic focus, editorial approach, and contributions to the field.

The STUDIO - 1893

A significant early design publication, *The Studio* played a pivotal role in the Arts and Crafts movement and modernist design, highlighting aesthetics and craftsmanship in the visual arts.

ARCHITECTURAL REVIEW - 1896

The *Architectural Review* is an active publication covering contemporary global architecture. It was established in 1896 and is published 10 times a year. The publication serves as a leading international forum for the critique and analysis of architecture, emphasizing the critical examination of contemporary architectural practices, seeking to inspire professionals in the field with innovative designs and theoretical discussions. Coverage includes subjects such as urban design, landscape architecture, environmental sustainability.

DOMUS - 1928

Domus is one of the most influential voices in contemporary design and architecture. As well as detailed coverage of projects and in-depth profiles of influential architects and designers, *Domus* features theoretical pieces, criticism and intellectual debates. Between 1950 and 1970, the magazine represented the story of new objects and new spaces (D'Uffizzi, 2023). Over time, there has been a notable increase in the use of visual content and graphic design, which has demonstrated its significant communicative and evocative power. As Mario Piazza observed, "*It is the graphics that modelled and made visible a symbolic universe through which consumers encountered the product.*" Even though the publication is now indexed as a scientific journal in the Italian educational database (ANVUR), the magazine continues to retain its original graphic features and the same visual approach.

CASABELLA - 1928

Casabella is a monthly Italian architectural and product design magazine with a focus on modern, radical design and architecture. Over its history[1], *Casabella* has featured influential figures like Franco Albini, Gae Aulenti, and Marco Zanuso, as well as international designers such as Tomás Maldonado. In January 2017, the magazine underwent a redesign, updating its cover and layout. Alongside its traditional section dedicated to book reviews and discussions, it introduced new sections focusing on professionals and industry news, project drawings and plans, and design history. *Casabella* is indexed as

a scientific journal in the Italian National Database (ANVUR).

ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN – 1930

Also known as AD, is a UK-based architectural journal. With an almost unrivalled reputation worldwide, it is consistently at the forefront of cultural thought and design. Since 2000, it has been edited by the Wiley Publishing Group and has transitioned into being recognized as a scientific journal, a testament to its influence in both academic and professional spheres.

GRAPHIS – 1944

The Graphis Magazine, spanning from 1944 to 2005, delve into the rich history of visual communications, exploring the evolution of Graphic Design, Illustration, Photography, and Advertising. It encompasses renowned artists, visionary creatives, and thought-

provoking editorial content from around the globe. With a rich history and commitment to the design and visual communications industry, Graphis unites all creative disciplines

including Design, Advertising, Photography, and Illustration Art under one roof, representing global industry influences, culture, and trends.

DESIGN QUARTERLY – 1946

Published by the Walker Art Center, *Design Quarterly* was a key platform for design theory, exploring topics in architecture, graphic design, and industrial design. It featured prominent designers and theorists, influencing design discourse throughout the 20th century.

ID – 1954

ID: The International Design Magazine was pivotal in industrial design,

covering

product design, branding, and sustainability. It was influential in shaping the understanding of design as a commercial and cultural practice.

STILE INDUSTRIALE – 1955

Founded in January 1955, The year before, Alberto Rosselli had founded the magazine as an offshoot of *Domus*, driven by the conviction that architects and designers should be concerned with the form of all things industrial. *Stile Industria* was the only Italian magazine dedicated solely to industrial design and

played a key part in establishing industrial design as a discipline.. At a time when Gio Ponti, the editor of Domus, was giving space mainly to interiors and products crafted by artisans in small numbers, and when Ernesto Nathan Rogers, editor of Casabella, was focusing on architecture, Rosselli chose to devote his research to mass production².

FORM- 19657

A German design magazine, Form has focused on product and industrial design, serving as a crucial reference for critical discussions on contemporary design practice, craftsmanship, and functionality.

ABITARE - 1961

Abitare magazine, published monthly in Milan, Italy, is a design magazine. It was first published in 1961 by Piera Peroni. It was devoted to architecture, interior design, furniture, product design and graphic arts and was published in both Italian and English. The magazine temporarily ceased print publication in March 2014. However, its

online version continued to publish content when the magazine was relaunched with a new format and graphics under the editorship of Silvia Botti.

OTTAGONO - 1966

Ottagono magazine of architecture, furniture and industrial design was a magazine on architecture, furniture and design published by Editrice Compositori. Founded in 1966 by the collaboration of eight historic brands of Italian-based design Arflex, Artemide, Bernini, Boffi, Cassina, FLOS, ICF DePadova, and Tecno-it

² <http://kvadratinterwoven.com/stile-industria>

has been a landmark magazine for the world of design and architecture. In 1979 the magazine was awarded the "Compasso d'Oro," the prize of the Industrial Design Association. The magazine discontinued its issues at the end of 2014.

VISIBLE LANGUAGE - 1967

Focused on typography, communication, and semiotics, *Visible Language* was one of the first academic journals dedicated to design research, offering critical essays on the intersection of design and language.

MODO - 1977

Modo was an Italian design magazine published from 1977 to 2006 by the Milan-based publishing house Ricerche e Design Editrice (R.D.E). Founded in 1977 by Valerio Castelli, Giovanni Cutolo and Alessandro Mendini, a leading exponent of Italian radical design. For 28 years, the monthly magazine has been a

spokesman for Italian and international design culture (the subtitle, chosen by Mendini, is Rivista di cultura del progetto), always preserving an attitude of stimulation and curiosity about new trends, often placing itself in contradiction with current ideas, with polemical and provocative intent.

BLUEPRINT - 1983

A British magazine focusing on architecture, design, and urbanism, *Blueprint* offers

critical perspectives on the built environment, influencing contemporary discussions on design's role in society.

In the 1970s, the debate about the need to formalize and scientificise the design discipline led to foundational changes in how design was perceived by the academic communities. This movement aimed at establishing design as a legitimate area of scientific research, shifting an only-practice-based discipline to one that develops research methodologies. The actors of this transformation, both scholars and practitioners, began to recognize the value of research-based outputs and the importance of academic publication as a means of disseminating knowledge. This led to the establishment of a new wave of scientific design journals, which adopted traditional scientific methodologies to validate their findings: empirical studies, peer review, and structured articles. The conventional way of publication that these journals implemented supported the validation of design as an academic discipline and facilitated the disciplinary cross-pollination between design and other scientific fields such as engineering, psychology, and the social sciences, reinforcing the interdisciplinary nature of design research. During this period key design journals were established, which still play a central role in the scholarly conversation in design today, such as *Design Issues* (1984) and *Journal of Design History* (1988). In the next chapter, the research will offer an in-depth analysis of the open-access design journals worldwide (the *Design Research Journal Database*). As mentioned in Paragraph 2.2, also in the design field, the role of scientific societies has been crucial to design knowledge evolution. These organisations have served as venues of discussion, exchange and dissemination of diverse perspectives within the discipline, contributing to the advancement of the research field and the recognition of design as a field of study. Primarily, they have been central in bridging the gap between academia and industry, enhancing the cross-over between theoretical advancements and real-world applications. They can be accredited for elevating design within academic and professional communities. Their role in design knowledge dissemination has become evident and they currently promote a culture of investigation and innovation of today's global challenges. Notable examples include the *American Institute of Graphic Arts (AIGA)*, which has promoted design standards and education; the *Industrial Designers Society of America (IDSA)*, which has advanced industrial design through research and advocacy; and the *Royal Society of Arts (RSA)* in the UK, which has supported the intersection of design, social innovation, and policy. Additionally, the *Society of Graphic Designers of Canada (GDC)* has played a significant role in establishing design as a professional discipline in Canada. *Design Research Society (DRS)*, which focuses on advancing design research and education; *IDEO*, focusing on human-centred design and innovation; and the *World Design Organization (WDO)*, which promotes design's role in social and economic development.

It is significant for the contribution to the participatory approach implemented in this doctoral research, to mention the Italian context, where specifically the Italian Society of Design was established in 2013 to promote design cultures and design research in Italy.

2.4 Fast-forward: is Design Publishing serving the Community? Insight from Experts

A significant role of this research is played by an in-depth interview with Louise Valentine, Editor-in-Chief of *The Design Journal*, which offers a critical perspective on how scientific publishing is currently addressing the needs of the design community, and Carl di Salvo, Editor of *Design Issues*, which discusses the challenges currently facing the journal. Both have been invited in their capacity as experts, holding multiyear editorial and practice experience, able to provide a unique perspective on the evolving landscape of design publishing.

The interview with **Louise Valentine** explores key trends in digital publishing, particularly those aimed at improving the reading experience in online formats. Valentine highlights the importance of inclusivity and transparency within design scholarship, stressing how these values are now central to the discipline. Moreover, Valentine discusses the emergence of non-traditional publishing formats that, while not strictly scientific, incorporate provocative elements designed to encourage researchers to experiment more freely with design practices. This flexibility fosters creativity and allows for a broader exploration of design methodologies, supporting the dynamic and evolving nature of the field. The integration of interactive and multimedia elements in digital publications is also noted as a key trend, aimed at enhancing reader engagement and enriching the dissemination of design knowledge. She also reflects on the peer review challenges associated with visual content, pointing out the need for a well-structured process to assess the visual aspects of articles. Furthermore, she advocates for fostering a broader perspective within the design research community by encouraging readers to engage with entire journal issues, rather than focusing on individual articles. Valentine concludes by underscoring the importance of maintaining high standards of excellence in academic design research while recognizing that these standards are constantly evolving in response to the changing nature of design practice and dissemination. The insights provided by Valentine serve as a critical framework for this research, helping to contextualize the broader trends in design communication and assess how such developments are shaping the evaluation of scholarly outputs within the discipline.

Carl Di Salvo, among the Editors of *Design Issues*, interviewed within the context of this doctoral research in April 2024, highlights very similar points of discussion when analysing future trends of design publishing ecosystem. He acknowledges that as design increasingly intersects with other fields like policy, governance, and artificial intelligence, it becomes difficult for the journal to maintain a coherent editorial scope. In addition, finding the right reviewers for such a broad range of topics presents a persistent challenge, as the field diversifies, and the pool of experts becomes more specialized. The peer review process at *Design Issues* is described as rigorous

but also flexible and supportive. The interviewee contrasts the journal's method with that of traditional scientific venues, such as computing journals, where reviewer scores often directly determine acceptance or rejection. At Design Issues, the editorial board plays a more involved role, reading and discussing all papers internally before sending them out for external review. This conversational and vision-driven approach helps to ensure that the journal not only maintains scholarly rigor but also supports the development of the design field. The review process is thus framed as both a collaborative and critical process, emphasizing the importance of editorial engagement. Di Salvo is cautious about predicting future trends but notes several developments worth watching, including the growing influence of AI in translation and publishing.

Building upon insights from both editors, the following chapter will examine the current publication trends in the design publishing ecosystem.

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Analysing Design Journals: The Design Research Journal Database (DRJD)

Building on the theoretical context of the previous section, this chapter proceeds to the mapping of 92 contemporary Design Journals indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) (1.1). This mapping provides a landscape view of design dissemination today, focusing on how these journals meet the demands of scientific standards, accessibility, inclusivity and assessment. Through comparative analysis (2.1), the chapter identifies key innovation trajectories and trends in design publishing (3), highlighting how design journals are incorporating new models of knowledge production and dissemination. These trajectories reflect both the ongoing tension between design as a scientific discipline and the interdisciplinary nature of design knowledge.

1 Mapping Scientific Design Publishing: Analyzing Open Access Design Journals

This research project proposes an original matrix and database for examining open-access design journals on a global scale. Inspired by the work of Perry and Soares Pereira (2023), who utilized bibliometric analysis to explore diversity and inclusivity in design research, this project diverges by opting for manual analysis rather than software automation. While the manual approach was considered less feasible by these authors, it enables a more nuanced, context-sensitive evaluation of design journals that might not be captured through automated means. The primary aim is to map and identify innovation trends and gaps in the dissemination of design knowledge while providing a comprehensive overview of open-access design journals worldwide.

Through established selection criteria, the database offers a detailed, manually-driven analysis of **92 design journals**, highlighting trends, impacts, and distinctive features in the design publishing landscape. This resource will be instrumental in uncovering dominant trends and key dynamics that shape the future of design dissemination, offering a critical perspective on the evolving nature of open-access design publications across various regions and sub-disciplines.

The rationale behind this research output includes several important goals:

- (1) Trend identification: the database allows for the identification of emerging trends and future directions in design.
- (2) Impact assessment: quantitative and qualitative analysis of journals allows the investigation of the impact and influence of publications.
- (3) Accessibility to knowledge: with a focus on open-access journals, the database promotes the dissemination of knowledge, breaking down barriers related to subscriptions.
- (4) Interdisciplinarity and connections: the tool highlights how design interacts with other disciplines such as engineering, social sciences, technology, architecture, fine arts, computer science, business and management, and many other scientific fields. This is critical to understanding the role of design in interdisciplinary contexts.
- (5) Supporting academic research: the database provides a vital reference for researchers and students, facilitating the discovery of relevant and quality journals for publication and reference.
- (6) Promoting diversity: analysis of diversity and inclusivity in publications helps assess how well journals represent global voices and diverse viewpoints, contributing to a more equitable and representative design landscape.

Methodology for data collection

The methodology adopted for this research is based on a systematic and inclusive approach to the analysis of scholarly journals in the field of design and design cultures. The selection of journals was made by considering their geographical affiliation, based on six macro-regions:

- North America
- South America
- Europe
- Italy
- Asia
- Africa
- Australia

As part of this research, a specific section for Italian academic journals has been reserved. This choice is motivated by the fact that the research project is conducted at an Italian university, making the inclusion of a special focus on the national academic production of design knowledge relevant and meaningful. This approach not only enriches the overall analysis but also provides a solid basis for developing further insights in the later stages of the research, exploring in detail the contributions of Italian journals to the field of design and design cultures. Such a distinction will shed light on specificities, trends and patterns peculiar to the Italian context, thus contributing to a deeper and more contextualized understanding of design dynamics locally and globally.

To conduct the research and collect data, the **DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)** database, recognized for its inclusiveness, ease of navigation and accessibility, was chosen (Brieflands, 2023; Ford Holder, 2022). The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a comprehensive, freely accessible database that indexes over 18,000 open-access journals from various disciplines, promoting peer-reviewed scholarship globally. It categorizes journals using the Library of Congress Classification system, with the largest representation in Medicine and Social Sciences. The database includes contributions from both university publishers and major commercial publishers like Elsevier and Wiley, and it features materials published in 80 different languages across 130 countries. DOAJ serves as a valuable resource for researchers evaluating or looking to publish in open-access journals. DOAJ represents a reliable and widely used resource in the academic community, as it overcomes the limitations of databases such as SCOPUS and Web of Science (WOS), which impose restrictive selection criteria and expensive application processes.

The choice of DOAJ is particularly significant because the database is dedicated exclusively to open-access journals¹, a crucial factor in ensuring the global dissemination and accessibility of research. Open access not only democratizes knowledge but also allows for

¹ <https://doaj.org/apply/seal/>

the inclusion of a wide range of regional and cultural perspectives, contributing to a more comprehensive and diverse understanding of academic disciplines. In addition, numerous studies emphasize (Sumathipala et al., 2004; Demeter et al., 2021) the importance of including journals from different parts of the world to avoid regional bias and promote a global perspective in scientific research. This methodology, which combines the use of an inclusive database such as DOAJ and a diverse geographic selection, ensures a broad and representative panorama of academic publications in the field of design.

Above all, the choice of DOAJ proves essential considering the criteria I selected to build the database of journals. Since one of the basic requirements is the ability to freely access content to ensure a broad and representative search, the use of open-access journals becomes essential. Journals requiring subscriptions would have limited access and make the comprehensive analysis I aim for impractical. The selection of DOAJ, with its focus on open access, allows for the construction of a database that meets the criteria of inclusiveness, transparency, and accessibility, and provides an accurate view of current trends and patterns in the field of design.

This research methodology includes a targeted selection of scholarly journals based not only on geographic origin but also on specific Subjects relevant to the field of design and design cultures. To reduce and select journals within the DOAJ database, the research has selected design journals intersecting with the following Subjects:

- **Fine Arts: Drawing. Design. Illustration**
- **Fine Arts: Visual Arts**
- **Fine Arts: Architecture: Aesthetics of cities. City planning and beautifying**
- **Fine Arts: Decorative Arts**
- **Fine Arts: Arts in General**
- **Technology: Technology (General): Industrial Engineering. Management Engineering: Information Technology**
- **Technology: Building Construction: Architectural Engineering. Structural Engineering of Buildings**
- **Technology: Engineering (General). Civil Engineering (General): Engineering Design**
- **Language and Literature: Philology. Linguistics: Communication. Mass Media**
- **Political Science: Political Institutions and Public Administration (General)**
- **Social Sciences: Economic Theory. Demography**
- **Technology: Building Construction: Details in Building Design and Construction. Including Walls, Roofs**
- **Technology: Technology (General)**
- **Social Sciences: Economic Theory. Demography: Economics as a Science**

These Subjects have been selected to ensure that research covers a broad range of topics relevant to design, including closely related disciplines such as visual arts, architecture, engineering, technology, communication, and social and economic sciences. This choice allows for an interdisciplinary and in-depth view of academic publications that explore design in different contexts and applications, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the most relevant and representative journals in the field.

The main field remains firmly Design Cultures, but a series of Subjects have been selected to reflect on the inherent interdisciplinarity of design cultures. Indeed, the idea of design is not limited exclusively to the visual arts or architecture, but extends and intersects with numerous fields, enriching and influencing disciplines such as engineering, technology, communication, social sciences, and economics. This selection of Subjects only goes to show how design is a discipline that operates on multiple levels, touching and influencing many other fields, thus solidifying its position as a central node in a network of interdisciplinary knowledge (see paragraphs 1.1 and 1.2).

1.2 Discussing Limitations and Gaps of the Methodology

It is important to recognise that the adopted methodology has certain limitations, particularly related to its reliance on qualitative and manually-driven analysis. In contrast to the limitations faced by large-scale quantitative bibliometric analyses (Perry & Pereira, 2023), the primary limitation of this research lies in its manual and qualitative nature. While qualitative methods provide in-depth insights, the main challenge arises from the subjective interpretation of the data and the time-intensive nature of manual analysis. Unlike automated tools that process big datasets in a short time, this approach limits the scalability of the study and introduces potential biases that are based on the researcher's perspective. Moreover, manual analysis lacks the comprehensive scope of large-scale automation, as it focuses on fewer data points, risking overlooking broader trends identifiable in quantitative studies. However, this is not a limitation of qualitative methodologies but rather a trade-off that allows for a richer and more nuanced understanding of each journal. Additionally, by focusing on context-specific features like local traditions, language barriers, and regional publication dynamics, this research sheds light on variables often missed by automated, quantitative approaches, such as the diversity of voices in global design dissemination. Many journals, especially those not indexed in Scopus or Clarivate, lack sufficient scoring or data. The primary limitations include:

- (A) **Subject coverage:** the selection of subjects was conducted thoughtfully and comprehensively; however, it cannot be claimed to be exhaustive. By its nature, subject selection is subjective and open to interpretation, which may lead to varying conclusions regarding the inclusion or exclusion of relevant fields within the broader discipline of design.

- (B) **Global South:** to evaluate authorship diversity and inclusiveness within underrepresented areas of the Global South, this research focuses on low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) as defined by the World Bank (2023).
- (C) **Challenges in assessing authorship diversity:** assessing authorship diversity and levels of inclusivity poses challenges, particularly due to the difficulty posed by a manually-driven approach. Consequently, for this specific criterion, the analysis has been limited to the last five issues of the journal under review.

Also, it should be considered that not all design-relevant journals are indexed in DOAJ. Although DOAJ is an inclusive and widely used platform, there are other, lesser-known but equally important databases that may contain journals not found in DOAJ. This limitation means that some relevant journals may not have been included in the analysis. To address this gap, **9 design journals not indexed in DOAJ** have been included in the analysis due to their historical significance and impact on the global design community. These journals are:

- ii. Design Studies
- iii. Archives of Design Research
- iv. Africa Design Review Journal
- v. Design Issues
- vi. The Design Journal
- vii. CoDesign
- viii. Design and Culture
- ix. Journal of Design Research
- x. Dialectic

However, for the purpose of this research, the range of Subjects and the selection of journals through DOAJ is sufficient to provide a representative overview of current trends and publication patterns in the field of design. The main goal is to identify and analyze key trends, and the methodology adopted provides a solid basis for achieving this goal while acknowledging the inherent limitations of the process.

1.3 Comparative Matrix: Analyzing Quantitative and Qualitative Criteria

The next step was to construct and select the criteria for the journals' investigation. I used a set of criteria to construct the database of journals to be analyzed, taking into consideration various aspects, both quantitative and qualitative.

This table describes each criterion selected for this analysis, on what type of methodological approach is based (qualitative or quantitative) and finally what is the standard trend of the criteria. This column is relevant to draw a line between standardization and the innovative patterns that will be later investigated by the research.

CRITERIA	DESCRIPTION	TYPE	STANDARD
Affiliation University Press or Publisher or Association	This criterion serves to categorize the primary affiliations of design journals, allowing for a comprehensive mapping of the publishing landscape. By analyzing the affiliations – whether they are associated with academic institutions (University Press), commercial publishers, or professional associations – this data will provide insights into the structural dynamics of the design publishing ecosystem (analysed in Chapter 2).	QNT	University Press Commercial Publisher Learned Society
Funding date	This criterion is relevant to map the journal's longevity and its impact on the field, highlighting how established journals may differ in their influence compared to newer publications.	QNT	
Language	This criterion is crucial for mapping the linguistic diversity within design dissemination. By identifying the languages accepted for manuscript submissions, we can assess which languages dominate the design publishing landscape and understand their implications for global accessibility and engagement.	QNT	English language
Scope and relevance	This criterion evaluates how well the journal's scope aligns with the broader field of design and its various sub-disciplines. By analyzing the journal's thematic focus, we can determine its relevance to current trends, challenges, and discussions within the design community. This assessment is vital for understanding the journal's position within the design discipline, as it highlights the topics it prioritizes and its contribution to ongoing dialogues in the field.	QLT	Interdisciplinarity with: Arts & Humanities Social Sciences Engineering
Design and layout	Assess the visual design, readability, and overall presentation of the journal and the digital presence (functionality of the journal's website and digital archives). This criterion maps the editorial platforms used by the open-access journals in design and the level of accessibility and user-friendly interface to navigate the submission platform and archives.	QNT/ QLT	Traditional Open Access Publishing Platforms such as Open Journal System (OJS).
Publication frequency	This criterion examines the frequency with which the journal publishes issues (e.g., monthly, quarterly, biannually). A regular publication frequency may indicate a commitment to disseminating research and facilitating ongoing discourse within the design community.	QNT	1 to 3 publications per year

Accessibility	Check if the journal is open-access or subscription-based and its digital accessibility to the global design community. This criterion assesses also Article Process Charges.	QNT	Presence of Article Process Charges.
Journal impact and reputation	This criterion examines the journal's impact based on its indexing levels and geographical reach. Assessing its reputation can help contextualize its role in shaping design discourse and advancing the field.	QLT	Regional/Global Impact
Impact score	This criterion measures the journal's influence through its impact factor and other citation metrics, such as those provided by <u>SJR</u> (Scimago Journal Rank). By assessing these quantitative indicators, we can gauge the journal's visibility and significance within the academic community.	QNT	Scopus Indexing
Articles impact and quality of published articles	This criterion assesses the quality and significance of articles published within the journal. Key metrics, such as citation rates from Scopus's Citescore ¹ , will be utilized to measure the scholarly influence and reach of individual articles. Additionally, this analysis will consider the impact of linguistic barriers and geographical distribution (language prevalence).	QNT/ QLT	Scopus Indexing
Diversity and inclusiveness	Geographic Diversity: This aspect examines the geographic representation of authors, assessing the variety of countries and regions. Topic Diversity: This evaluation assesses the range of topics covered by the journal within the design discipline. Inclusivity: This dimension evaluates the journal's efforts to include diverse perspectives and amplify underrepresented voices in the field of design.	QLT	Predominance of Authors from Western and Global North Countries.
Editorial composition	Evaluating the geographical distribution of board members can indicate the journal's commitment to representing a variety of perspectives from different regions. By having board members from different backgrounds, the journal can promote inclusivity and equity in the publication process, encouraging submissions from underrepresented regions and voices within the design community.	QNT	International but regional.
Review process	This criterion assesses the methodology and rigour of the journal's peer review process.	QNT	Single/Double Blind Peer review. No recognition of reviewers.
Ethical standards	Check for adherence to ethical guidelines in publishing, such as COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) standards.	QNT	COPE Ethical Standards.

Innovative practices and experimentation	This criterion assesses whether the journal incorporates innovative practices and experimental methodologies within its publishing framework. By examining the inclusion of interactive articles, multimedia content, and unique design practices, this criterion provides insight into the journal's commitment to advancing the field of design through innovative approaches and emerging technologies.	QLT	Text-heavy publications in PDF format.
Networking activities	This criterion evaluates the extent to which the journal engages in networking activities that promote collaboration and knowledge exchange within the design community. Specifically, it includes a. organization of conferences/workshops, sponsoring major design conferences; b. facilitation of collaborations between academia and industry.	QLT	Proceedings of Conferences.
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines	This criterion evaluates the journal's publication of significant interdisciplinary research that integrates design with fields such as engineering, social sciences, and computer science.	QLT	Pervasiveness of articles is evident, but not quantified.
Interdisciplinary impact	This criterion assesses the frequency with which articles are cited in other scientific disciplines, utilizing Scopus CiteScore and focusing on journals in the best quartile.	QNT	Scopus Indexing

Tab IV. Methodological Matrix of Criteria. .

2 Analysis of the Design Research Journal Database

This section presents an analysis of the results derived from the collected data, organized into two levels of analysis:

Individual analysis: Each journal will be examined using a case study template, with the detailed cases included in the Appendix /2 and uploaded to an interactive online platform. This allows for easy access and engagement with the individual analyses [The Design Research Journal Database in Appendix /2].

Trajectories of innovation: The analysis will focus on four key trajectories, supported by a graphical representation visualising the data. This graphic enables readers to easily identify the innovation gaps in design dissemination, based on the standards already provided in Table 1. The innovation results have been clustered into four trajectories:

- **Editorial/Interface innovations:** exploring technological advancements in editorial practices and user interfaces that enhance accessibility and engagement.
- **Interdisciplinary pervasiveness:** assessing how design research integrates with and influences other scientific disciplines.
- **Inclusivity:** evaluating efforts to embrace diverse perspectives and underrepresented voices within the design community.
- **Evaluation innovation:** investigating new methods of assessing design research (peer review assessment).

The following paragraphs present an analysis of the second level of data, focusing on concise and direct insights.

2.4 Visualizing the Database

In the next section, the research presents a series of infographics that visually represent the data from the Design Research Journal Database (DRJD) across six different geographical continents.

FOCUS

Visualizing the Database

JOURNAL CASE STUDY OF EDITORIAL/INTERFACE INNOVATION

JOURNAL DECLARES INTERDISCIPLINARY PERVASIVENESS IN SCOPE AND AIM

JOURNAL HAS NO APCs; INTERNATIONAL BOARD; INCLUDES UNDERREPRESENTED VOICES

JOURNAL DECLARES AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF PEER REVIEW PROCESS/ REVIEWERS RECOGNITION

INCLUSIVITY IS BASED ON THE REGIONAL AFFILIATION/ LIMITED INCLUSIVITY

LIMITED INNOVATION PEER REVIEW / ASSESSMENT

LIMITED INNOVATION IN EDITORIAL IN EDITORIAL/ INTERFACE INNOVATION

Journals

	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity			Evaluation Innovation
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
Temes de Disseny		●	●	●	●	●	●	●
ALFA	●	●	●		○	●	●	
DATE			●		○	○	●	○
i-COM			●	●		○	○	
Revista de Expresión Gráfica en la Edificación		●	●		○	●	●	
Technology and Technique of Typography			●				●	
Research in Arts and Education			●		●	●	●	
IxD&A	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
JIDEG			●				○	
Artifact			●	●	●		●	
Convergências			●	●		●	●	
Eme			●				●	
Arte, Diseño e Ingeniería			●		●		●	
Res Mobilis			●	●	●		●	
Theory and Practice of Design			●				○	
gráfica		●	●	●	○	●	●	
Journal of Computational Design and Engineering		●	●	●	●		○	○
Design Science		●	●	●	○	○	○	
Immaterial			●	●	●	●	●	
i + Diseño			●		●	●	●	
International Journal of Food Design			●	●	○	○	●	
JOCIS			●		●		●	
ADEMAS DE			●		●		●	
designs			●		●	○	○	
UXUC			●		●	○	○	

Europe
(40 Journals)

Journals

	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity			Evaluation Innovation
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
Temes de Disseny		●	●	●	●	●	●	●
ALFA	●	●	●		○	●	●	
DATE			●		○	○	●	○
i-COM			●	●		○	○	
Revista de Expresión Gráfica en la Edificación		●	●		○	●	●	
Technology and Technique of Typography			●				●	
Research in Arts and Education			●		●	●	●	
IxD&A	○	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
JIDEG			●				○	
Artifact			●	●	●		●	
Convergências			●	●		●	●	
Eme			●				●	
Arte, Diseño e Ingeniería			●		●		●	
Res Mobilis			●	●	●		●	
Theory and Practice of Design			●				○	
gráfica		●	●	●	○	●	●	
Journal of Computational Design and Engineering		●	●	●	●		○	○
Design Science		●	●	●	○	○	○	
Immaterial			●	●	●	●	●	
i + Diseño			●		●	●	●	
International Journal of Food Design			●	●	○	○	●	
JOCIS			●		●		●	
ADEMAS DE			●		●		●	
designs			●		●	○	○	
UXUC			●		●	○	○	

Europe
(40 Journals)

Journals	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity			Evaluation Innovation
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
AREA		●	●		●	○	●	
[re] Design			●			○	●	
Pós		●	●		●	○	●	
KEPES			●	●		○	●	●
InfoDesign		●	●			○	●	
Dapesquisa			●			○	●	
Creación y Pensamiento			●		○	●	●	
SDJR			●	●	●	●	●	
Estudos em Design		●	●		○	○	●	
Iniciacao	○		●			○	●	
Design e Tecnologia			●			○	●	
Projetica			●		○	○	●	
UCES		●	●		○	○	●	○
Ergodesign & HCI			●				●	○
A3MANOS		○	●			○	●	
DATJournal		●	●		○	○	●	
DAYA			●		○	●	●	
Revista Projetar			●		●	●	●	
Diseña			●	●	●	●	●	
Ñawi			●		○	○	●	
ACTIO		●	●		○	○	●	
REAMD			●			●	●	
MAGDU			●			○	●	
Legado de Arquitectura y Diseño	○		●	●	●	○	●	
Designio			●			○	●	

South America (25 Journals)

Journals	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity			Evaluation Innovation
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
IJDesign			●	●	○		○	
Nirmana Jurnal Desain			●		○		●	
Jurnal Desain			●			○	●	
JShe Ji			●	●	○		○	
ANDHARUPA			●			○	○	
JADECS			●			●	●	
IJGSI			●		●		○	
Theoretical Principles of Visual Arts			●	●	○		●	
CUBIC	●		●	●	●	●	●	
Indonesian Journal of Computing, Engineering and Design			●	●	●	○	○	
JAARD			●			○	○	
PARAGRAPH							○	
NOT INDEXED IN DOAJ								
The Design Journal	●		●	●	●		○	

Asia (12 Journals)

Journals	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity		Evaluation Innovation	
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
International Journal of Designs for Learning NOT INDEXED IN DOAJ	●		●		○		●	
Design Issues		●	●	●	○	○		
Dialectic			●				●	
Image & Text NOT INDEXED IN DOAJ	●		●		○	●	●	
Africa Design Review Journal			●			○	●	
Journal of Health Design NOT INDEXED IN DOAJ			●		○	●	●	
Design Studies		○	●	●		○		

North America
(3 Journals)

Africa
(2 Journals)

Australia
(2 Journals)

Journals	Editorial / Interface Innovations		Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness		Inclusivity		Evaluation Innovation	
	Design/ layout	Innovative Practices	Scope and aim	Inter-disciplinary Impact	Editorial Board	Under-represented voices	Accessibility	Peer Review
DIID, disegno industriale industrial design		●	●		●	●	●	
AND			●		●		●	
PAD			●		●	●	●	
ZoneModa Journal			●		●		●	
Technè			●				○	
MD Journal Media			●		●		○	
Agathon			●	●	○		○	
Fashion Highlight			●		●		●	

Italy
(8 Journals)

2.2 Results: Examining Patterns and Insights from the Data Collection

The methodology reported previously describes in detail how the collected data from journal analyses, based on the established criteria (3.3), has been organized into four primary innovation curves. These curves serve as original categories for interpreting the data:

Editorial/Interface innovations:

This category identifies cases of innovation in editorial processes and user interfaces (website, platforms) that enhance the accessibility, usability and interaction of design journals. It is based on two specific criteria described in Table 1, Design/Layout and Innovation Practices.

Interdisciplinary pervasiveness:

This aspect examines how design journals converse with various disciplines, fostering cross-disciplinary research. It relies on two specific criteria outlined in Table 1: Scope and Aim, as well as Interdisciplinary Impact. This last criterion is applicable only if the journal provides relevant data, such as that available from SCOPUS or SCIMAGO indexing.

Inclusivity:

This curve represents the level of inclusivity of design journals of diverse voices and perspectives, reflecting peripheral and emerging experiences and out-of-the-mainstream backgrounds within the design community. It relies on three specific criteria outlined in Table 1: Editorial Board, Underrepresented voices, and Accessibility.

Evaluation innovation:

This category reports on new evaluation methods and criteria for assessing the quality of design research, and case studies of Journals using different evaluation frameworks. It is based on one specific criterion described in Table 1: Peer Review.

These innovation curves provide a framework for understanding the evolving landscape of design journals and their role in disseminating knowledge. Given this methodological overview, the following section presents a detailed analysis of the results for each continent. This analysis highlights regional trends and patterns in design journals.

EUROPE

The investigation focuses on the analysis of 40 journals, four of which are not indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), based in Europe. As illustrated by the infographic, the primary innovation trajectories among the selected journals fall under the categories of Interdisciplinary pervasiveness and Inclusivity. All journals declare in their Scope and Aim/About sections that they focus on a multidisciplinary and multifaceted scope of design culture and research. However, only 17 of these journals are indexed in Scopus, which enables the provision of citation data from other scientific fields and demonstrates their interdisciplinary impact. Regarding inclusivity levels, nine journals (including hybrid open-access journals not indexed in DOAJ) charge Article Processing Charges (APCs), which limits accessibility for researchers wishing to publish their work (Mehmeti, 2022). Conversely, half of the journals (16) demonstrate good inclusivity by featuring authors and case studies from peripheral regions of the globe, particularly the Global South. A minority of the selection (10) boasts an international editorial board; however, most members are

SOUTH AMERICA

Very similar to the European publishing landscape, the 25 journals selected from the South American continent show high levels of innovation in the categories of Interdisciplinary pervasiveness and Inclusivity. All the journals state that they accept and publish content related to design topics at the intersections of arts and sciences; however, only 4 of them provide statistical data on their interdisciplinary impact due to Scopus indexing: *InfoDesign*, *SDJR*, *Diseña*, and *Legado de Arquitectura y Diseño*. **Inclusivity** levels are high: in fact, none of the journals charge Article Processing Charges (APCs). However, most of the authors represented (19 journals) are affiliated to Latin American countries, which even if they are considered underrepresented in the Western academic discourse (Formia et al., 2023), demonstrates a lack of representation from other marginalized and peripheral areas of the Global South. This issue of underrepresentation of other areas affects also the composition of the editorial boards, where only 7 journals demonstrate an international board (from all over the world), while the remaining boards consist mainly of members from Latin American countries. Several innovations have been explored on the level of editorial and layout interfaces (7 in total), which include the use of preprints (e.g., *A3manos*, *UCES*), thematic dossiers, categories for young researchers (Iniciación Científica in *Estudios em Design*), and QR codes (*ACTIO*). However, innovations in assessment practices are limited, with only 2 journals publishing the peer review forms on the website. It is important to note that Italian journals have been intentionally excluded from this analysis, as the research will focus specifically on them in a separate section.

ASIA

Evaluation
Innovation [0]

The selection of journals from the Asian continent includes 12 publications, with 1 of them not indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). None of these journals show any innovation in assessment models and peer review. It is significant to highlight that 7 of the journals impose Article Processing Charges (APCs), which impacts their accessibility to potential authors. Only 4 of the journals under examination have international editorial boards, while the remaining boards consist of national members or those from the local region. Similar to the journals in Europe and South America, they declare to accept manuscripts from a multidisciplinary context for design topics, yet only 5 of them provide impact data through Scopus indexing. Interesting to point out that 2 journals present innovative publishing websites, standing out from the majority that utilize the Open Journal System. These two journals, CUBIC and Archives of Design Research, offer a high level of interactivity for users, enhancing the reading and navigation experience.

NORTH AMERICA

Editorial / Interface Innovations[0]

TheThe journals examined from the Northern Hemisphere of the American continent include 3 Journals, with Design Issues standing out as one of the most significant and influential journals for the design community as before mentioned. Despite its relevance, Design Issues is not indexed in the DOAJ, as it is a hybrid open-access journal and charges Article Processing Charges (APCs) to authors intending to publish in Open-Access mode. None of the selected journals show any innovations in assessment models. In terms of editorial innovation, the International Journal of Design Learning (IJDL) publishes text-based and hybrid text/multimedia articles, incorporating multimedia features alongside traditional text. Also, Design Issues invites submissions of visual projects that are either theoretical or experimental in nature. However, both journals primarily utilize PDFs as standard text formats for publication, limiting in practice interactive formats. Concerning inclusivity levels, the results indicate moderate efforts. The levels of accessibility for underrepresented voices in the design community remain low, with the majority of the editorial boards affiliated with the Northern Hemisphere, and therefore to the mainstream discourse.

AFRICA- AUSTRALIA

The journals selected from Africa and Australia show similar innovation patterns. Design Studies, which is traditionally affiliated with the UK, has been categorized under Australia based on the current affiliation of its editorial team. Innovation levels in these journals are standard. Accessibility is generally medium to high, although African Design Review Journal features case studies predominantly from its own region, limiting global inclusivity. Editorial boards also tend to be composed of national members, reflecting regional limitations in diversity. In terms of editorial practices, there are few innovations. 2 of the Australian journals include sections dedicated to multimedia formats, such as videos, audio slides, and podcasts, but these sections remain unused and empty. The range of interdisciplinary topics covered is broad, even though only Design Studies provides citation data through Scopus indexing.

2.3 FOCUS on Italy

Italian design journals show notable variations across the Innovation Trajectories identified by the research. Among the 8 selected Journals, the focus of innovation is predominantly on interdisciplinary integration and inclusivity, while evaluation methods and improvements in digital interface/editorial processes remain limited. Interdisciplinary engagement proves to be a significant priority since Italian journals look oriented toward the integration of content from/with other scientific fields such as architecture, sociology, technology, fashion, etc. Inclusivity and accessibility levels represent the most prominent trajectory, emphasizing the regional mission to integrate diverse voices, regions, and perspectives from all over the world, reflecting the country's connections within the global design discourse. In contrast, evaluation innovations are scarcely implemented, indicating a reliance on conventional peer review practices. Finally, Italian design journals have shown limited progression in editorial and interface innovations, suggesting that digital experience improvements, such as enhanced interactivity and reader engagement tools, are not yet adopted. The outcomes of this research phase have been validated through the participation in the focus group PRO.DES of the Italian Design Society Conference, allowing the research to gather feedback from the Italian design community involved. While acknowledging that the research is based on a limited number of people interviewed and researchers who were asked for feedback, the data collected and processed are

Evaluation
Innovation [0]

fairly homogeneous in recognising criticalities in the current publishing ecosystem that consequentially affect design publishing. In 2022, as part of a focus group within the Italian Design Society (SID), established by the Italian design scholars Eleonora Lupo (Politecnico di Milano), Elena Maria Formia (Università di Bologna) and Dario Scodeller (Università di Ferrara), this focus group called PRO.DES aims to collect feedback and map innovative case studies among the Italian design community concerning design publishing practices.

The criteria adopted in the research path of the “PRO.DES” project are related to rigor and authority of excellence and impact:

- Innovativeness of publication format (the very concept of “publication” is intended to go beyond that of the traditional article, in favor of augmented content not just text);
- Openness and inclusiveness (non-exclusively mainstream approach regarding the Global South–Global North relationship);
- New models of evaluation (transparency) and assessment (qualitative–quantitative, e.g., CoARA).

In particular, the proposed methodological approach aims to shed light on new interdisciplinary ways of publishing scientific content, considering approaches in STEAM fields and hybrid disciplines, to challenge the rigid barrier between hard and soft sciences that is also reflected in scientific knowledge. In this approach, design cultures are placed at the centre of the methodological and programmatic discourse of new forms of innovation in scientific publication, welcoming scientific results and products that have not yet been institutionalized and accredited. This results in several intermediate and ultimate goals. Among the main ones, there is the desire to return a picture, albeit an evolving one, of publishing platforms in the field of design that adopt an inclusive and non-hegemonic approach; to stimulate exchanges of knowledge, practices and formats among the main actors in the system (journals, academic institutions, open platforms); reconsidering the paradigms of impact and excellence of different forms of publication through a multiverse perspective; and imagining new workflows and types of fruition of scientific production, also in order to ensure a different longevity and interaction of the same. This project has led to the organization of three brainstorming workshops:

- (1) Innovative forms of publication
- (2) Plurality in Design Publishing
- (3) Quality and impact assessment of Design knowledge.

3 Current Publication Practices in Design Evaluation: an Overview

Editorial/Interface Innovations (Technological)

In terms of editorial innovations, Europe, South America, and Asia display moderate technological advancements as most of the journals rely on the Open Journal Systems², while North America, Africa and Australia lag slightly behind. Preprints, multimedia formats, and thematic dossiers are common across multiple regions. Europe has introduced some innovations such as Video introductions to issues and design practice briefs, while South America includes case studies of Journals using preprints and QR code integration (on pdf files). Asia is distinguished by innovative interfaces in publishing platforms like *CUBIC* and *Archives of Design Research*, which offer higher user interactivity, standing out compared to the global reliance on the Open Journal System. In North America, despite the limited number of journals, *Design Issues* encourages visual and experimental projects, while *IJDL* attempts to make use of hybrid text/multimedia articles. However, most publications remain rooted in traditional PDF-based formats, limiting innovation in layout interfaces. For Africa and Australia, the innovations in editorial interfaces are less prominent. Journals such as *Design Studies* include sections for multimedia formats like videos and audio slides, but these sections are often empty, indicating a lack of practical application.

Interdisciplinary Pervasiveness

Interdisciplinary pervasiveness emerges as the prominent innovation category across all continents. Most journals claim to incorporate multidisciplinary scopes in design topics, particularly at intersections with arts, architecture, engineering, and technology. However, few are able to substantiate this claim through Scopus-indexed data or citation metrics, which are critical for demonstrating real interdisciplinary impact. In Europe, 17 of 40 journals are indexed in Scopus, allowing for a measurable interdisciplinary reach, while South America lags behind with only 4 journals offering similar data. The Asian selection is even smaller, with 5 Scopus-indexed journals. North America lacks indexing in DOAJ but still emphasizes multidisciplinary content. The African and Australian journals exhibit broad interdisciplinary scopes, but only *Design Studies* can provide citation data from Scopus.

Inclusivity and Accessibility

Inclusivity shows varied progress across regions. South America stands out as a leader, with no journals charging Article Processing Charges (APCs), significantly enhancing accessibility for authors. In contrast, Europe and Asia both present substantial barriers to

² Open Journal System is a free editorial publishing platform to publish content in Open Access. <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/>

inclusivity with APCs being charged by 9 and 7 journals, respectively. North American journals also show moderate levels of inclusivity, but marginal and peripheral voices from the Global South remain underrepresented. Inclusivity in editorial boards follows a similar trend, with South American journals displaying more international diversity compared to Asian journals, which tend to have editorial teams composed predominantly of national members, even though in many cases the affiliations are international but based in the Latin continent. Therefore, Europe shows the highest levels of international composition. In Africa and Australia, regional biases persist, and Design Studies stands out as the only journal with an international editorial board.

Evaluation and Assessment Innovation

Assessment innovations are largely underdeveloped across all regions. Europe shows minimal progress, with *IxDa* and *Alfa* adopting the *CRedit platform* to improve reviewer registration and recognition. In South America, only 2 journals publicly share peer review forms, which is similarly seen as a small step toward transparency. In North America, despite the relevance of *Design Issues*, no significant advancements in assessment processes have been noted. Both Asia, Africa and Australia exhibit a lack of innovation in peer review or assessment models. However, some Asian journals offer a more interactive user experience on their platforms, although this innovation does not extend to the peer review process.

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The Ecosystem of Scientific Publishing: Implications for Design Knowledge Production

This chapter aims to analyse the current practices in the global publishing ecosystem, shedding light on the relations and dynamics between the actors, on the economic and political levels. This research relies on the assumption that the concept of scientific publishing is an ecosystem, composed of diverse approaches, platforms and methods. The comparison with the biological field and the theory of biodiversity strengthens the dynamics of the ecological system, where diversity and inclusivity are the responses and solutions to the fragilities that affect the ecosystem. By investigating the ecosystem, it is possible to identify the negligences and shadows of innovation attempts in the publishing industry, and how to address them in order to foster interdisciplinary collaboration, transparency, and inclusivity, fundamental components for the future of scientific knowledge production and dissemination. The chapter delves into the economic value of the ecosystem (1.1) by mapping the key actors of this industry (1.2). The intertwined dynamics between them are significantly affected by the power of multinational commercial publishers, who rigidly influence any attempt at structural shift (2.1). The rise of digital platforms (2.2) over print formats has created hopes in terms of accessibility, transparency and democratization of knowledge; however, the digitalization of knowledge has been monopolized by the power dynamics of the ecosystem. The research continues the investigation by focusing on the design production area: by analysing the data collected in the Design Research Journal Database (Chapter 2) from 92 design Journals, it shows patterns of knowledge production and dissemination according to the institutional affiliations of the selected journals (3; 3.1). By reporting the interviews with Paolo Manghi and Nick Lindsay, the discussion delves into the future advancement of the Open Access movement (3.2) and its financial implications on the ecosystem (3.3).

‡ The Ecosystem of Scientific Publishing: Current State

Over the recent years, the scientific publishing ecosystem has faced significant challenges that have initiated conversations to re-evaluate its structure. Scientific communication, as the fundamental pillar of academic advancement, struggles to reflect the demands and transformative changes of the current social and academic context due to the rigidity of its traditional mechanisms. A consequence of this systemic problem is the replication crisis¹ phenomenon, described as a slowdown in progress caused by inefficiencies of the peer review process and recognition dysfunctions. Academic competition among researchers for career advancement complicates this scenario, due to the pressure of obtaining grants and positions, driving researchers to prioritize quantitative metrics of publications over meaningful contributions toward innovation. These issues, which cause scientific misconduct, highlight the current limitations of the ecosystem to serve the global scientific community, especially young researchers, adequately. In this research, the use of the concept "ecosystem" is intentional and justified; in biology, biodiversity strengthens ecological systems. Likewise, this doctoral research suggests that diversity in approaches, platforms, models and processes could mitigate the fragilities of the current system. This analysis becomes foundational in proposing innovative models that foster transparency, inclusivity, and innovation in scientific knowledge production.

In the contemporary scientific landscape, it is evident that while technological advancements have accelerated, the pace of fundamental innovation – those groundbreaking theories and engineering practices that drive long-term progress – appears to have slowed (Mastroianni, 2023). Despite the proliferation of scientists and the increased investment in research, much of today's scientific output is characterized by incremental advances, rather than advancing revolutionary new paradigms. This perceived slowdown can be attributed in part to the shift in the day-to-day behaviour of scientists, which has been heavily influenced by changes in performance metrics and incentives (Geman & Geman, 2016). As Geman and Geman (2016) describe, modern academia often feels like a "small-idea factory," where the pressure to publish frequently has fostered a culture that prioritizes visibility and productivity over deep, exploratory thinking. Researchers now pursue "minimum publishable units," producing incremental findings that are quickly superseded, while the search for novel and revolutionary ideas is discouraged due to the professional risks involved.

¹ The replication crisis is a methodological crisis in which the results of many scientific studies are difficult or impossible to reproduce. Because the reproducibility of empirical results is an essential part of the scientific method such failures undermine the credibility of theories building on them and potentially call into question substantial parts of scientific knowledge. For more information, Staddon, J. (2017). *Scientific Method: How Science Works, Fails to Work, and Pretends to Work* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315100708>.

Furthermore, the peer review process, one of the primary mechanisms for evaluating scientific performance, often reinforces conservative research paths. As Ness (2015) and Alberts et al. (2014) highlight, the current system rarely supports ideas that diverge sharply from mainstream research or that venture beyond the boundaries of previously established work. This risk-averse environment, compounded by the need for scientists to secure external funding and institutional support, has created significant barriers to innovation, particularly for early-career researchers who are increasingly relegated to minor roles in larger projects to sustain their academic careers.

According to the biologist Nurse (2021), a "tyranny of the field" obstacles the emergence of ideas that challenge the dominant consensus. It is scientifically intrinsic to reject false facts, however, journals, funders, and evaluation committees should remain open to reasonable new interpretations or disruptive theories, even if they deviate from the general academic consensus, recognizing that innovation requires risks and exploration. Therefore, while technological advances have transformed tools and methodologies of scientific research, the incentives and structures within the scientific publishing ecosystem are obstacles to the creative and fundamental innovations necessary to drive future progress in our society. These systemic issues within the current scientific publishing ecosystem are particularly relevant to understanding why design publishing, a relatively young field, faces significant challenges in finding new pathways for innovation. The rigid structures of the current system, make it difficult for emerging disciplines like design to reflect its hybrid and peculiar features of practice, due to the mentioned constraints.

This analysis is relevant in describing the mechanism that hinders the academic publishing landscape and consequentially impacts the dissemination of design knowledge. By examining the key stakeholders of this ecosystem, their relational and economic dynamics, and the consequences of these interactions, the research presents insights concerning the issues of the system.

Fig.1: Visual elaboration of the ecosystem. By the Author.

Fig. 2: stakeholders involved in the scholarly publishing ecosystem. By the Author.

11 Market Analysis of Scientific Publishing

In a speech titled "*Reimagining Scholarly Publishing to Promote Credible and Trustworthy Research*," Brian Nosek, from the University of Virginia, critiques the fundamental disconnect between the intended purpose of scholarly publishing and the current realities of the system. He argues that "the purpose of scholarly publishing is to facilitate the communication of evidence and claims to advance knowledge production." However, this purpose is increasingly undermined by the business-driven nature of the publishing industry. Nosek emphasises that the current publishing ecosystem is slow, incomplete, opaque, and static, as it prioritized the research article over the value of the intellectual research output. Furthermore, the reward system underpinning the publication of scientific results has become dysfunctional as it is based on citational metrics or journal prestige, rather than the real impact of the results published. These complexities call for a need to reform the current landscape of academic publishing toward a more transparent and open-access dynamic model.

Until the second half of the 20th century, scientific publishing was managed by learned societies, as briefly described in the first chapter (2.2). Members of the societies had access to journals and publications, and there were products of internal evaluations and conversations among the members; this method ensured a trusted readership of editorial experts. However, due to the expansion in volume and disciplinary diversity, commercial publishers entered the market to address the increasing demand for publishing venues. During this process, many academic societies started collaborating with commercial publishers, which provided a larger scale of editorial operations and marketing capacities, increasing efficiency in production. This represents the key shift in the academic publishing industry: researchers, who are funded by public resources, produce and review content for commercial publishers (not for societies anymore) without economic compensation, but are compelled by the academic needs to share research outputs. The indirect consequence of this process is the privatization of public funds. Commercial publishers, especially those in Europe and North America, achieve profit margins as high as 20–30%, with annual price increases significantly exceeding inflation (Larivière et al., 2015).

The commercial publishers, for profit purposes, focus on increasing their introyits by reducing production costs and maximising scale. Scientific societies continue to be silent partners of the commercial publishers, who keep the tradition of unpaid labours for researchers. The large-scale operations are not sustainable anymore for societies publishing which have to rely on external subsidies or commercial partnerships. This current model raises concerns about the balance of public/private interests among researchers, civil society, and publishers.

1.2 Mapping the Stakeholders in the Ecosystem: Roles and Relationships

In this paragraph, the research delves into a visual representation of the scientific publishing ecosystem. The diagram (**Fig. 1, Fig. 2**) illustrated the key actors, their positions and interactions across two major dichotomies: Academia/Society, Knowledge/Innovation. These identified dimensions frame the different roles of the stakeholders and their dynamics within the presented system.

At the central axis of the diagram, and thus of the ecosystem, lies the Open Access wave: a transformative shift that has deeply affected the characteristics of scientific communication over the recent decade. Its centrality in the diagram represents its influence on the academic, economic, political and knowledge sectors. This paradigm shift has deeply changed the publishing model imposed by commercial publishers so far, redefining economic and institutional relationships between key stakeholders. The actions towards Open Access have challenged the conventional mechanisms by advocating for increased accessibility and equity in the production and distribution of scientific knowledge. However, this shift is still in an initial phase of development, definition and acquisition: the current publishing infrastructure needs structural changes to fully adapt to Open Access requirements. The roles of the actors in this ecosystem need to be reevaluated in light of this new paradigm, emphasizing the relevance of collaboration between economic, political, and academic career-oriented domains to support open

knowledge in contemporary scientific discourse. Thus, this diagram serves as a visual tool to understand the interconnectedness of the actors and their position in the broader ecosystem.

Through the words of Laura Hanscom from the MIT Libraries and Nick Lindsey, Chief of Open Access at MIT Press, interviewed in the framework of this doctoral project, the research explores the implications of this shift. Their insights contribute to shed light on how institutions like libraries and university presses are adapting to these changes, and how they envision the future of Open Access in the context of academic publishing.

RESEARCHERS	Researchers contribute to the production and consumption of academic knowledge. They engage in reading, citing, and building upon published work. Their need for accessible and up-to-date information aligns with the goals of the Open Access movement, which aims to break down barriers to knowledge.
AUTHORS	Authors are the primary creators of scientific knowledge, producing research articles, monographs, and other forms of academic work. Their role involves generating original research, submitting it for peer review, and often collaborating with others in the production process. In the Open Access paradigm, authors also engage with rights management, deciding how their work is shared and accessed.
SCIENTIFIC/LEARNED SOCIETIES	These organizations represent academic disciplines and foster scholarly communication. They often publish journals and advocate for ethical standards in research. Some societies have been central to promoting Open Access, while others face challenges in adapting to its demands.
REVIEWERS	Reviewers play a critical role in ensuring the quality and credibility of scholarly publications. They provide peer evaluations of submitted works, offering constructive feedback to authors and editors. In the Open Access model, reviewers are increasingly recognized for their contributions, as transparency in the review process becomes more common.
JOURNALS	Journals serve as the primary medium for the dissemination of research findings. They manage submissions, conduct peer review, and publish articles. The shift towards Open Access has seen many journals embrace new publication models that make research more widely available and enhance the impact of scholarly work.
LIBRARIES	Libraries ensure access to scholarly resources. They are strong advocates of Open Access, often providing institutional repositories and funding for Open Access publishing. Libraries also support the long-term preservation of scholarly output, ensuring its accessibility to future generations.
UNIVERSITIES	Universities are major actors in research production and dissemination. They support authors through funding and infrastructure, while also acting as publishers in some cases, particularly through university presses. Universities are also key players in the Open Access movement, with many adopting policies that mandate the deposit of research outputs in institutional repositories.

UNIVERSITY PRESSES	<p>University presses publish scholarly books and journals. They play a key role in ensuring the availability of high-quality academic content, and many are transitioning to Open Access models to increase the reach and accessibility of their publications.</p>
PUBLISHERS	<p>Commercial and non-profit publishers are responsible for producing and distributing scholarly content. While traditional models have centered on subscription-based access, many publishers are now embracing Open Access models, offering more flexible publication options that support greater dissemination of research.</p>
DATA REPOSITORY/INDEX	<p>These repositories and indexing services provide centralized access to data sets, research outputs, and citations. They support Open Access by hosting and cataloging materials that are freely available, helping to ensure that research is discoverable and reusable.</p>
PUBLISHING ASSOCIATIONS/ NETWORKS	<p>These entities bring together various stakeholders in scholarly publishing, including authors, editors, and publishers. They advocate for industry standards, promote ethical practices, and often play a role in advancing Open Access initiatives by supporting collaboration and innovation.</p>
SUPPLIERS (Tech)	<p>Suppliers provide the technological infrastructure and tools that support scholarly publishing, including manuscript submission systems, peer review platforms, and digital distribution services. Their role in enabling Open Access publishing has become increasingly important as the demand for digital tools grows.</p>
NO-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS	<p>Non-profits in the scholarly publishing ecosystem often advocate for equitable access to knowledge, focusing on Open Access and related initiatives. They provide alternative models to commercial publishing, seeking to reduce costs for researchers and institutions while maximizing the availability of scientific knowledge.</p>
AGENCIES FOR THE EVALUATION OF OF THE UNIVERSITY AND RESEARCH	<p>These agencies evaluate the research output of universities and individual scholars, often relying on publication metrics to assess performance. Their recognition of Open Access publications as valid research outputs is crucial for incentivizing scholars to publish in accessible venues.</p>
POLICYMAKERS	<p>Policymakers influence the regulations and funding structures that shape the scholarly publishing landscape. Their support for Open Access policies—such as mandating the deposit of publicly funded research in accessible repositories—has been instrumental in advancing open research agendas.</p>

TRANSFORMATIVE AGREEMENTS	Transformative agreements, often negotiated between libraries, universities, and publishers, seek to transition subscription-based journals to Open Access. These agreements aim to reduce costs while increasing access to scholarly content, making them a key component in the shift towards a more open publishing model.
FUNDERS	Funders, including government agencies, foundations, and non-profits, play a critical role in supporting research. Many funders now require that research outputs be published in Open Access formats, directly influencing how scholarly work is disseminated.
RESEARCH CONSULTING	Consulting firms provide strategic advice and services to universities, publishers, and policymakers. They help shape the future of scholarly publishing by offering insights into emerging trends, including the rise of Open Access and the development of new business models for disseminating research.

Tab. V: Stakeholders of the Scientific Publishing Ecosystem

This list of stakeholders has been created and developed over the course of this research project and it has been finalized during the participation in the OASPA 2024 Annual Conference on Open Access Scholarly Publishing², held in Lisbon from September 16 to 18, 2024. OASPA (Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association) brings together a diverse community of publishing stakeholders, including scholar-led and commercial publishers, platform providers, Libraries, and academic researchers. Its mission is to promote the open-access model for scholarly communication. At the conference, I had the opportunity to engage with several actors in the ecosystem, which allowed me to observe first-hand the dynamics. This direct interaction offered valuable insights into this research, as well as enhanced my understanding of how various stakeholders navigate the complex landscape of economic, political, academic, and ethical interests. These insights contributed to the development of the stakeholder mapping presented in this chapter. By attending such a relevant event in the open-access publishing field, I was able to witness the discussion about the future trends and challenges of scientific communication.

By using the quotation of Lyman and Chodorow (1998, p. 89) from Larivière et al., 2015,

“University presses and disciplinary associations were founded to disseminate research in the original cycle of scholarly communication. The faculty produced the work to be published; non-profit publishers organized the distribution of knowledge; the university library bought the published work at an artificially high price, as a subsidy for learned societies; and the faculty used this literature as the foundation for further research and teaching. [...]”

² <https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-2024-conference-programme/>

However, over the past fifty years, as federal research funding has encouraged specialization, journal publishing has become commercialized, and some parts of the scientific and technical literature are now being monopolized by multinational publishing conglomerates”.

this research aims to highlight several key dynamics.

The foundational product of scholarly communication are scientific results of original research developed by researchers, which rely on scientific associations and scientific journals to publish their work for the community. Hence, this distribution of knowledge has been managed initially by non-profit publishers, such as University Presses or Learned Societies; however, the commercialization and the pressure of the publishing industry have transformed this landscape, increasing the numbers of private multinational conglomerates, which now, thank their production capacity, monopolize relevant portion of the scientific industry. This “privatization” shift caused several implications for the

accessibility and affordability of the publishing system – open access models–, affecting the relationship between research output (ACADEMIA) and public availability (SOCIETY), as illustrated in **Fig. 2**. In this ecosystem, University Libraries, traditionally relevant in the scientific communication cycle, find themselves increasingly dependent on other institutional and financial dynamics; they are compelled to support the flow of published work despite the financial burden they carry. This economic dynamic deeply affects the libraries’ capacity to support open-access initiatives or to acquire a decision-making role in the ecosystem. The 2012 case of the Harvard Library exemplifies the significant financial pressures libraries face within this system.³ The interview with the Head of the Department of Scholarly Communications and Collections Strategy (SCCS) at the MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) Libraries, **Laura Hanscom**, captures a comprehensive analysis of the evolving role of libraries, particularly in relation to digital technology, publishing practices, and the larger academic ecosystem.

At institutions such as MIT, technology has been deeply integrated into library functions because of the nature of research and the needs of the academic community. The adoption of technology, especially in the transition from print to digital, has been significant. However, the print paradigm remains a strong reference point, even though libraries now operate primarily with digital collections. This

³ https://www.theguardian.com/science/2012/apr/24/harvard-university-journal-publishers-prices?CMP=Share_iOSApp_Other

shift has led to a tension between the traditional ownership of physical books, which granted libraries significant control over use and sharing, and the leasing model that dominates digital resources, where ownership is no longer a given. This approach to leasing has introduced complexities, especially with regard to libraries' ability to share knowledge freely, as publishers increasingly control access through the management of digital rights, affecting both access and affordability. Finally, although MIT has experimented with new models and publishing arrangements, the main challenge remains: without a fundamental change in the incentive structures governing academic careers, any reform will only address the symptoms of the problem rather than the root causes. It is recognized that any meaningful change requires aligning incentives with what matters to the scholarly community, ensuring that the focus returns to the quality of the research itself, rather than just its publication.

2 Power Dynamics in Scientific Publishing

To begin analyzing power dynamics in scientific publishing, a significant recent event offers a compelling starting point: the **Class Action Lawsuit** filed against six major publishers—Elsevier, Springer Nature, Taylor and Francis, Sage, Wiley, and Wolters Kluwer—by the law firm Lieff, Cabraser, Heimann, and Bernstein⁴ on September 12, 2024. This lawsuit accuses the publishers of forming a cartel to exploit researchers by applying unfair practices. These include requiring scientists to perform peer reviews without compensation and limiting competition for manuscripts through restrictive submission policies; researchers are bound by strict non-disclosure agreements during the submission process, preventing them from sharing their findings with the broader scientific community. This has intensified concerns about labour practices in academia, as researchers are subjected to excessive workloads and receive no compensation for their key contributions. This lawsuit sheds light on how power imbalances between researchers, institutions and publishers contribute to systemic exploitation within the academic publishing ecosystem, further highlighting how centralized control and economic interests shape the production and dissemination of scientific knowledge.

As illustrated in **Fig. 2**, there are two distinct levels of policy dynamics. **The first layer** (purple zone) operates at the academic level, where universities, scientific societies and research institutions interact with publishers and the academic community at large. **The second layer** (green zone) often overlooked but equally significant, functions at the societal level, encompassing national government bodies and public institutions responsible for allocating public funds for research. This social dimension plays a crucial role in shaping the scientific landscape but is often marginalized in

⁴ The full complaint can be accessed here: <https://www.lieffcabraser.com/pdf/AcademicPublicationsComplaintFinal.pdf>

discussions of publishing dynamics. This second level is particularly relevant because it directly influences research agendas and knowledge accessibility through policymaking, public investment, and the push for open-access initiatives. Without acknowledging the power wielded at this level, any analysis of the academic publishing ecosystem remains incomplete.

2.1 The Oligopoly of Large Publishers: the “Big Five” and Implications over the Ecosystem

The current academic publishing system is largely dominated by a group of commercial publishers, known as the “big five” publishers: Elsevier, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, Springer Nature, and SAGE, which each year report substantial profits (Butler et al., 2023). The profits are generated through:

Publication models of the journals produced by the Publisher, using the resources of researchers who pay to be published;
Universities/Libraries that fund the research and pay fees to access the published content of the journals;

The high cost of journal subscriptions has made it increasingly difficult for institutions to afford access, leaving many researchers and the public locked out by paywalls. This commercial dynamic in scholarly publishing is detrimental to the intellectual and scientific progress not only of the academy but of society, as access to research is restricted, leaving it open to misinformation (Abizadeh, 2024). The root of this problem goes back several decades, when commercial publishers acquired journals from universities or disciplinary societies, gaining monopoly control and significantly raising subscription prices. In addition, publishers often bundle journals, forcing libraries to purchase unwanted subscriptions alongside needed ones. Although publishers have introduced “open access” options (publishing models are described in section 3.2), these come at a cost. Authors are charged high fees to make their work freely available, and universities usually cover these costs. This has created an incentive for commercial publishers to maximize the volume of articles published, leading to an increase in low-quality or predatory journals and weakening the quality controls of reputable ones (paragraph 4.2). The goals of for-profit publishing are not aligned with the principles of scientific inquiry and dissemination of knowledge.

In Butler et al. (2023), the oligopoly shift is comprehensively described and profits of the publishing market of the “big five” are provided in detail.

2.2 Digital Interaction and Scientific Consumption: Sustainability of Digital Platforms

The arrival of digital platforms has profoundly transformed the landscape of scholarly consumption, mainly to the benefit of commercial publishers. The digital era has enabled publishers to capture a much larger slice of the scholarly literature by developing increasingly sophisticated publishing and production technologies, de facto making the academic community increasingly dependent on their services (Larivière et al., 2015). So, despite the advantages and advances brought into the field by the digital shift, such as preservation, multimodality of use, etc., this change has also brought challenges, especially in terms of sustainability and equity. The seriality crisis, which strained academic budgets in the print era, has evolved into a new financial burden as article processing fees (APCs) have risen. Studies consistently show that APCs place a significant financial burden on both academic publishing and library budgets, exacerbating inequalities within academia. In addition, the lack of transparency on APCs complicates the collection of reliable data, hindering informed decision-making and raising concerns about the long-term sustainability of this model (Vox, 2019). The shift to digital formats is a paradigm shift that has always been greeted with optimism, as it was thought that the Internet and the advent of PDFs would reduce the cost of accessing journals. However, instead of aligning business models with the new digital reality, commercial publishers consolidated their power, resulting in subscription packages that continued to inflate costs for universities (Vox, 2019). Publishers, on the other hand, argue that the digital age has brought additional costs associated with maintaining infrastructure and expanding article volumes. They argue that these factors justify higher prices, even as institutions struggle to afford access (Vox, 2019). Given these thoughts, scholars argue that the commercial structure of scholarly publishing, driven by unsustainable pricing models, in this current form does not serve the broader scholarly community. As Steven Bachrach (2000) notes, even with societal changes and advances in digital communication, scholarly discourse remains deeply rooted in the traditional written formats of peer-reviewed articles published in scholarly journals, effectively perpetuating the status quo.

In design research, these same digital disruptions are shaping new paradigms of knowledge production and dissemination. As described in the first chapter, the disciplinary field of design is no longer defined by single disciplinary boundaries but has evolved toward transdisciplinary and even “alter-disciplinary” approaches in which digital possibilities are reshaping the foundations of design thinking (Rodgers & Bremner, 2017). This shift underscores the need to rethink both research and practice to respond to global challenges in ways that go beyond traditional academic forms. Thus, digital transformation has not only affected consumption patterns, but has also stimulated the development of new methodologies, practices, and philosophies in scholarly design research.

3 The Publishing Ecosystem of Design Knowledge Production: Analysis based on the Design Research Journal Database

In the ecosystem of scholarly publication, patterns of knowledge production and dissemination vary greatly according to the institutional affiliations of journals. In this section, I will explore the ecosystem of scholarly journals in the field of design, focusing on how these affiliations—whether university, corporate, or related to large commercial publishers—influence open-access patterns. As analyzed in the first chapter, many fully open-access journals do not fall under the direct control of commercial publishers, who rather tend to commercialize open access. Therefore, it is crucial to filter this scenario through the lens of knowledge production in design, seeking to understand the role of these different affiliations in supporting more equitable and inclusive access to research.

Fig. 3: Data visualization of the Design Journals Affiliation divided into geographical continents, based on the data collected from the Design Research Journal Database. By the Author.

From the data collected in the **Design Research Journal Database**, an interesting distribution of design journals' affiliations globally emerges. These affiliations are mainly divided between *University Press*, *Learned Societies*, and *commercial publishers*, offering insights into how different entities contribute to knowledge production and dissemination.

EUROPE

Distribution is more varied with 32 journals associated with University Press, 5 with Learned Societies, 8 with commercial publishers, and 2 with hybrid affiliations between Learned Societies and Publishers. This mixed landscape represents a tension between the European academic tradition of university publishing and the growing presence of commercial publishers, who are also trying to gain ground in this area.

SOUTH AMERICA

With 23 journals affiliated with University Press and 2 with Learned Societies, South America shows a strong predominance of universities in the production and management of scholarly content. This predominance reflects an orientation toward more independent and more accessible models than commercial publishers. Cross-referencing these data with those analyzed in the first chapter, where it was found that affiliated Journals in South America show a high level of accessibility, in terms of Open Access and APCs, the connection between open distribution models managed by universities rather than commercial publishers is evident.

ASIA

Asia presents itself as a growing publishing ecosystem; 7 out of 12 journals are affiliated with University Press, 3 with academic societies, and 2 with publishers (including 1 independent). A significant contribution comes from local universities and academic societies, especially in the country of Malaysia where the governmental strategies are pushing the academic institutions to opt for independent and open access publishing models. This figure highlights a progressive development of the Asian publishing landscape, particularly toward open access and independence from large publishers.

NORTH AMERICA

The ecosystem in this continent appears very limited, with only 1 journal affiliated with an academic society and 1 with a commercial publisher. This figure stands out in contrast to Europe and South America and may indicate a greater centralization of scholarly production in North American countries through commercial channels or alternative platforms not represented in this dataset.

AFRICA

The presence of 2 journals affiliated with University Press is an indication of the increasing focus on open scholarly production and dissemination of knowledge in a continent where funds and

resources are historically more limited. This figure, although modest, is relevant to the context of the diversification of voices and regions in scholarly publications.

AUSTRALIA

With 1 journal affiliated with an academic society and 1 with a publisher, Australia appears to follow a narrower model, reflecting less publishing fragmentation than other geographic areas.

3.1 General results: the Design Knowledge Ecosystem

This analysis of design journals' affiliations around the globe offers an interesting insight into the management of knowledge production and the knowledge ecosystem itself. Starting with the limitation already described in the first chapter in section 3.2 of the methodology, where it is outlined that the selected journals were chosen from DOAJ's Open Access repository, it is clear that most journals that offer an open access publication model are managed by University Presses and the editorial process is edited by groups of researchers within departments. However, this publishing model has proved to be economically unsustainable, as described in the previous paragraphs: researchers work under heavy production pressure without compensation and the production activities of these Journals can rely entirely only on university funds. However, Journals managed by University Presses are predominantly Open Access (Gold or Diamond Model) and do not charge authors with APCs. In the next section, the research will delve into Open Access models and subscriptions.

Thus, while University Presses continue to play a crucial role in many areas, especially in South America and Asia, Learned Societies and commercial publishers are carving out different spaces, especially in Europe and other regions where scholarly publishing has an established tradition.

3.2 The Open Access Movement: Interview with Paolo Manghi (OpenAIRE) and Nick Lindsay (MIT Press)

Given the main digitisation priorities recommended by international political strategies, this research project aims also to investigate the digital accessibility of scientific journals dealing with design cultures. Scientific journals preserve and witness the research process and result through words and images. Thus, it is essential to keep the cultural content of publication archives through digital open-access distribution, especially related to young disciplines such as design. Open access (OA) refers to removing major barriers to accessing, sharing, and reusing the results of scientific research. The reason is that ensuring rapid and broad access to research results facilitates the research process, allowing all communities to

build on them and participate in the scientific conversation. The open access movement is inseparable from the development of the Internet and the redefinition of communication and publishing. This has led to widespread dissatisfaction with expensive traditional publishing models, leading to the OA movement (Tennant et al, 2016).

The interview with **Paolo Manghi**, carried out in 2022 (Manghi & Lupo, 2022), gives very significant insights to the Open Access movement. Paolo Manghi is (PhD) Researcher in computer science at Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione (ISTI) of Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (CNR). His research areas of interest are science and scholarly communication infrastructures, focusing on technologies supporting open science publishing within and across different disciplines, i.e. computational reproducibility and transparent evaluation of science. He is the CTO of the **OpenAIRE⁵** infrastructure and is also involved in the European Open Science Cloud projects (EOSC) pilot project. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) promotes the access and reuse of research data. Implementing Open Science (OS) policies, workflows and infrastructures throughout all corners of the European research sphere is critical to EOSC work. It has an open governance structure, a space for bottom-up innovation, and a long-term pillar of the European Data Strategy. In the interview, he explains the problematic gap in the scientific publishing industry that an open-access platform such as OpenAIRE or EOSC tries to solve.

He introduced the subject of the interview by moving criticism to the publishing industry and the evaluation system to which all scholars are inevitably subjected. We are seeing the gap getting smaller and narrower and narrower. Things are changing in many domains going towards this idea of open science, meaning not just in how we publish but also in how we do science. Open science is the two sides of the coin: on the one hand, researchers want to do it by sharing what they're doing, sharing their process and making it open. And after that, they also publish openly, which means open access, but transparently. In such a way, others can understand the products of science that scholars are producing and know where they come from and the theory behind them. They can easily compare it to other ideas and combine and reassemble your results to perform further science. And it's clear that scientists want this to happen, but this will never happen unless the policymakers support it. And this is what is happening in Europe; the European Commission funds had a future vision which broke the rules, fought against and negotiated against big companies like Springer, imposing open access to the publication. It has not been an easy process, and things have been changing so far; in Horizon Europe⁶, the open data mandates are there, and much of the funding, about 350 million, has been spent around the European Open Science Cloud. According to Paolo Manghi, changing practices is incredibly

⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁶ Horizon Europe is a seven-year European Union scientific research initiative, successor of the Horizon 2020 programme and the earlier Framework Programmes for Research and Technological Development.

hard, because it is not a global and harmonic shift. A community does not have a chief of community that makes decisions, hence, different nations behave differently. There is a general global understanding of things, but evaluation then changes country-wise.

Open science and open-access communities are raising several challenges, with publishers facing a double-dipping phenomenon due to libraries paying for subscriptions and authors paying for individual licenses. **Nick Lindsay**, Head of Open Access Strategies at MIT Press, shares their insights into the complexities surrounding open access (OA) publishing. While open access brings positive impacts like increased accessibility and higher citation rates, he raises several issues in the current implementation of the strategies. First, concerns the perception of the quality of OA journals, especially those in the arts, humanities, and social sciences often face stigma, with some perceiving it as lower quality because it's freely accessible. Secondly, many OA journals rely on article processing charges (APCs), which creates a disparity where well-funded researchers can publish more freely, while those with limited funds, particularly in less-wealthy regions, face barriers (fee waivers exist but are inconsistent and often limited). The concerns about research integrity in OA publishing are fairly widespread: OA publishing models are more vulnerable to attracting paper mills (issue described in paragraph 3.4), unlike subscription journals. Interestingly enough, he mentions the use of AI by the publishers to screen articles of unusual citation patterns, before sending the article to external peer review. He shows positive interest in the use of AI in publishing, especially when supporting language improvement for non-native English speakers, thus enhancing inclusivity. Although the impact of AI on design publishing (and the publishing ecosystem in general) is not investigated in this research, it represents a relevant issue for the future steps of this study (Conclusion).

3.3 Financial Dynamics of Current Subscription Models: Open Access vs. Hybrid Models

While open access (OA) is seen as a solution to accessibility issues in scholarly publishing, not all OA models are created equal. The rise of hybrid journals, which combine subscription-based access with the option for authors to pay article processing fees (APCs) to make individual articles open access, has created significant ethical and financial challenges (Seeber, 2024). Initially, the hybrid model was intended to be a step towards a fully open-access landscape. However, it largely failed to achieve this goal, largely because of the financial incentives publishers had to maintain the status quo (**Fig. 4**).

Research shows that hybrid APCs tend to be more expensive than fully open-access journals, resulting in higher costs for researchers and institutions (Björk, 2012; Laakso & Björk, 2016). Additionally,

many publishers engage in a practice known as "double dipping," in which they charge both APCs for open-access articles and subscription fees for access to the same journal. This results in universities and libraries paying twice for the same content, exacerbating the financial burden on the academic community while increasing the profits of commercial publishers (Pinfield et al., 2015).

Fig. 4: Open access model characteristics. Source: adapted from Farquharson, Jamie (2022). Diamond open access Venn diagram.

Given this dynamic, the ethical transformation to open access is often even more cost-effective. Diamond Open Access offers an alternative model in which neither authors nor readers are charged. In this system, universities, libraries, and academic funding agencies directly support journals, eliminating commercial pressures and maintaining editorial integrity. By eliminating APCs and subscription fees, OA diamond journals provide unlimited access to research without placing a financial burden on researchers or institutions. Despite its clear advantages, diamond OA has not yet become the dominant model in academic publishing. A major obstacle is the need for sustainable sources of funding to support these journals. While librarians and open access advocates have supported diamond OA for years, many academics are reluctant to make the transition, for the low-quality perception of OA journals, as explained by Nick Lindsay in his interview (3.2). For early career researchers, especially those seeking for career advancements, the risk of publishing in newer, less well-known journals is often too heavy to bear.

3.4 "Publish or Perish": Predatory Journals and Paper Mills Scandal

In the interview with **Laura Hanscom**, she discusses concerns with large commercial publishers and their exploitation of unpaid labour, which is indicative of broader challenges in academia. Also, **Nick Lindsay** mentioned the risks of OA Journals of being vulnerable to paper mills and similar issues. They draw attention to the unethical actions of some publishers, including the use of "paper mills." The original meaning of Paper mill, which refers to the paper industry, has taken on a completely different meaning in scientific publishing, indicating a predatory practice which is unfortunately increasingly widespread and carried out illegally by profit-making organisations. Paper mills consist of the systematic production of fake manuscripts, often plagiarized or written with automatic systems, which are sold to researchers who propose them for publication in scientific journals passing them off as their own, in order to quickly achieve the minimum requirements for career advancement. Paper mills are companies that pay people to generate academic articles or provide false information; these works are often published by prestigious publications without having been properly vetted. The discussion highlights how this system compromises academic integrity, highlighting how large commercial publishers create the standards that cause these worrying practices. The use of "paper mills" is one of the unethical behaviors that is called attention to in order to underline the need to move towards responsible, i.e. accessible, publishing models.

Researchers' careers currently depend on how many publications they have in prestigious (or high-impact) journals (Vox, 2019). This includes the funds they receive and the promotions they receive. This leads to the well-known phenomenon known as "Publish or Perish," which implies that in order for researchers to stay competitive in the system, they must publish regardless of the development or success of their research topic. As long as those incentives remain in place and scientists continue to accept the status quo, open-access journals will not be able to compete with this loophole, which further marginalizes academics from Global South countries (a topic that will be covered in Chapter 3). Currently, a large number of scholars continue to avoid publishing in open-access journals. One major reason is that some people believe they are of poorer quality and prestige and that they force the cost of publishing on the scientists, fueling and reinforcing the current status quo and increasing the profits of commercial publishers.

4 Assessment Sustainability: the Critical Role of Peer Review in the Publishing Cycle

After examining the ecology of scientific publication and its changing dynamics, we must focus on one of its crucial elements: the peer review process. The foundation of scientific publishing is

peer review, which is the process by which research findings are verified, criticized, and eventually accepted by the academic community. This stage is the decisive procedure that turns a research project into an acknowledged element of scientific knowledge; it is not only a procedural one. Peer reviewers serve as gatekeepers of academic integrity by carefully examining, assessing, and providing input on published work, guaranteeing its rigor and applicability. According to Riding (2002), which provides also a detailed chronology of the peer review as a fundamental procedure of the scientific publishing cycle, it is evident that the peer review process was started in good faith to examine and, as a result, enhance scholarly works that were submitted for publication. Peer review is used almost everywhere, which is evidence of its general effectiveness. From unofficial requests from editors, it has developed into a highly formalized and structured system with multiple variations today.

Fig. 5: The RoRi Atlas of Peer Review. Image retrieved from: <https://researchonresearch.org/project/peer-review/>

Despite the widespread use of single/double-blind pre-publication peer review, no single system dominates. Critics argue that peer review can lead to mendacious and tardy reviewer reports, but no viable alternative has been proposed. Despite these criticisms, most researchers believe peer review is the best method of upholding standards and ethics in science and the arts. Publications without peer review are regarded with suspicion by all users. However, peer review is in constant transformation and may undergo radical changes in the future. It is often noted that reviewers are not paid or receive recognition for their important service to the scientific community. For this reason, the scientific community (Cope, 2018) has recently initiated a call for the development of new forms of official recognition for reviewers. Some publishers do offer incentives such as free online access to a journal or journals for a limited period, but cash payments are virtually unknown. New platforms for reviewer recognition have been started, as broadly described in Chapter 4 of this research project.

In the Class Action Lawsuit mentioned in paragraph 2, among the charges brought up by the accusers, they move the criticism against the publisher that they offer too little to reviewers, as evidenced by low (and constantly falling) acceptance rates of “invitations” to review. These are the charges in detail, as reported in the lawsuit:

1. *Peer review is invisible; no social capital is exchanged – unlike in article publishing;*
2. *Peer review is completely non-standardized; each journal (even across publishers) has its procedures and requirements. This makes the process unnecessarily long and fragmented;*
3. *Payment for peer review is often branded as unethical or impossibly expensive – although it is already quite common for books and models for journal article payment are already in place. Models that allow for economic remuneration without direct financial payments, including the rewarding of tokens, discounts on publication fees, books, and post-publication services, are also widely operational.*

Academic publishers are reminded in a scathing, occasionally contentious manner by Lucina Uddin's argument⁷ that no industry can function at the long-term expense of its consumers. It is imperative that publishers rise to the occasion and become more academic, even when it comes to peer review. In addition to legal concerns, the validity of financial models in academic publications is also at risk.

A volunteer-led study by Predatory Reports⁸, an organization dedicated to highlighting unethical publishing practices, revealed a scandal of “review mills” publications published by the open-access publisher MDPI across many journals. As reported by Julia Robinson (2024), investigative work was possible thanks to the new practice of transparent or open peer review, in which peer-review reports and reviewers' identities are made public alongside the publication. The investigation uncovered a total of 85 review reports published between August 2022 and October 2023 in 23 MDPI journals that were very similar in content, contained similar typos, and most of which included coercive citation (the practice in which reviewers ask authors to cite their own work to boost their citation counts). This recent scandal proves that the current evaluation system is prone to be affected by citation manipulation, which represents a concern for the whole publishing ecosystem. Thankfully, many publishers are collaborating alongside the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) to fight against significant threats to scholar publishing, such as Paper Mills and Review Mills.

⁷ Lucina Uddin is a Professor at the University of California Los Angeles who has filed the lawsuit, claiming in a proposed class action that they violated antitrust law by barring simultaneous submissions to multiple journals and denying pay for “peer review” services.

⁸ Predatory Reports website: <https://cabells.com/solutions/predatory-reports>

5 Implications of the Publishing Ecosystem for the Design Knowledge Production

This general analysis of the global dynamic of the publishing ecosystem is foundational to better understanding the challenges and issues of design research dissemination. As discussed in the first chapter, design is a disciplinary field characterized by features of interdisciplinarity, creativity and practice-based research, which influence its knowledge production and communication. Therefore, the challenges within the publishing ecosystem might have a different impact. A relevant episode evidencing the pressure imposed by the publishing industry on the design publishing ecosystem occurred in 2023 at *Design Studies*, an interdisciplinary journal under Elsevier. The journal's editorial board has fully resigned, after Elsevier abruptly replaced long-standing editor-in-chief, **Peter Lloyd**, with Cara Wrigley, under the request for rapid growth in submissions and thus, revenue⁹. *Design Studies*, originally launched by the Design Research Society in 1979, typically publishes around 35 of its 600 annual submissions. However, Elsevier's executive publisher set a new target to publish 250 papers annually, above Lloyd's proposal of 50. Peter Lloyd, invited during the panel "**Changing scientific production in design**" in October 2023, along with Elena Formia (Vice-Editor of the Italian design journal *diid.disegno industriale industrial design*), Edu Jacques (Associate Editor of *Strategic Design Research Journal*) and Renato Bernasconi (Editor in Chief of *Disena Journal*) confirmed the need to discuss the scientific production and publication in design as a research area, sharing opinions and best practices, and envisioning new directions, methods, policies. The panel's position was very homogeneous.

This analysis, including economic hierarchies, power dynamics and non-transparent assessment practices, also has significant implications on the design on the disciplinary level, if we assume that design operates at the intersection of theory, practice and creativity, differently from more rigid and traditional research structures in other scientific fields. This specificity makes the integration of design knowledge into the academic publishing ecosystem even more complex, especially when considering that it is the ecosystem as a whole that decides what knowledge is deemed to be "valid" or "scientific" in design research. In fact, the interdisciplinary nature of design, challenges the traditional categorizations of scientific publishing, especially if we consider the use of visual communication, speculative scenarios, local practice-based research, and critical theory. All these formats struggle to find appropriate publication venues within a system that generally accepts only text-heavy or traditional methodological research formats.

⁹ <https://www.designresearchsociety.org/articles/the-future-of-design-studies-update>

Therefore, design discipline dissemination is often hindering how its contributions are recognized and evaluated within the scientific community. According to Lupo (2023), the objective is to produce creative forms of authoritative, high-impact, and successful academic communication through a multiscale and mixed media approach that ensures long-term influence while retaining rigor and authority. In this environment, scientific publication of design is taking on new forms and purposes, making the design discipline an important sector for the trial and discussion of new scientific publication formats for scientific research.

Concerning the evaluation process, the evolution of peer review attracts several doubts and issues, as the central pillar of the scientific process recognition. The challenges that all system is undergoing, are exacerbated when discussing the design field. The intrinsic nature of design research, as subjective and creative, makes it difficult to be assessed through conventional peer review methods, based on objectivity and rigid traditional methodological criteria. This imbalance causes a mismatch between the interdisciplinary values of design and the evaluative criteria of the publishing ecosystem, which may not fully understand and recognize the innovative and practice-led approach of design discipline.

As discussed in paragraph 3.1, the issues affecting the global publishing ecosystem have implications also for access and inclusivity in design dissemination. Even though the global trend is pushing for the democratization of knowledge and a full open access approach, at the expense of the commercial publishers and their profits, several design journals, especially the most prominent for the design community worldwide, remain behind the paywall of their commercial editors and do not adopt open-access models (only hybrid approach). In the next chapter, the research will analyse in deep the consequences of this limitation for the global design discourse and design scholars, particularly those from underrepresented regions or disciplinary branches.

Finally, the data presented in this chapter show that the current scientific publishing ecosystem shapes and limits the way design knowledge is produced, validated and shared. Design as a culture, continues to evolve, thus it is crucial to shape the future design discourse around the adaptations of the publishing models in order to address the specific evolving needs and outputs of the design community. The global call for structural changes in the publishing industry and in the peer review process can be grasped by the design community to foster greater innovation in the societal and cultural contexts where design operates.

5.1 Quality and Impact of Assessment in Design Knowledge: PRO.DES Workshop within the Italian Design Society

In 2022, I was involved in a focus group within the **Italian Design Society (SID)**, created by the Italian design scholars Eleonora Lupo (Politecnico di Milano), Elena Maria Formia (Università di Bologna)

and Dario Scodeller (Università di Ferrara). This focus group is called PRO.DES and aims to collect feedback and map innovative case studies among the Italian design community concerning design publishing practices (Chapter 1).

The third focus group of **PRO.DES** was dedicated to Quality and Impact Assessment of Design Publications. The workshop included 7 participants; 4 Professors, 1 Assistant Professor, 2 PhD Students. The results of the brainstorming workshop are very significant and can be clustered into 5 main priorities:

Challenges in Peer Review and selection criteria

Many researchers highlighted difficulties in the peer review process and how it varies across disciplines, emphasizing the need for clearer criteria in selection.

Alternative review models

The participants have raised the need for alternative review models like open peer review and editorial intervention on transparency of the process. Moreover, there's an exploration of models and single-blind vs. double-blind mechanisms.

Evaluation and editorial procedures

The data collected from the brainstorming highlight that researchers point out the need to discuss evaluation mechanisms for assessing research articles, stressing diversity, metrics, and systematic processes for inclusion in the evaluation of scientific output.

Power dynamics and decision-making in publishing

The design scholars discussed the hierarchies and decision-making structures within the editorial process, tackling who decides what gets published and how. This is strongly linked to the debate on distributed leadership within editorial boards and challenges of gatekeeping in academic publishing, that will be deeply analysed in Chapter 4.

Inclusion and diversity

Researchers addressed diversity issues in research, emphasizing the need for more inclusive evaluation practices that account not only for different cultural contexts, but also gender diversity, different disciplinary sub-branches, bringing to focus cultural diversity as a central concern in publishing.

Fig. 5: Miro Board used during the PRO.DES workshop.

The results gathered from the workshop show that the scientific community involved identifies an ethical dimension to be explored with regard to the peer review process, which, as also described in the preceding paragraphs, is a demand brought forward by the entire scientific community in toto. Moreover, their choral thinking invites reasoning about the training of peer reviewers, especially early-career researchers, to establish and develop a so-called “Review Culture” that is based on ethical aspects of transparency, respect, and inclusiveness. The remunerative aspect of the reviewer's work has emerged, and positive reinforcement for the fundamental work of the peer reviewer is called for.

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Towards Pluriversality in Design Publishing through a Distributed Leadership Approach

In this chapter, the investigation explores how principles of distributed leadership and accessibility can be applied to transform the current traditional, often exclusionary, structures of knowledge production in design publishing of the publishing ecosystem presented in Chapter 3. Grounded in the theory of pluriversality, which advocates for multiple and diverse representations of disciplinarity and practice, this chapter delves into the need for more inclusive frameworks within design scholarly communication. Starting with an overview of pluriversality in design publishing, the research frames how the diversification of voices, especially from underrepresented regions and disciplines, is crucial for expanding the boundaries of design knowledge (1). This theoretical grounding provides a segue into the concept of distributed leadership (2; 2.1), where decision-making and power are shared across a collective rather than concentrated within a few central figures. I argue that when adapted to the design publishing ecosystem, distributed leadership can foster more equitable and transparent systems of knowledge assessment, allowing for broader participation and reducing the exclusionary tendencies of traditional scientific publishing. Following this, I present case studies of publishing platforms and assessment models that successfully implement principles of transparency, inclusivity, and accessibility in the 8th Forum Design as a Process of the Latin Network (3.1; 3.2). These cases demonstrate the potential of rethinking publishing workflows to enhance inclusivity and fairness in knowledge dissemination. The chapter concludes by offering a Manifesto of Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing, developed through a community-led and collaborative approach of a Publishing Alliance (4.1; 4.2). These principles, which have served as a foundation for the development of the Co.Re Model in the following chapter, provide actionable strategies for creating more inclusive and accessible systems of knowledge production and assessment in design.

‡ Pluriversal Perspective in Design Community

"I think we, in the academy, lost sight of this crucial dimension of reality, which is the ontological dimension. What do we assume reality to be? What do we assume humans to be?"

Arturo Escobar

Exposing the concept and approach of *pluriversality* (Escobar & Maffei, 2021) in this research serves to frame the demand for "inclusivity" in design publishing. The pluriversal approach is the solution to the war against the *ontological dualism* that affects our reality: human/nature, human/machine, them/us, West/the rest, developed/underdeveloped, hard science/soft science, theory/practice, subject/object, etc. Escobar (2021) calls for a shift: from this ontology of separation to an *ontology of relatedness and interdependence* as the basis of existence, where everything is mutually constituted, where anything to exist, everything else has to exist. This is the ontological assumption underpinning the pluriversal approach: the recognition of the other as fundamental for anything else own existence. Applying this approach to design knowledge production is very important because this perspective enables the exposition of cultural identity and local knowledge. Unfortunately, design knowledge (but also scientific knowledge as such) is influenced by hegemonic structures and narratives in global knowledge where the ideology of knowledge supremacy in scientific production has emerged consistently in the last 25 years. Design cultures have problematized the idea of power, borders, marginality, and periphery, with the concept of pluriversality emerging as a critique of modernity. Scholars like Walter D. Mignolo (2012) have developed southern theories that challenge the dominance of Western theories and their geo-political, cultural-historical location in Europe (Blair Vasconcelos & Martin 2018, 8), that generally favour Western hegemonic positions (Kozma, 2023). Pluriverse is not just about diversity living and coexisting alongside, but also about energetic engagement with diversity. The concept of pluriverse is debatable, as it relies on plurality but should be more than acknowledging or "tolerating" differences or multiple perspectives as advocated by pluralism (Querejazu 2016). Masaki (2021) points out that pluriversal arguments fail to fully shed the binary logic entailed in Western modernity or fail to shed light on the multifaceted nature of transformative initiatives (not overcoming the autonomy/heteronomy separation). Although these concepts are reported and reframed into the disciplinary logic of design cultures, the research acknowledges the intrinsic bias of this application, as the perspective comes from a Western researcher affiliated with a Global North University. However, to answer the main research question of this doctoral study on inclusivity and transparency, the investigation of the pluriversal concept is deemed to be essential.

Design cultures have problematized the idea of power, borders, marginality, and periphery, with the concept of pluriversality emerging as a critique to modernity. The current state of the design discipline demands a shift towards plurality and pluriversality, which are crucial issues for new geopolitics of knowledge. However, pluriversal arguments fall short of fully shedding the binary logic entailed in Western modernity and fail to shed light on the multifaceted nature of transformative initiatives. Design practice offers a greater awareness of diverse perspectives compared to the field of design knowledge (Tunstall, 2023), due to the legacy of colonization and the need to embrace cultural dynamics outside hegemonic centres (Bonsiepe, 2021). However, design knowledge tends to adhere to a mainstream methodological structure (Perry & Soares, 2023), potentially limiting the inclusion of diverse perspectives. This exclusionary practice highlights a broader issue where scientific publishing manifests differently in the Global South and peripheral contexts of the globe, because mainstream and predominant academic journals tend to overlook contributions from non-Western authors, often citing a perceived lack of academic rigour (Reiter, 2019).

To address this debate, a new paradigm is proposed for the design publishing ecosystem: pluriverse as a shift from processes of power and control over knowledge to processes of distributed knowledge leadership. As explained in the next paragraph, knowledge leadership can be defined as an attitude or action that drives people to create, share, and use new and important knowledge to bring change in collective thinking and outcomes beyond the reach of a single actor, involving a range of agencies (Mabey et al., 2012). To promote a real pluriversal perspective, it is crucial to reframe and distribute knowledge practices among all stakeholders of the ecosystem of scientific publishing in design.

Fig. 1: Image used by Renata Leitão during her speech at the 15th International Conference of the European Academy of Design (EAD) at the São Paulo Hub - Living in the Pluriverse: inclusion and Diversity in Design Research and Education. Credits: Renata Leitão.

2 Defining a Distributed Leadership in the Publishing Ecosystem

This chapter is closely related to the ecosystem analysis presented in the previous chapter. As discussed in the second chapter, the ecosystem of scientific publication undergoes political and economic imbalances that have consequences and impacts on the levels of inclusion and transparency of knowledge dissemination practices. This occurs because the leadership of the ecosystem is highly centralized and unbalanced among the various stakeholders and actors living in this ecosystem. This research proposes an alternative model of ecosystem power management, referred to as “Distributed Leadership” (see Bolden, 2011 for a historical review of the concept). The concept of distributed leadership has been outlined by Peter Gronn (2000) as a potential solution to the tendency of leadership thinking to be divided into two opposing camps: those that consider it largely the consequence of individual agency and those that present it as the result of systems design and role structures. Distributed leadership represents a shift in focus from the behaviours of individual ‘leaders’ to a more systemic perspective, where ‘leadership’ is perceived as a collective social process emerging through the interactions of multiple actors (Bolden 2011), becoming a fluid phenomenon of transformation.

The concept of Distributed Leadership applied to the publishing ecosystem, is defined as a shared and collaborative responsibility of decision-making, across a variety of actors and stakeholders (Chapter 3: paragraph 1.2), instead of concentrating the decision-making power within a central authority, such as a cartel of commercial publishers or governments. By applying this approach to the system, all actors are included and responsible for shaping policies, contributing to publishing strategies and guiding editorial decisions. This methodological approach based on a bottom-up and collaborative dynamic, can foster transparency, inclusion, adaptability and sustainability of the publishing ecosystem. Pearce and Conger (2003) provide several explanations for this trend, including the emergence of cross-functional teams, faster delivery, better information availability, and increased job complexity. Faucheux (1997) reviewing the book *The Connective Edge: Leading in an Interdependent World*, also identifies rising global interconnectedness and aspirations for inclusion and diversity as driving forces that expose the limitations of more individualistic approaches to leadership (as the publishing ecosystem could reflect this description). In fact, it is argued that the leader-centric approach, which worked well enough and offered a (possibly illusory) promise of order and control to organizations for much of the twentieth century, is no longer fit for purpose and must be revised.

The key aspects of the Distributed Leadership are:

Fig. 2: Diagram summarising the key values underpinning the concept of Distributed Leadership. By the Author.

The impacts of applying these aspects to the Publishing ecosystem can be clustered into 3 areas:

Shared decision-making: instead of adopting a top-down approach, where the editors and publishers lead strategies and dictate policies, the proposed method suggests distributed decision-making across the publishing community, where readers, authors, peer reviewers, and societies contribute to the governance and systemic publishing process.

Collaborative governance: multiple stakeholders engage and collaborate in the publishing process. This model highly fits with open-access environments where transparency and inclusivity are prioritized.

Decentralization of authority: within this approach, power is not centralized but distributed and dispersed, meaning that leadership roles are taken by different actors of the ecosystem, diversifying perspectives and interests. In this way, gatekeeping tendencies in traditional publishing structures are reduced.

2.1 Core Values of Distributed Leadership: Openness, Inclusivity, Interaction

Joy Owango, Founding Director of the Training Centre in Communication (TCC Africa), an award-winning Trust registered in Kenya and the first African-based training center to teach effective communication skills to scientists, spoke at the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association Conference in Lisbon in September

2024 during the Panel "Who Cares about Equity?" TCC Africa collaborates with the University of Nairobi in Kenya to enhance African scholars' visibility and production by offering training in scholarly and scientific communication. Her speech during the Conference is highly relevant and the insights provided are particularly unique, especially because she represents an underrepresented area (the African continent). The first question she posed to the audience was: "How to enhance a multidisciplinary approach when there is no access to social sciences resources?".

She calls for a collaborative lobby on public institutions and governments to build infrastructures for Journals in the African continent. As well explained in the slide (Fig. 3), the concept of inclusion is not based on the idea of providing equal resources, but it's about creating equal opportunities based on the diversity of the context. Therefore, she argues that we need to contextualise how we make resources equitable and why. She focuses on the reasons why the developed countries (Global North) are undertaking the mission of inclusion: is it for post-colonialist aftermath? Or for a conscious of Guilt? Or is it based on a global movement on equity? To this question, she believes that the only reason leading this movement should be an ethical reflection completely divorced from the so-called messiah complex¹.

¹ For a detailed up-to-date description of the phenomenon see: <https://www.theatlantic.com/books/archive/2022/10/howard-baskerville-persian-constitutional-revolution/671787/>

3 Experimenting with Alternative Paradigms of Distributed Leadership in Design Knowledge

This section of the research is dedicated to a series of field experimentations that attempted to highlight the potential need to rethink publishing workflows to enhance inclusivity and transparency in design knowledge dissemination and evaluation. For this purpose, the Latin Network has been deemed to be the appropriate context for several reasons.

As comprehensively reported by the Italian design researcher **Elena Maria Formia**, (2024) the Latin Network was established in 2008 with the “Carta di Torino” Manifesto and is composed of a group of researchers of Latin language and culture, counting around 60 members from 15 countries, and more than 20 universities in Europe and North/Central/South America². The genesis was aligned with a geopolitical shift in the early 2000s when the mutual interest between European and Latin American design scholars was sparked again after a first wave emerged in the period following WWII. Thus, the connotation of the Network implies a geo-political will, questioning the centre-periphery model and its effect on designing in Latin America (Margolin 2007): the Latin vocation means to unify a territory in a cultural and political sense, seeking to recognise common perspectives, tools, methods, and approaches, beyond the native language they share³.

The Latin Network's historical evolution was marked by a first period of great attractiveness and a desire to internationalize cultural experiences based on scientific evaluation of the design processes, followed by a second phase dominated by nationalism. In this current phase, the two Latin continents (Latin America and Europe) have reverted to treating each other with respect. Nonetheless, over time, the network has strengthened relationships between Latin countries and LA, and as a result, these countries became privileged interlocutors for dialogue/confrontation and objects/contexts of experimentation, including in the editorial field, as evidenced by the Publishing Alliance that will further be discussed in the fourth paragraph of this chapter.

The Latin Network has represented an adequate context where to experiment with alternative frameworks of knowledge assessment in design publishing for several reasons. First, by organizing conferences it provides a consistent and accessible publishing venue for a large part of the design community around the world. Secondly, its inclusive reach, geographically and disciplinary, attracts a diverse audience of researchers from the Global South, including early-career researchers. This diversity in conferences emphasizes a multiplicity of perspectives and voices in the design

² For an overall representation of the Latin Network, see: <https://www.forumdesignprocess.org/dgdw22/past-editions/>

³ It is important to specify that the Latin Network includes, as effective members, the following countries: France, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay and Venezuela. However, the Network has opened its community to worldwide contribution.

landscape. Finally, the Latin Network's focus on the design process rather than results and outcomes allows to draw attention to local knowledge and endogenous design practices, by valuing context-specific approaches that often challenge Western-centric frameworks of research.

Given these aspirations of the Latin Network to advocate for a more pluralistic view of design knowledge, the experimentation within this setting aligned with the network's mission of promoting pluriversal principles in design. The research chose to experiment with knowledge assessment practices, as they are considered to be the central gatekeeper for global south researchers. For these researchers, alternative assessment models can be particularly valuable as they address issues of accessibility and recognition that traditional frameworks often overlook. Within this context, experimental assessment methods can be tailored to prioritize inclusivity and support underrepresented voices, adding a layer of validation for local and regional contributions.

Therefore, the Latin network's context also makes it a natural setting for reimagining knowledge assessment toward inclusivity and transparency.

✂ Inclusivity in Assessment: Ensuring Equity in Research Assessment

In this paragraph, the research aims to map out the theoretical assumptions to support the research hypothesis on the necessity to increase inclusivity and equity in design evaluation practices through a pluriversal approach and distributed leadership.

In the modern knowledge field, there is a clear dichotomy between true and false, granting modern science the paradigmatic monopoly of this epistemological dispute (Santos, 2014). This division, defined as abyssal thinking, causes a monopoly of knowledge which determines what research outcomes are considered scientific and non-scientific; this hegemonic paradigm in the dispute between scientific and non-scientific is held by Western modernity.

Nowadays, this paradigm is being challenged, especially in the field of design cultures, where concepts of inclusivity and intersectionality are becoming foundational concepts of design practice (Khandwala, 2019). In contemporary literature, the ideology of knowledge supremacy is challenged beyond critiques of modernity and colonialism (Leitão & Noel, 2022). New practical approaches, theories, and methods propose alternatives to the hegemonic and dominant narrative, emphasizing the need to go beyond "tokenism," urging to accept new ways of thinking from actors outside the mainstream to generate "worlds with many centers" (Leitão & Noel, 2022).

In the discipline of design, a critical reflection on the concept of peripheral action is underway, highlighting the centrality of work "in" rather than "for" the peripheries (Bonsiepe, 2003) as outstandingly explained by Joy Owango in her speech at the OASPA Conference

(paragraph 2.1). There is also attention to the concept of marginality, acknowledging that the Eurocentric epistemological foundation of design education and practice needs a process of decolonization (Fry, 2017). The practice of design, both as a profession and a research field, already reflects this need for “a world of many centres”; on the other hand, this process is still germinal in design knowledge production. Hence, the concept of pluralization becomes central in design methodology, acknowledging and incorporating diverse cultural, biological, and social pluralities within processes. Pluralization means recognizing the existence of ecosystemic biodiversity and coordinated efforts to diversify meaning, scope, and political ontologies. Design practice is already undergoing a reconnection with endogenous practices to recognize and increase awareness of the inevitable epistemological impact of dominant narratives on the global design community (Cardini, 2022). Design practice exists in relation to local knowledge ecologies, ontologies, systems, and kinship responsibilities.

It is very important to maintain these two levels distinct when discussing inclusive practices in design: design practice and design knowledge. If the impact of the concept of plurality/pluriversality and inclusivity on design practices is generally recognised, the impact on the system of knowledge is still underresearched. The most evident impact of the global system of knowledge is that academic knowledge in scientific publishing takes different forms in the Global South (Mehmeti, 2022). Also Louise Valentine in her interview, sheds light on recognising the different cultures of design in academic scientific journals, not only geographically but in terms of cultures of thinking. A community-led knowledge and new editorial workflows should be reinvented to engage communities to experiment and prototype new knowledge interactions through open peer review, social annotations, or collaborative writing and editing, shifting from individual proprietary forms of authorship towards more communal forms of knowledge (Adema & Kiesenwetter, 2022).

The Western diktat “Publish or Perish”, already analysed in Chapter 3, hinders the scientific advancement of the Global South and largely impacts the dissemination of local knowledge; in order to challenge the privileged knowledge generated in the Global North, the research argues the need to expand community-led knowledge through a new collaborative approach in international events to engage researchers and early career researchers towards inclusive and transparent knowledge interactions.

3.2 Applying Distributed Leadership to Knowledge Assessment: the Case of the Proceedings of 8th International Forum of Design as a Process of the Latin Network

The 8th International Forum of Design as a Process, titled “**Disrupting Geographies in the Design World**”⁴, was held in Bologna

⁴ <https://www.forumdesignprocess.org/dgdw22/>

in June 2022 and organised by the Design departments of the Università di Bologna (Italy), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile (Chile) and Tecnológico de Monterrey (Mexico). The forum aimed to explore how design principles and practices can adapt to the diversity of the contemporary world. The forum received over 145 submissions, primarily from researchers from the Global South. The conference provided an opportunity for researchers from the South and underdeveloped countries to present their scientific contributions and be recognized by the international/Western community. The Latin Network's evolution facilitates a parallel approach to designing research education, enabling young researchers to navigate the Global North's academic systems and share their knowledge and case studies.

However, the research must point out that the evaluation system used to review both the long abstracts, and the full papers was developed on a traditional submission system (Open Journal System) of a publication venue based in Europe, which is intrinsically biased. Despite this, the focus of the evaluation methodology remained on increasing publishing accessibility and visibility of early-career researchers from low-middle-income countries (LMICs) and experimenting with a more inclusive evaluation framework for the peer-review process of the long abstracts and full articles.

Evaluation Framework of the Proceedings

The Proceedings underwent a single-anonymous form of peer review. In this method of peer review, a) the Reviewer's identity is not made visible to the author, b) the Author's identity is visible to the reviewer, c) the Reviewer's and Author's identity is visible to the Editor⁵.

According to Wiley, the advantages of this method rely on the anonymity of the reviewer, which allows him/her to be honest without fear of criticism from an author. Moreover, knowing who the author is (and their affiliation) allows the reviewer to use their knowledge of the author's previous research and background. On the other side, the limitations of this editorial procedure include a potential conflict of interest, as the transparency of the author could overshadow the quality of the work, potentially leading to a lack of scrutiny, especially if the track record of an author is unknown. The second limitation is based on the potential for discrimination based on gender or nationality. Discrimination based on non-scientific criteria is unacceptable, but in the case of perceived discrimination based on nationality, it is often conflated with discrimination based on bad English. Acknowledging the potential challenges and concerns associated with this form of peer review, the Editors carefully considered and evaluated this approach. Generally, double-blind peer review is the most used methodology, but in this case, the single-anonymous review was employed to actively engage reviewers towards the validation of a

⁵ <https://authorservices.wiley.com/Reviewers/journal-reviewers/what-is-peer-review/types-of-peer-review.html>

non-Western article. In addition, concerns have been devoted to mitigating any drift of inclusivity attempts to domestication or anthropologization of 'other' knowledge (Reiter, 2019). Therefore, the Editors consciously chose the single-blind peer review, to raise the awareness of reviewers to prioritize content over language skills and traditional methodological scientific standards. Furthermore, as previously discussed, this method was adopted to enhance accessibility for young researchers from non-Western countries, mitigating the risk of biased evaluations influenced by language or regional factors. This decision reflects a broader commitment to foster a fair and inclusive evaluation process within the scholarly community.

Nevertheless, the evaluation criteria of the Proceedings' peer review were consistent with those regularly employed for the submissions in the **diid.disegno industriale industrial design**⁶ Journal. They considered:

- Originality and relevance
- Congruence with the Design field
- Scientific rigour
- Relationship to literature
- Methodology
- Results and conclusion
- Quality of communication
- Final comments to the Author and suggestions

These criteria were applied to ensure a comprehensive evaluation process, maintaining the standards acknowledged for international conference Proceedings. However, along the whole process, the two criteria of relevance and scientific rigour were often challenging: non-Western contributions are often supposed to lack academic rigour, but standards elevated as universal by Western thinking were questioned. Therefore, reviewers were committed to evaluating relevance based on contextual knowledge, local design, community-led projects, responsible innovation, social justice, and ecocentrism, while avoiding romanticising them. They also committed to assessing scientific rigour without downsizing it in favour of Global South knowledge with the risk of endorsing dualist logic. For this aspect the partnership with the two Latin American universities was crucial. Finally, reviewers were carefully selected to mitigate conflicts of interest.

Finally, as suggested in the guidelines provided in Recommendation 5. Foster Equity in Peer Review (2024), the strategies to counteract unconscious and conscious biases present in the peer review process, involve the direct action and engagement of publishers and editors who can provide resources and education to those involved in the process and consider alternative peer review models, as well train reviewers and help them gain experience to successfully participate to the editorial process (Recommendation 4, 2024).

⁶ www.diid.it

3.3 Multipolar Vision for Geopolitics of Design Knowledge: Lessons Learned from the 8th International Forum to Foster Accessibility for Researchers of the Global South

The previous paragraphs have addressed the accessibility gap of researchers from LMICs and Global South Countries in the geopolitical knowledge and publishing system affected by ethnocentrism and Western hegemony. Proposing alternative evaluation methodologies in publishing venues aims to make the system more permeable in favour of a more pluriversal design knowledge. The 8th Forum has offered an experiment targeting the Latin Network and Global South countries to experiment with the traditional framework of peer review processes based on Western-centric values. The evaluation framework proposed by the 8th International Forum, avoiding a dualistic approach, offers alternatives to complement the ecosystem of design publishing (journals and conferences) in decentering design publishing, although still bearing limits in terms of indexing and clarity in the review process. Increasing accessibility to international research venues might be a solution to address inequality in research, as it remains a critical factor for the academic growth of LMIC researchers. While introducing new visibility channels marks an initial move towards enhancing actors' and participants' capabilities in knowledge production dynamics, transitioning from plurality to pluriversity requires further support for distributing knowledge leadership. Language concerns persist, as adopting English as the primary language, though facilitating wider dissemination, may diminish the richness of expression in Latin American languages. As argued by Amano et al. (2023), the use of English as the common language of science represents a major impediment to maximising the contribution of non-native English speakers to science. Yet few studies have quantified the consequences of language barriers on the career development of researchers who are non-native English speakers (Havemann, 2023). Thus, bilingual processes should also be encouraged to address this issue. The analysis conducted on statistical data shows that a more flexible evaluation framework of submissions has allowed more than 90 early-stage career researchers from 11 countries of the LMICs to present and publish their research. Nevertheless, this research is aware that the evaluation framework proposed is a tentative initiative to suggest new hierarchies based on a more distributed knowledge thus innovating publishing processes and pushing forward standards, cross-disciplinary practices and self-advocacy in knowledge development. This research supports the concept of pluriverse and has tried to apply it critically to inform the publishing process, resulting in a methodology and a statement of practice that can contribute to better managing knowledge dispersion in design and pave the way for future work (Formia et al., 2024).

FOCUS

**Is There a
South-North
Knowledge
Gap?**

This in-depth study has been previously published as a Visual Essay on the Italian Design journal *diid.disegno industriale* industrial design, as part of a thematic study on the current landscape of design publishing (Lupo, 2022). This focus aims to provide focus on scientific journals based in the Global South regions. The limits and challenges of doing science in any Global South area are widely understood, especially among Global South researchers. Even with such circumstances, a larger dimension of the impact of research generated by and from the Global South must be

recognised (Cortes, 2022). This study sheds light on 7 peer-reviewed and open-access Journals based in a Global South country (World Bank Classification) in all the continents; the selection criteria were:

- Digital;
- Open Access;
- Affiliation;
- Geographical area of main research focus in the Global South;
- Impact score.

The following boxes analyse one/two case studies per each continent.

The research was not based on comparing the selected Journals with the characteristics of the leading journals published in developed countries; on the opposite, the study intends to highlight and compare the research features among the presented case studies to avoid comparison between countries of different income and educational levels, as indicated by recent development cooperation theories (Mitchell, 2021) and by the speech of Joy Owango about the Messiah Complex (2.1). Many factors could be observed and analysed when developing a comparison based on data sets; in this focus, the research has considered the composition of Editorial and Scientific Boards in these publication venues as the leading factor in the analysis. The results show a lack of scientific intertwining of researchers between the Global South and Global North, but the two spheres remain interconnected. Using this indicator, the study highlights a quantitative and qualitative approach (shown in the density map) per each Journal that is representative of a status quo of non-contamination between the South and

the North, where the North is less involved in the scientific research and impact conducted by the Global South. The investigation is aware that the involvement of the Global North cannot be measured only based on the inclusion in Editorial or Scientific Boards. However, the institutional appearance on a Board can be considered a crucial factor among others; as evidenced by PAD (Pages on Art and Design) Journal, which is based in Italy and focuses on the Mediterranean area, its composition is the most “intertwined” of the case studies. Most of them are not indexed and do not have an impact score, which indicates that their scientific advancement levels cannot challenge the status quo or privilege knowledge generated primarily in the Global North. This limit has a significant impact on access to funding which perpetuates the problem. The density map indicates all the countries where the researchers of the Editorial and Scientific Boards are affiliated; in most cases, the Board is predominately composed of researchers from the same country (or University) where the Journal is based.

Sitography

Africa Design Review Journal

Ellipses

Asia Design Journal

Central Asian Journal of Arts and Design

Pages on Art and Design

South European Journal of Architecture and Design

Strategic Design Research Journal

Fig. 1

ASIA

C	Asia Design Journal	D	Central Asian Journal of Arts and Design
Affiliation	Seoul National University, Korea	Affiliation	Central Asian Studies (CAS)
Funding date	2004	Funding date	2020
Open Access	Yes	Open Access	Yes
Impact score	N/D	Impact score	N/D
North-South composition in the Board	62% South - 38% North	North-South composition in the Board	77% South - 23% North

Promoted by the Korean Design Research Institute (KDRI), Asia Design Journal aims to find and create concepts and trends in Asian values and culture every year. It hopes to explore new Asian ideas each year through papers on multi-interdisciplinary topics, including culture, social science, literature, engineering, management, liberal arts and design, which deal with Asian culture and design. KDRI strives to make the Journal more helpful to the readers and become the centre of healthy debate on innovation.

CAJAD provides an international forum for research in art and design education in Central Asian Studies. It is a source for disseminating independently refereed articles about the visual arts, creativity, crafts, design, and art history, in all aspects, phases, and types of educational contexts and learning situations in the region. The Journal welcomes articles from a wide range of theoretical and methodological approaches to research. It also welcomes multidisciplinary submissions from the broader fields of education and the arts concerned with learning through art and creative education.

ASIA
DESIGN
JOURNAL

CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN

SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE

E Pages on Art and Design	
Affiliation	University of Palermo, Italy
Funding date	2005
Open Access	Yes
Impact score	N/D
North-South composition in the Board	65% North – 35% South

PAD publishes research findings from researchers and professionals across different countries and cultures of the Mediterranean areas and encourages research on the impact of cultural factors on design theory and practice. Critical, review and comparative studies are particularly prominent, as are contributions that draw upon other literature, such as those derived from historical, philosophical, sociological or psychological studies of technology or design, to address issues of technology concern. PAD aims to promote knowledge transfer between professionals in academia and industry in the southern areas of the Mediterranean area.

PAGES ON
ARTS AND DESIGN

F South European Journal of Architecture and Design	
Affiliation	University American College Skopje, Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia
Funding date	2015
Open Access	Yes
Impact score	N/D
North-South composition in the Board	95% South – 5% North

SEEJAD promotes a wide range of research areas in architecture and design in the Eastern European region. The journal promotes the advancement of empirical and theoretical research papers through interdisciplinarity in the related fields of architecture and design, providing a link between theory and practice for researchers and practising professionals.

SOUTH AMERICA

G Strategic Design Research Journal	
Affiliation	University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos, Brazil
Funding date	2019
Open Access	Yes
Impact score	0,44
North-South composition in the Board	97% South – 3% North

SDRJ focuses on the design potentials for the elaboration of strategies and the search for innovation related to any kind of organisation, educational institution, cooperative, association or movement. It considers the strategic contribution of design in all the fields of its practice, such as product and service development, communication, fashion, social and cultural innovation, or technology. SDRJ is a cross-cultural and cross-disciplinary forum for academic discussion, debate and criticism; it focuses on the dialogue between academia and creative industries. Their approach to internationalisation has always been inclusive since they accept articles written in Portuguese, English, Spanish, Italian and French; the aim is to strengthen the Latin Network for the Development of Design Processes.

4 Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing: A Community-Led Approach

In the following paragraphs, the research aims at acquiring as a foundational base the principles and theoretic debates presented in the previous paragraphs and report how they have been experimented in two specific occasions:

1. During the focus group PRO.DES Workshop within the Italian Design Society (in 2023)
2. During the establishment of a Publishing Alliance between two design journals: *DIID.disegno industriale industrial design* and *Strategic Design Research Journal*.

The described application fields result in significant opportunities not only to gather feedback and thoughts from design researchers in Italy and globally, but also to establish and develop a methodological approach to change in the scientific publication industry that is bottom-up and community-led. The design community in this sense can prove to be pioneers and experience a process of change that is not institutionally imposed.

The following paragraphs will delve into the two projects.

4.1 Plurality in Design Publication: **PRO.DES** Workshop within the Italian Design Society

In the framework of the bottom-up focus group within the **Italian Design Society** (SID), created by the Italian design scholars Eleonora Lupo (Politecnico di Milano), Elena Maria Formia (Università di Bologna) and Dario Scodeller (Università di Ferrara), this research was able to gather some feedback and data from a workshop on the issue of "*Pluriversity in Design Publishing*".

As the aim of the PRO.DES focus group is to collect feedback and map innovative case studies among the Italian design community concerning the design publishing practices, workshop delved into the:

Openness and inclusiveness (non-exclusively mainstream approach regarding the Global South-Global North relationship).

The second focus group of PRO.DES was dedicated to Plurality in Design Publication. The workshop included 5 participants; 3 Professors and 2 PhD Students. The results of the brainstorming workshop are very significant:

Inclusion and representation:

Various perspectives contribute to concepts of tokenism, prejudice, and subjectivity in the formulation of consultative and participatory questionnaires. It is concerned with the dominance of Anglo-American perspectives in editing. Examples in the discussion such as "prejudices in scientific boards and their geographic composition" and "dominance of Western values" show that participants are aware of a systemic disequilibrium in terms of representation and inclusivity inside scientific journals.

Challenges in editorial publishing:

Participants highlighted issues including "process acceleration" and "accessibility" and "transparency" management in public statements. Through the use of rhetoric and the concept of "participation in co-creation," the discussion suggests the necessity of true collaboration in editing. Other areas of interest include the political-cultural aspect of editing.

Best practices in editorial politics:

One note collected during the brainstorming illustrates the best practices and success stories related to diversity, while another highlights the need to speed up processes or pay closer attention to various cultural issues (for example, the shared thought about "out of the European context"). The role of editors and consultative committees has been discussed, with special attention to their role in promoting the inclusivity and accessibility of the articles.

Power and decision-making:

These reflections demonstrate the questions of transparency and editorial committees in determining what should be made public or what should be given priority. The mention of who makes the choice reflects the need to understand and improve academic editing processes.

Based on these findings collected during the focus group, there is a clear call for more inclusive, transparent, and culturally varied procedures in scientific publication, particularly in domains like design. Editors and publishers should utilize these talks to establish methods that decrease prejudice and encourage greater involvement from underrepresented regions. Moreover, the reoccurring issue of prejudice and exclusion on advisory boards calls for a change in how peer reviewers and editorial committees are chosen, resulting in more diverse and representative boards. This connects to the issue of expanding the recognition of the global design research. In design cultures, where cultural values, context, and local practices are intrinsic, these ideas might be critical in developing journals that value cultural diversity.

4.2 Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing: A Manifesto for a Publishing Alliance

During the third year of the Doctoral Research, I had the opportunity to participate, as Associate Editor, in the establishment of a new Publishing Alliance between **DIID.disegno industriale industrial design** Italian Journal, affiliated with the University of Bologna, and the Brazilian **Strategic Design Research Journal**, affiliated to UNISINOS University.

Fig. 4: Cover issues of the two Journals (DIID and SDRJ) Partners of the Publishing Alliance.

diid

73

disegno industriale industrial design teoria pòiesis praxis diid.it

Elena Alfaro, Margherita Ascari, Luca Barbieri, Alberto Bassi, Andrea Boeri, Francesca Bonetti, Paolo Bonora, Lucilla Calogero, Giorgio Casoni, Andrea Cattabriga, Flaviano Celaschi, Erik Ciravegna, Laura Daglio, Michele De Chirico, Daniele Fanzini, Franco Fassio, Paolo Franzo, Pietro Gamberini, Valentina Gianfrate, Ami Liçaj, Danila Longo, Giuseppe Lotti, Martina Massari, Lorela Mehmeti, Elena Mussinelli, Tonino Paris, Irina Rotaru, Francesca Sabatini, Andreas Sicklinger, Laura Succini, Michele Trimarchi, Raffaella Trocchianesi, Alessandra Vaccari, Elena Vai, Francesca Zanella

This initiative, initiated in Spring 2024, by the Editorial Teams of both Journals, has been called and developed as the result of a historical urgency of innovating the design publishing framework. In the following diagram, the main points of the long-term vision of this alliance are summarized in **Fig. 5**.

For the end of this research project, it is highly significant to include in the discourse the draft of the Manifesto for the Publishing Alliance, an initiative aimed at reshaping and strengthening our approach to scholarly publishing. This manifesto will serve as the foundation for the collective commitment to uphold core principles that guide transparent, inclusive, and open-access publishing practices in design knowledge. Each journal wishing to join the Alliance will need to align with these principles, ensuring that our community of design researchers moves forward with shared values and goals. However, this manifesto is not set in stone, it is a draft. As the Partners of the Alliance believe in co-creation and collective intelligence, this manifesto will be collaboratively shaped in a future workshop, inviting editors, researchers, publishers, and other actors from the design publishing ecosystem to refine this document. Through dialogue and collaboration, the manifesto will be created to reflect the needs and aspirations of this Alliance.

The methodology guiding this process is simple but effective: starting with the principle, it reflects with concrete actions, and from there, these actions reflect with the editorial operations that put these values into practice. This structured approach will allow the Publishing Alliance to transform high-level ideals into real, impactful practices in the journals and publications part of the Alliance.

Fig. 5: Long Term Vision of Publishing Alliance.

Long Term Vision of the Publishing Alliance

Strategies for Sustainable Collaboration

Develop robust strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of the collaborative efforts, focusing on both operational and financial stability.

Challenge Standardization in Publishing

Actively work against the standardization of the publishing sector to foster diversity, creativity, and innovation in research dissemination.

Building a Collaborative Alliance

Establish a long-term alliance that provides an alternative to hegemonic, for-profit editorial entities, promoting an open and equitable publishing environment.

Manifesto of Shared Values

Create and uphold a manifesto that clearly outlines the shared values and principles guiding the collaboration, ensuring alignment and commitment across all participants.

MANIFESTO FOR A DESIGN PUBLISHING ALLIANCE

PRINCIPLE	ACTION	EDITORIAL OPERATION
<p>1. Principle of Open Access and Open Knowledge in Scholar Dissemination.</p> <p>Scientific knowledge should be freely accessible to all, fostering open discussions and transparent sharing of research findings. This ensures equitable access to research and promotes innovation, particularly in underfunded and developing regions.</p>	<p>Call for active engagement from governments and research institutions to prioritize and financially support open access journals over those controlled by major commercial publishers. By reallocating resources and funding towards open access initiatives, these entities can help break down barriers to knowledge, ensuring that research outputs remain accessible to all, regardless of economic or geographic constraints.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize meetings and roundtables with relevant governmental entities. - Advocate for Creative Commons Licenses. - Support Journals to search for fundings. - Establish Business / Consultancy Models for Open Access Journals that can provide economic support (Proceedings, Special Issues, etc.)
<p>2. Promote Interdisciplinary Research in Design Knowledge and Foster Interdisciplinary publishing models.</p> <p>We believe that design discipline promotes interdisciplinary research and thus it drives innovation to address complex global challenges.</p>	<p>Advocate for the experimentation with formats – incorporating diversity and interdisciplinary approaches through design – to enhance experimentation as a leverage for creation, especially given the capabilities of the digital medium.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourage and support cross-disciplinary projects and submissions where design discipline stands as catalyzer in bridging different scientific fields to create new knowledge and solutions. - Preparing an open visual map which systematizes the relation between other scientific disciplines and design for each Journal of the Alliance.
<p>3. Commitment to Inclusivity in Design Cultures.</p> <p>We aim to foster an open and inclusive collaborative environment that welcomes diverse voices in the ecology of knowledges and practices, from different cultures and backgrounds, to promote alternative and less institutionalized knowledge from both LMIC countries.</p>	<p>We seek to include underrepresented groups, perspectives and practices in all aspects, from authorship to peer review, in the dissemination and knowledge production of design cultures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Special Issues allowing publication in other idioms and new formats (different ways of narratives and rhetorics), - Enlarge Reviewers’ Pool and Editorial Board to represent all the voices from all regions and sub-disciplines - Organize webinars or events with people representing other-than-hegemonic institutions. - Organize courses with early-career researchers to get familiar with design knowledge production practices and ecosystem

<p>4. Building Alternative Models to Hegemonic Publishing Practices.</p> <p>We stand against the monopolization of knowledge by for-profit publishers and strive to provide equitable access to research.</p>	<p>Develop alternative publishing models that prioritize accessibility, affordability, and the dissemination of knowledge for all communities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing this Publishing Alliance can represent a concrete editorial process to establish an alternative model of institutionalization which is not managed by for-profit Publishers, but is managed by Editors. - Use not-for profit platforms and collaborate with not-governmental organizations.
<p>5. Efficient and Valued Evaluation Process in Design Knowledge Production.</p> <p>Both the quality and timeliness of peer reviews are essential in the editorial process. An efficient review system enhances the publishing workflow while also recognizing and valuing the critical contributions of reviewers.</p>	<p>Establish clear guidelines and expectations for reviews, alongside providing tools and resources that support reviewers in delivering thoughtful, thorough evaluations. Implement strategies to formally recognize and reward reviewers' contributions, whether through public acknowledgment, incentives, or formal metrics of recognition.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce systems to track and publicly acknowledge reviewers' contributions, such as badges, certificates, or credit on platforms like ORCID or ReviewersCredits. - Offering incentives, such as discounts on journal subscriptions, conferences or professional development opportunities, to motivate reviewers.

This manifesto is a work in progress, co-created and evolving in alignment with the mission of the Design Publishing Alliance. Nevertheless, it already reflects the design community's commitment to fostering a more inclusive, transparent, and distributed ecosystem for design publishing.

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**Iterative
Prototyping of
an Alternative
Peer–Review
Model for Design
Journals:
*The Collaborative
Revision Model
(Co.Re)***

This chapter introduces and presents an alternative model of the peer review process, called the Co.Re (Collaborative Revision) Model, that has been experimented at the nonprofit organisation Knowledge Futures during the research semester abroad carried out in the United States. Knowledge Futures is an independent organisation powered by academic, industry, and advocacy groups and it aims to support products and protocols to make knowledge open and accessible to all. By developing an analysis of current alternative assessment platforms or case studies of reviewers' recognition (1.3, 1.4) based on specific methodological criteria, the project identifies the Editorial Personas of the editorial workflow by analyzing the potential needs of each editorial persona – Author, Peer Reviewer, Editorial Manager, and Reader – within the context of this model (2.1; 2.2; 2.3). Based on this comprehensive and technical study, an alternative assessment model is prototyped (3.1, 3.2). It is significant to highlight that this analysis has been possible thanks to the direct observation of the editorial operations carried out as Associate Editor at the Design Journal: *DIID.disegno industriale industrial design* on the Open Journal System (OJS) platform. The Co.Re Model aims to innovate traditional peer review by incorporating collaborative and interactive elements of conversation experience that enhance transparency, engagement, and constructive feedback. Secondly, the research outlines the Co.Re Model by providing a detailed description of the model's structure, processes, and key features (4.1; 4.2; 4.3). By examining the Co.Re Model, this chapter aims to showcase its potential to propose a new innovative approach for Design Knowledge assessment, within the established norms of the academic system, contributing to the ongoing evolution of design scholarly publishing (5.1, 5.2, 5.3).

‡ Increasing Recognition and Acknowledgement of Reviewers: State of the Art

This experimentation aims to foster discussion on innovative peer review models designed to make published information more useful and reusable within the scholarly community. The mission of the open access movement involves more than mere accessibility and final publication outcomes; it must represent a comprehensive methodology and guiding principle applicable to all stages of the publication process, from manuscript submission to sharing final research findings. Failure to do so could result in contradictory and incomplete implementation of open access principles. Continuing the discourse from our previous issue on promotion, tenure, and academic recognition models, we address the problematic "publish or perish" mentality and the gatekeeping dynamics in scientific dissemination, where peer review serves as a major gatekeeper for both quality and quantity. Given the ongoing need to extend open access principles throughout the entire editorial workflow, the discussion focuses on enhancing accessibility during the critical phase of peer review. Despite its significance, peer review's status and purpose are often contested, with concerns about trust, bias, abuse, and reliability (Trovò et al, 2021).

This model aims to re-assess how the outcomes and the process of the peer review system can be structured to increase transparency and build trust in the publishing system. This prototype is based on a meta-experiment¹ on peer review process which explores alternative and unconventional peer review models, characterized by an open and transparent conversation between two reviewers which will be published alongside the original article. Peer review, the cornerstone of scholarly publishing, is undergoing a transformative shift towards a more collaborative and sustainable approach (as described in Chapter 2). Originally, peer review was intended as mutual control of scientific results by peers in the same discipline. However, the commercialization of scientific publishing has turned the process into a tool of a hyper-competitive industry, intertwined with academic career progression. Nowadays, peer review is described as a "black box" (Tennant et al., 2017); to address this, various scientific and not-scientific communities are increasingly experimenting with alternative methodologies aimed at maximizing peer review's effectiveness and impact beyond the publication lifespan. The criticalities of the current traditional structure of peer review that are methodologically addressed in this project encompass several aspects, that can be identified in the following table (Tab. I).

¹ Meta-experiment or meta-test is the activity aiming to test a function while providing no data to test it.

Inefficiency

The traditional peer review process proves to be inefficient for both structural and behavioral reasons. Its rigid framework, culminating in binary recommendations, does not foster a constructive dialogue. Authors often perceive the feedback as judgmental directives from an authoritative figure, which they feel compelled to address solely to achieve publication. On the other hand, reviewers receive no formal recognition for their fundamental contributions to the scientific community. Their efforts are often unrewarded, both in terms of recognition and monetary compensation for the time and effort invested. The issue of behavioural incentivization within the peer-review culture remains a subject of strong debate.

Lack of transparency

Anonymized peer review lacks transparency: reviewers' comments and recommendations are not shared with the audience, and their identities remain undisclosed to both the author and the readers. This lack of transparency contributes to the unrecognized role of reviewers in the publication process. Enhancing transparency could be the first step towards acknowledging the fundamental contributions of reviewers to scholarly publications. However, on the other hand, this anonymity also allows reviewers to be shielded from accountability when they provide low-quality or biased reviews. This lack of transparency undermines trust and reliability in the review process, in addition to the loss of knowledge granularity (Pawlak, 1998).

Obsolescence

The content of reviews might be considered obsolete for two reasons. First, reviewers' comments and suggestions are not publicly available, making this editorial work useless and unreferenced in scholarly debate. This lack of visibility prevents vital input from being added to the academic debate and slows the development of common knowledge. Second, since the review information is inaccessible, the article loses crucial procedural context during the transition and alteration from the initial submission to the amended version based on the reviewers' remarks. Without access to the review content, readers and future scholars miss out on understanding the evolution of the manuscript and the reasons behind the revisions, which reduces the potential effect of the publication.

Tab. VI: Criticalities of peer review process.

Starting from this panorama of issues, the goal is to propose a dynamic and transformative perspective on peer review. This research aims to introduce a flexible review format that emphasizes direct conversation between reviewers, fostering a more interactive and constructive evaluation process. This approach seeks to replace the traditional, rigid review system with a dynamic evaluation model that addresses specific review aspects in real time. By moving away from a blind, static framework, we hope to create a more transparent, engaging, and effective review process that enhances the quality and impact of scholarly publications.

Fig. 1: Diagram summarising the main issues of the Peer Review Process. By the Author.

1-1 AI in Scientific Publishing: Introduction to Opportunities and Challenges

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic publishing has transitioned from speculative discussion to tangible implementation. Current debates focus on the opportunities and risks, key beneficiaries and those potentially excluded, and the contexts and timeframes over which these changes will occur within this sector (Wiley, 2023). Scholarly communication and dissemination are under strain; authors expect time-efficient and rigorous peer review processes, while finding appropriate reviewers for submissions has become increasingly time-consuming for editors and publishers (Gibney, 2023). This trend appears as an undesirable byproduct of the increasing volume of publications observed in recent decades. AI has emerged as a transformative tool across various stages of the editorial process. For instance, publishers like Frontiers have utilized AI in pre-peer review quality checks since 2018 via the in-house developed tool Artificial Intelligence Review Assistant (AIRA) (Frontiers, 2018). Similarly, AI-driven tools can analyze large datasets, identify trends, and generate hypotheses, significantly accelerating the research process (Liu et al., 2023).

The current debate also focuses on the evolving role of AI in scientific publishing, acknowledging the ethical dimensions of AI adoption concerning transparency, accountability, and the potential risks of over-reliance. Notably, AI's role in content generation has raised concerns about the integrity of scientific literature, as AI-generated content may lack the nuanced understanding inherent in human authorship (Van Noorden, 2023).

While the relevance of AI in scientific publishing is undeniable, this introduction serves as an entry point into the discussion rather than a central focus of this research. The implications of AI for the automation of editorial processes, peer review, and broader publishing workflows constitute a vast and complex area that would require dedicated research. As such, this study does not delve into these aspects in depth but instead lays the groundwork for future investigations. Hopefully, future research will build upon the results of this thesis to explore the role of AI in optimizing and automating scientific publishing processes.

2-Case Studies Collection on Alternative Peer Review Formats

In this section, the research presents a selection of case studies showcasing several alternative peer review formats. These case studies provide insights into alternative approaches to peer review and serve as benchmarks for developing the review model proposed in this doctoral research. By analyzing the innovation features as well as the characteristics of these case studies, the goal is to find the

most balanced model between innovation and the requests of the traditional academic system for scientific recognition.

The selected case studies were chosen based on the following criteria:

<p>Relevance to peer review process: Each case study focuses specifically on innovations within the peer review process, ensuring they are directly applicable to the scope of this research.</p>	<p>Originality and pioneering status: The case studies are recognized as original and up to date by the scientific publishing community, highlighting their significance in advancing peer review methodologies.</p>
<p>Impact and influence: The case studies demonstrate a measurable impact on the scholarly communication landscape, proving scalability for broader adoption.</p>	<p>Diversity of approaches: To provide a comprehensive analysis, the collection includes a diverse range of approaches and models, from open peer review to post-publication review and beyond.</p>

The methodology of this selection has intentionally excluded:

- 1) **Platforms/websites not updated in the last two years:** make sure that the case studies reflect current practices and remain relevant to contemporary discussions on peer review innovation.
- 2) **Platforms linked to social media accounts (e.g., Twitter):** focusing on dedicated peer review platforms rather than those driven by social media interactions.
- 3) **Models with no potential innovation:** excluding models that do not offer significant improvements from traditional peer review processes.

This selection is not comprehensive and is primarily based on hand research and direct observation of case studies collected during their experience at Knowledge Futures, where The organization's team provided a list of innovative platforms they have worked with over the years.

FOCUS

**Case Studies
Collection:
Alternative
Peer Review
Models**

ResearchHub

<https://www.researchhub.foundation/>

Description: The ResearchHub Foundation is a global decentralized community that aims to align incentives in academia, making science more open and collaborative using ResearchCoin (\$RSC).

Innovation features: Open forum for discussion of articles. Within the ResearchHub platform, research papers are stored and grouped in 'Hubs' by area of research. Individual Hubs act as live journals within focused areas, within highly upvoted posts. (i.e the paper and its associated summary and discussion) moving to the top of each Hub. Users can create a ResearchHub page for any paper, allowing for summary and discussion. It is a very engaging way of publishing, both for authors and the audience, that can make notes and take part in a discussion with the authors in sort of "blog" dynamic.

Peer-review process: The reviewer is offered 150 ResearchCoins for the Review. The reviewers' name and comments are publicly displayed along with the article. The audience can REPLY or TIP or CITE the reviews.

Issues:

1. Isolation from Traditional Academic Publishing

Visibility and Credibility: ResearchHub might struggle to gain the same level of recognition and credibility as traditional journals, which are often associated with established academic institutions.

Integration with Existing Systems: Researchers might find it difficult to integrate their work on ResearchHub with traditional academic systems, such as citation indexes, university repositories, and tenure evaluations. **Adoption and Participation:** Encouraging widespread adoption among researchers who are accustomed to traditional publishing models could be challenging.

2. The peer review process on ResearchHub lacks the oversight of an editorial manager, potentially leading to inconsistent review quality and reliability. Quality Control: Without a dedicated editorial manager, there may be variations in the quality and thoroughness of reviews.

Bias and Fairness: The lack of oversight might also lead to potential biases and unfair reviews, as there is no central authority to mediate disputes.

3. The functionality and benefits of ResearchCoin (RSC) are not clearly communicated, which might hinder user engagement and participation.

PeeryView

<https://peeryview.org/>

Description: PeeryView is a new concept for scientific publishing: subjective, decentralized, and interoperable.

Innovation potential: Weighted subjective reviews; open protocol; omnigram.

Subjective: When you weight (vote on) another user, that user becomes part of your network. Other users that they've weighted become part of your extended network. Your view of site content, such as which posts you see and in what order, and the ratings and comments you see in posts, depends entirely on the users in your network. **Decentralized:** Moderation of site content is achieved by users weighting each other. We don't use black-box algorithms to determine what you see, so you can vote down a user and be assured you'll never see their content. And because votes are publicly visible by default, users have an incentive to post good content. **Interoperable:** The site is completely open-source. Moreover, data stored on the site follows a standardized format, and is served over the Braid protocol. This means that you have no obligation to use the site just because your friends are: if you don't like the frontend, you can host your own customized instance and set it to pull posts and data from anywhere else.

Peer-review process: The peer review is based on the vote of users among them. Each user can vote another user's post in the network. Below the usergram is a list of posts, sorted based on post votes. Like reddit or hackernews, a post is just a link and a title. On the right, you'll notice a **slidergram**, which is similar to the omnigram. The slidergram shows everyone's votes on the post.

Issues: The platform is developed as a blog. Publications are published along with posts, including reflections, thoughts and questions. Users are not categorized.

The Longevity Decentralized Review

<https://longevity.review/faq>

Description: Provides funding for researchers to review each other's work. It addresses critical issues with academic journals: it is an opt-in mechanism for researchers to get extra eyes on their work.

Innovation potential: It is an on-demand peer review service. There is a free and paid tier. Articles from websites known as "Rxiv" (pronounced "archive") [preprint servers](#), BioRxiv, MedRxiv, and Arxiv are auto-posted daily to the homepage. The incentive for peer reviewing these freely posted manuscripts is to receive a share of the donations given to TLDR. The paid tier differs in that it allows researchers to post their work directly to have it reviewed. Reviewers have extra incentive to review paid manuscripts because they not only receive a portion of the total donations but also a portion of the total subscriptions.

Peer-review process: TLDR reviewing is similar to traditional peer reviewing, however, it differs in that it is quantitative. The ranking of each work is based on upvotes by ones peers. It is similar to how it's done at Hacker News. Also the reviews are ranked by upvotes. Anyone can review a work by clicking 'Write review' under each manuscript. TLDRs have value when compared to traditional reviews because though they will likely be shorter than traditional peer reviews, they can be faster and the voting can enable a broader consensus. This contrasts with traditional peer review that is performed by a relative small number of people (2-4). Researchers can evaluate the reviews using upvoting and commenting. This feedback helps reviewers grow their reputations and determine their payouts.

Issues: While the TLDR peer review system addresses some critical issues with traditional academic journals, it also has notable shortcomings:

- 1- Lack of clarity in the business model: The system mentions a share of donations and a paid tier, but it is not clear how sustainable these funding mechanisms are in the long term.
- 2- Actual benefits to researchers: while reviewers are incentivized with donations and subscription shares, it is uncertain how regular or substantial these payments are.
- 3- Quality and rigour of reviews: the emphasis on upvotes and quantitative measures may lead to popularity-based reviews rather than those based on rigorous academic scrutiny. Important but niche research might not receive the attention it deserves.

OpenReview

openreview.net

Description: Provides a platform for peer review that generalizes over many gradations of openness, allowing conference organizers, journals, and other "reviewing entities" to configure the specific policy of their choice.

Innovation potential: the OR platform innovates academic publishing by streamlining submission and coordination through a shared and distributed system. It promotes open access with free access to papers and submissions. OpenReview supports open discussion by hosting accepted papers with reviews and comments, and maintaining a continued discussion forum. Editors control the review structure and access. The platform also includes an open recommendations system for reviewer-paper matching and paper recommendations.

Peer-review process: Reviews and revisions are public and accessible to the audience. Each team manages the review process based on their editorial workflow. The editorial teams are free to customise their workflow on the platform. Authors can respond to the reviewer's comments online. Reviewers are free to display their identity. Revisions are also publishing and readers can compare different versions of the article (when available by the editorial team).

Issues: The OpenReview platform introduces several innovative features to transform academic publishing, but it also faces some significant issues. Despite its potential, the platform's usability and credibility present challenges.

1. User Experience and navigation: The platform is not user-friendly and can be difficult to navigate. This complexity can deter users from fully engaging with the system, thereby limiting its effectiveness and adoption.

2. Credibility and recognition of reviewers: Although reviewers are free to display their identity, many choose to use pseudonyms. This anonymity can undermine the credibility and recognition of the reviews, as users cannot verify the qualifications or expertise of the reviewers. The use of fake names reduces accountability, which can affect the trustworthiness and perceived quality of the reviews.

Crown Preprint Review

<https://asapbio.org/crowd-preprint-review>

Description: In 2021, ASAPbio launched initiatives to facilitate public reviews on preprints, drawing inspiration from the crowd review model pioneered by the journal *Synlett*. The organization coordinated a group of researchers to provide comments on cell biology preprints, producing 14 public reviews. Due to the high level of engagement from reviewers, ASAPbio extended these activities into 2022.

Innovation potential: The crowd preprint review approach provides a way to engage in public preprint feedback while mitigating those concerns, as it provides a format that gives flexibility on what comments to provide and generates public reviews that do not link the commenter's identity to specific comments in the review.

Peer-review process: There are different crowds with specific scopes. Each crowd circulates a new preprint for comments every two weeks, and crowd members are asked to contribute comments over the following 14 days. Crowd members provide comments via a collaborative Google Doc. After the commenting period, a collective synthesis of the comments are posted as a public review on the preprint. Those public reviews also listed on Sciety.

Issues: The platform uses Google Docs to provide comments; while using Google Docs for comments might offer convenience, it raises significant concerns regarding privacy, control, integration, and standardization. These issues could impact the security, confidentiality, and effectiveness of the peer review process.

Preprint Club

www.preprintclub.com

Description: Cross-institutional Preprint Journal Club posting public reviews of preprints.

Innovation potential: A joint immunology preprint journal club during which we assess up-and-coming trends in the field of immunology. Using a community-based effort, it offers a new model of preprint reviewing in a transparent and rewarding manner.

Peer-review process: Transparent, open and public. The Preprint Club is organized in small hubs of 2-4 collaborative institutions. Once a Preprint Club hub has formed, an online schedule is formed with alternate presenters, ideally making sure that presentation slots are evenly distributed. Two presenters are scheduled per week and session. The presenters select a recent preprint of their choice, which is then presented and discussed during the online journal club session. Each participant uses a three-category voting system to rank the preprint with a score of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest. Preprints are assessed based on their novelty (are the findings novel and original?), their scientific quality (quality of experimental design and data obtained, and how well they support the authors' conclusions) and their significance (how likely this study is going to impact its research field and immunology in general). After the journal club, presenters are encouraged to take aboard the feedback from the discussion and write up a peer review digest to give feedback to the preprint authors. This feedback is uploaded on the Preprint Club Website and made publicly available.

Issues: The Crowd reviewers are part of a Google group. Their comments are visible by any member of that group but not to the public. For the synthesized review that is publicly posted, the team aggregates the comments and list contributors as a list, without linking specific comments to the commenter. A Crowd member collects the comments on the preprint at the end of the commenting period for a paper and generate a synthesis. This consolidates comments related to different sections of the paper for ease of reading. There are any edits done for content, except if any concerns arise about the tone or nature of the comment, in which case, ASAPbio can decide to exclude specific comments from the synthesis. The synthesized review is posted publicly on the preprint. Those who contributed comments are acknowledged in the synthesized review, without linking specific comments to the commenter.

Peer Community In <https://peercommunityin.org/>

Description: It is a free recommendation process of scientific preprints based on peer reviews and a journal. The platform is based on thematic Peer Community In (PCI). The role of the thematic PCIs is to organise the evaluation of preprints in their field and, for the texts accepted, to publish a recommendation text with the reviews, converting the recommended text into a final, valid and citable article.

Innovation potential: The thematic PCIs evaluate preprints in their scientific fields based on rigorous peer review. After evaluation, the PCIs may recommend those preprints, to make them complete, reliable and citable articles, without the need for publication in 'traditional' journals. Authors who need to publish their article in a journal can publish it for free in Peer Community Journal or submit it to a PCI-friendly or other journal.

Peer-review process: The recommendation of an article is a positive editorial decision made by a recommender based on at least two rigorous peer reviews and after one or several rounds of peer reviews. The recommendations are published in the corresponding thematic PCI websites with a DOI and can be cited. Once recommended by PCI, articles become citable valid references, similar to journal articles, but they can still be submitted to a journal or directly published in the Peer Community Journal

Issues: While Peer Community In (PCI) offers an innovative approach to evaluating and recommending preprints, it faces some notable challenges. The platform is based on preprints, which are not always familiar or widely accepted within the academic community. Researchers, especially those at the beginning of their careers or in more traditional fields, may be unfamiliar with this mode of publication and may view it as less credible than traditional journal articles. Additionally, the institutional recognition of preprints can be a concern. PCI's recommendations, though rigorous and citable, might not carry the same weight as publications in established journals. This can impact researchers' career advancement and academic recognition, as preprints are often perceived as less prestigious compared to articles published in traditional peer-reviewed journals.

preLights <https://prelights.biologists.com/>

Description: Preprint highlights service run by the biological community and supported by The Company of Biologists. Here, a team of scientists regularly review, highlight and comment on preprints they feel are of interest to the biological community, based on specific field categories.

Innovation potential: The service is based on a community which carefully selected group of early-career researchers with a shared interest in reviewing and communicating new research. The service is supported by The Company of Biologists, but the opinions and views expressed on this website are those of the community.

Peer-review process: A team of scientists from the community select, highlight and comment on preprints they feel are of particular interest to the biological community. You'll find a summary of each preprint, the reasons it was selected and the selector's thoughts on its significance. You might also see relevant comments from the preprints' authors. All preLight posts have a permanent DOI. The DOI is displayed on the bottom of the highlight seven days after it is posted on the website. Anyone can comment on a preLights post. At the end of each post the reader sees a box giving the option to comment.

Issues: It does not publish pre-prints, but only highlights pre-prints from other publications servers. preLight posts do not count as a publication, nor do they impact the peer review and publication process of preprinted manuscripts. PreLights are preprint highlights, offering a 'News & Views' type perspective on new research that has already been posted on a preprint server.

ReviewerCredits

<https://www.reviewercredits.com/>

Description: Peer Review Recognition Service for Professional Researchers. The main users of this service are Peer-reviewers and Journals/Publishers.

Innovation potential:

For peer-reviewers: Researchers use ReviewerCredits to gain recognition for their academic profiles and to reward their peer review efforts. Researchers can register and enrich their peer reviewer profile at no cost by importing reviews using their ORCID ID. For each review completed, researchers earn tangible ReviewerCredits, which can be redeemed for publishing discounts, editorial services, translation services, and more. Additionally, they can enhance their multilevel cross-publisher performance metrics and Reviewer Contribution Index, and receive trusted certification for their academic contributions.

For Journals/Publishers: Journals can use ReviewerCredits to recognize and reward their peer reviewers. They can register their journal's profile and invite peer reviewers, with automatic registration of performed reviews and reviewer performance through seamless integrations. Journals can reward reviewers with tangible ReviewerCredits, which are redeemable for publishing discounts, editorial services, translation services, and more. They can track performance metrics and Reviewer Contribution Index to gain trusted certification for their peer review processes, enhancing the visibility and credibility of their journal.

Peer-review process: //

Issues: The ReviewerCredits system offers an interesting approach by providing monetary recognition to peer reviewers, aiming to enhance their credibility and reward their efforts. However, several issues arise in analyzing this model:

Lack of clear leverage: while ReviewerCredits incentivizes reviewers with tangible rewards, it remains unclear how this system leverages broader changes in the peer review process. The impact on the overall peer review ecosystem and how it influences systemic improvements or shifts in peer review practices is not well defined.

Sustainability: the business model's long-term sustainability is also a concern. It relies on the continuous issuance and redemption of credits, but the financial viability and operational scalability of this model need to be addressed.

2.1 Identifying Editorial Personas and needs analysis mapping of the publication cycle

In order to ensure that the Co.Re model effectively addresses the requirements of all key stakeholders involved in the peer review process, it is necessary to identify and define the stakeholders of the editorial workflow, named as editorial personas. The editorial personas include:

- a) **Author:** Researcher who contributes their work for publication.
- b) **Reviewer:** Expert of the research community who evaluates the quality and validity of submitted research.
- c) **Editorial Manager:** the individual responsible for overseeing the editorial process and ensuring the integrity of the publication.
- d) **Reader:** Member of the academic community and the general public who consume and utilize the published research.

Based on this needs analysis, the proposed review model has been developed to address and integrate the requirements and expectations of each persona, ensuring a comprehensive and balanced approach to peer review innovation.

2.2 Mapping Editorial Personas' Needs and Needs Analysis in the Editorial Workflow

The following section aims to analyze and describe the potential needs of each editorial persona [AUTHOR, REVIEWER, EDITORIAL MANAGER, READER], identified for the specific purpose of this model. Based on the needs' analysis, the model has been developed.

AUTHOR

Efficient submission process	A streamlined, user-friendly system for submitting manuscripts.
Constructive feedback	High-quality, detailed, and constructive peer reviews to improve the manuscript.
Visibility and impact	Opportunities to increase the visibility and impact of their work through innovative dissemination methods.
Recognition	Acknowledgment of their contributions and engagement with the academic community.

REVIEWER

Clear guidelines	Access to comprehensive guidelines and criteria for conducting reviews.
Efficient Review process	Access to comprehensive guidelines and criteria for conducting reviews.
Recognition and incentives	Tangible incentives and recognition for their contributions.
Constructive interaction	Opportunities for constructive interaction with authors and other reviewers.

EDITORIAL MANAGER

Control over the workflow	The need for tools that facilitate efficient management of the submission, review, and revision stages.
Increase the quality of publication	Ensuring that the peer review process is thorough and respectful.
Widen readership	Strategies and tools to increase the dissemination and visibility of published research to a broader audience.
Target the authors	Implementing initiatives to attract high-quality submissions from reputable researchers and institutions.
Make all information accessible and reusable	Ensuring that all data, reviews, and related materials are accessible and can be reused by the academic community.

READER

Access the Article	Access the article, in any form, on a user-friendly platform, where the parts of the article are selectable.
Cite the Article	Ensuring that the Article is identified (DOI) and is fully citable.
Contextualize the content and be able to engage in the discourse	Being able to read the content by engaging in the broader context of the knowledge field, by positioning the article in a specific disciplinary topic and research community.
Identify the Authors and Reviewers	Being able to read and access the name of Authors and reviewers to increase transparency and understanding of the knowledge created by the submission and publication of the article, as well as identify the experts engaged in the topic.
Understand the evolution of the manuscript throughout the editorial process.	Understanding how the initial article has changed during the editorial process, especially after the peer review process.

2.2 Integrating Needs into an Open Peer-Review Model: an Editorial Storyboard

The following phase of the Co.Re (Collaborative Revision) Model design involved integrating the needs identified in the previous section into the editorial publication process for each editorial persona. This was achieved through the creation of a narrative editorial storyboard, which illustrates how the CoRe Model addresses and fulfills these needs at each stage of the publication process.

The storyboard outlines the journey of each editorial persona, Author, Peer Reviewer, Editorial Manager, and Reader, highlighting key interactions and features of the Co.Re Model that cater to their specific requirements. By mapping out these interactions, the storyboard ensures that the needs of all personas are seamlessly integrated into a cohesive and functional editorial process.

AUTHOR

Goals:

1. Submit a “form” [article/image/video (multimodal article)]
2. Check the submission status
3. Access both reviews and the names of the reviewers
4. Make revisions to the submitted article once reviews have been received.
5. Access/download/cite the form
6. Access and visualize publicly the reviews I received connected to the form.

USER-STORY ANALYSIS

- As a [author], I want to be able to [upload] a document, so that I can [complete] a submission.
- As a [author], I want to be able to [check] the status of the submission process **so I know what’s going on with my submission and when to respond to reviewer comments.**
- As a [author], I want to be able to [access] the reviews and the name of the reviewers after they make their initial remarks so that I can [interact] with the reviews **I can gain an understanding/synthesis of what the reviewers comment/suggest (especially w/ help of editorial manager) when there are differing opinions from the reviewers. This will also strengthen community relations amongst authors and reviewers. Especially compared to writing a paper, which oftentimes is collaborative, this format would invite that collaboration during the review process.**

- As a [author], I do not receive a decision from the reviewers about publication **so that I can focus on the comments from the reviewers. The subjectivity of the reviewers' opinion of major/minor is removed and thus forces reviewers to make comments rather than their high-level decision. This allows the author to engage with the comments themselves rather than reckoning with the "major" or "minor" revision label.**
- As a [author], I do not get to [make revisions] to the document or [upload] a revised document **because the experiment is focused on the conversation between me and the reviewers.**
- As a [author], I want to be able to [read] or [visualize] the reviews of the publication document on PubPub². **Because the interaction is published alongside the article, it will force me to really consider what I'm sharing initially and be intentional and meaningful about it. In the long run, this increases the quality of published articles (even though it may mean fewer papers overall or more time spent analyzing the data, it improves the quality of scholarship generally). There may be a hesitation to say something provocative, but the aim is to initiate conversation around the research. Overall, this will strengthen community relations among authors and reviewers. Especially compared to writing a paper, which oftentimes is collaborative, this format would invite that collaboration during the review process.**

REVIEWER

Goals:

1. Download the article
2. Visualize the article on the platform
3. Complete the review
4. Add comments (text, links, images) to the document through a sharing visualization format (e.g. google drive) by highlighting specific portions of the text or timestamps in case of videos.
5. Access the comments of Reviewer 2.
6. Interact with the comments of Reviewer 2 (replying to comments).
7. Access and visualize the review publicly.
8. My name is publicly displayed in the published article as a Contributor Role.

USER-STORY ANALYSIS

- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [download] the article on my device.

² PubPub is the editorial platform developed by Knowledge Futures for the publication of editorial contents by editorial groups. <https://www.knowledgefutures.org/pubpub/>

- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [access/visualize] the article on the platform.
- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [complete] the review article on the platform.
 - As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [comment on] the article on the platform through comments by highlighting specific portions of the text or timestamps in case of videos so that my critiques are anchored to specific parts of the article. This will reduce confusion around what my comments refer to in the author's document.
- As a [reviewer], I want to get [notifications] when other reviewers make a comment so I can know when to respond to their comments and feel compelled to also make my own comments.
- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [access and reply to] the comments of Reviewer 2 on the platform because it offers me a way to communicate with other reviewers about cutting-edge research and new ideas within their field. It's a way I can share my opinions and have a way in the newest research because their comments are available to everyone. Additionally, it reduces the amount of work/time for a second reviewer because they could agree with what reviewer 1 said (a risk of this is that reviewers become reviewers of the review, but then again this is the thing we are designing for a conversation).
- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [have a conversation with] the author after the reviewer's initial remarks because it will strengthen community relations between authors and reviewers. Especially compared to writing a paper, which oftentimes is collaborative, this format would invite that collaboration during the review process.
- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [access and visualize] the review on the publication platform as a citable thing because it will enhance the long-term impact of my voice. With my review being transparent, it becomes another platform for me to share my opinion in a way that's considered legitimate in scholarly circles. Compared to a Twitter post, my options will be indexed along with the article I'm commenting on so it will be easier to recall and find.
- As a [reviewer], I want to be able to [read] my name on the publication as a Contributor Role because it's a chance for me to receive credit for the work that I normally do without recognition. Additionally, because my name is attached to my review, the editor will be able to easily recall my work and good conversations on an article should they want to invite me to review again. Being invited back will feel good because my work has been appreciated by the editor.

EDITORIAL MANAGER

Goals:

1. Check the submission status: info of the authors
2. Download the article
3. Visualize the article on the platform
4. Invite external reviewers
5. Access both reviews
6. Publish the name of reviewers on the final article.

USER-STORY ANALYSIS

- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [access] the submission and the authors' information.
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [download] the submission.
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [visualize] the article on the platform.
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [invite/give access] external reviewers. **I acknowledge that I will have to be extra careful about who's invited to review (probably cannot invite a graduate student to review a tenured prof or vice versa), and that I have to do more work initially with submitted articles because they are the ones accepting or rejecting papers.**
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [read] both reviewers' comments on the article **so I can moderate the conversation between reviewers. This will also increase engagement with readership because posting the review conversation invites more conversation from readers.**
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [publish] the article on the platform.
- As a [editorial manager], I want to be able to [publish] the name of the Reviewers as a Contributor Role **so I can invite them back when a good conversation happens on a paper because I trust that they will have good comments again on a similar submission.**

READER

Goals:

1. Access the review conversations alongside the published article.

USER-STORY ANALYSIS

- As a [reader], I can toggle the review comments so that I can see the peer review process. Mainly, access to the reviews published gives the reader a learning experience. Because I can see what a reviewer is asking for or critiquing in a research article, as a reader I will anticipate the types of questions I'll be asked when I submit a research article eventually. Additionally, much like comments and replies on a video or social media post, the reviews will be just as interesting to me as the article.

3-Methodology of Experimentation: Application at the Knowledge Futures Group (Research Semester Abroad)

The research relies on a six-month research period at the organization: Knowledge Futures (KF). KF is an independent nonprofit organisation powered by academic, industry, and advocacy groups; it aims to support products and protocols to make knowledge open and accessible to all. Founded in 2018 as a partnership between the MIT Press and the MIT Media Lab, Knowledge Futures was created to build sustainable tools and technologies for libraries, presses, museums, activist organisations, researchers, and others whose knowledge work seeks to serve collective understanding and the public. What began as a handful of grad students working on publishing tools grew to an organisation focused on addressing the systemic challenges faced by public-oriented groups beholden to infrastructure designed with misaligned incentives and unjust power dynamics. Knowledge Futures serves as a long-lived institution solely focused on building infrastructure to address the complex problem of ineffective research practices and wasteful traditions around how we share, produce, and evaluate knowledge.

Title of the Research Project

Designing Knowledge Cultures: a common-place of publishing for design cultures.

Goals and Objectives of the Research Project

The project's overarching objective was to research community-led knowledge production and scientific publication ecosystems. The proposed approach consists of shedding light on new interdisciplinary ways to publish scientific content, considering approaches in STEAM fields and hybrid disciplines such as design cultures. The stiff barrier between hard sciences and soft sciences is strictly reflected in scientific knowledge; therefore, this project aimed to prototype with the KF Team a new workflow and process that takes into account different scientific approaches in traditional

publications. Knowledge Futures is already familiar with prototyping new publishing workflows, as they have created the PubPub system. The methodological framework adopted by the project is heterogeneous. It is based on desk research, interviews, mapping and analysis of major design-focused and design-related journals and other platforms, and research of new initiatives for innovative scientific publication. The research will also rely on interviews with major mainstream magazines and journals that are not design-related but that are constantly reporting design case studies and methodology as models.

Specifically:

- a) Data research (existing data) at KF and MIT Press
- b) Qualitative methods (Interviews)
- c) Ethnographic observation of the workflow prototyping on the KF infrastructure (PubPub).

The research at KF contributed to opening up a discussion on new, alternative peer review models designed to make published information more useful and "recyclable" within the academic community, improving it throughout the publication's lifecycle. It acknowledges that open access involves more than just the accessibility of information or outcomes; rather, it represents a comprehensive methodology and guiding principle applicable at all stages of the publishing process, from manuscript submission to the sharing of final research results. Failure to adhere to these principles could lead to an incomplete implementation of open-access ideals. Given the ongoing need to expand open access principles across the entire editorial workflow, this discussion focuses on enhancing accessibility at a critical stage in the traditional publishing process: peer review. Despite its significance, the role and purpose of peer review are often contested, with concerns about bias, abuse, and reliability. The research seeks to explore how the results of the peer review process can be made accessible inclusively and equitably to increase transparency and build trust in the open-access publishing system. Peer review, as the cornerstone of academic publishing, is transforming a more collaborative and sustainable approach. By discussing innovative methodologies such as open and collaborative peer review, the research advocated for transparency in the peer review process. When reviewer identities are disclosed and review reports are made publicly available, accountability and trust within the academic community are strengthened, allowing for recognition of reviewers' contributions. This transparency can help mitigate biases and ensure that the evaluation process is fair and inclusive. Additionally, open-access journals that employ innovative approaches to peer review often have lower barriers to participation for both authors and reviewers. For authors, this means increased access to publication opportunities regardless of geographical affiliation or financial resources. For reviewers, it offers the opportunity to contribute to academic discourse and receive recognition for their expertise, independent of hierarchy. New peer review methodologies enable continuous feedback and review of

Fig. 2: Co.Re Model Process. By Author.

research outputs, ensuring not only the quality and relevance of the published research but also giving authors the chance to respond to feedback and improve their work over time, making published information more useful and recyclable within the academic community. The experimental initiative undertaken by the Commonplace Series, dedicated entirely to peer review innovation, will be conducted using the new Version 7 of the PubPub platform by Knowledge Futures. For the first time, this software will support multi-format article reviews. The experiment will focus on key elements such as:

- Transparency of reviewers, with their names published alongside the authors,
- Publication of reviews in infographic form, and
- A review form based on Blocks, offers reviewers freedom in how they comment and review the paper, especially in cases of multi-format articles.

3.1 Design and Implementation: Iterative Development of an Alternative Review Model

In this section, the research describes the three field experiences that have supported the experimentation of an alternative peer review model and how the direct observation and first-hand approach have methodologically and technically contributed to the iterative development of the model.

1. ***Design Journal: diid.disegno industriale industrial design (Editorial Infrastructure: Open Journal System)***

diid is an open access design journal that uses the Open Journal System platform to manage the publishing workflow. As an Associate Editor of the journal, the access and in-depth knowledge of the platform has greatly contributed to the technical and infrastructural understanding of the peer review process. The peer process consists of numerous internal steps (reviewer invitation, reviewer acceptance, reviewer completion of the form, reviewer thanking, reviewer sharing the review with authors) that only through direct experience within a journal is it possible to learn about and deepen.

2. ***Knowledge Futures Publishing Space: Commonplace (Editorial Infrastructure: Pub Pub)***

Commonplace is a publication of Knowledge Futures and a space to discuss the digital infrastructures, cultures, and actions needed to distribute, constellate, and amplify knowledge for the public good. This publication relies on the PubPub publishing infrastructure,

which is very different from the Open Journal System. Pub Pub is a repository managed directly by editorial groups that publish in the repository, based on a total editorial flexibility. With the support of the platform's technology team (KF), it is possible to build a tailored and unique editorial process according to the needs of the publishing group. The ability to be able to experiment on this platform has granted the experimentation a building approach outside the already fixed and compiled editorial schemes and standards typical of platforms such as Open Journal System or Editorial Manager.

3. **Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA) Conference**

The presentation of the model at the OASPA 2024 Conference did not contribute to the development of the model from a technical and infrastructural point of view, but from a point of view of gathering feedback from potential publishers and stakeholders potentially interested in experimenting with this alternative evaluation model. Conversations with interested actors allowed the research to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the model, while recognizing the need for experimentation on real-world scenarios to collect data and implementation results.

To summarise, these three experiences mixing both technical and ethnographical approach during the research project have been fundamental in contributing to the conception and development of the Co.Re model presents in the following paragraph.

4-Experimental Peer-Review model: The Collaborative Revision Model (Co.Re Model)

The experimentation model prototyped is an open review process based on dialogue between invited reviewers (**Fig. 2**). This format enables authors to focus directly on the reviewers' comments, eliminating the subjectivity of major/minor revision labels. Consequently, reviewers are encouraged to provide detailed feedback rather than high-level judgments, allowing authors to engage deeply with the content of the comments themselves. In this experimental approach, the conversation between reviewers will be published alongside the article. Authors are not required to submit a revised version of their paper, which incentivizes them to concentrate on their original submission. The hypothesis is that, over time, this approach will enhance the quality of published articles. Although it may result in fewer papers being published or require more time spent on data analysis, it addresses the issue of the overwhelming volume of published research.

This model aims to foster richer scholarly discourse and strengthen community relations between authors and reviewers. While there may be initial hesitation to make provocative statements in articles,

the primary goal is to stimulate a robust scientific discussion around the research. The open conversation format encourages collaboration during the review process, akin to the collaborative nature of writing a paper.

After 15 days of open dialogue between reviewers, authors will gain access to these discussions, receiving a comprehensive synthesis of comments and suggestions, especially with the assistance of the editorial manager. This collaborative interaction enhances understanding and effectively addresses differing opinions among reviewers. It also allows the review process to be completed within a month, speeding up the publication timeline.

Additionally, the proposed model seeks to improve community relations by offering researchers a platform to communicate about cutting-edge research and new ideas. By publishing reviewers' names alongside the authors', it provides reviewers with recognition and credit for their contributions. This transparency enhances the long-term impact of reviewers' voices, making their work transparent, citable, and easily accessible. It also encourages reviewers to frame their feedback constructively and sensitively, thereby reducing harsh or judgmental comments and making the review process more enjoyable.

Publishing the reviews also offers a valuable learning experience for readers, who can see what reviewers analyze in a research article. This insight helps authors anticipate the types of comments they might receive and teaches young researchers how to conduct peer reviews effectively. Just as readers are engaged by comments on social media posts, they will likely be intrigued by the public dialogue between authors and reviewers. We aim to recreate the same level of engagement seen on social platforms, where opinions, thoughts, and reflections spark vibrant discussions. On social media, there is often no formal reward for commenting; instead, the interaction and conversation with others make it more enjoyable. Similarly, we believe that this interactive review process can serve as a article of incentivization for reviewers. By fostering meaningful exchanges and collaborative dialogue, reviewers may find greater satisfaction and motivation in their contributions, enhancing the overall quality and impact of the peer review process.

4.1 Design and Implementation: Iterative Development of an Alternative Review Model

The purpose of this paragraph is to set the stage for a detailed, phase-by-phase comparison of the editorial workflow in both systems. This comparative analysis aims to highlight the key differences, advantages, and potential improvements that the CoRe Model offers over the conventional approach.

SUBMISSION PHASE

TRADITIONAL PEER REVIEW	CoRe MODEL
In the traditional system, authors submit an article text along with a set of images or multimedia data. The documents must be downloadable and readable for the reviewer to provide comments. Since the peer review form is usually standardized, the article must strictly follow a scientific structure.	In the CoRe model, authors can submit articles in various multimodal formats. The data must be downloadable and accessible for reviewers to provide comments. Unlike the traditional system, the peer review process in the CoRe model is flexible, allowing articles to have diverse structures and formats.

REVIEW PHASE

TRADITIONAL PEER REVIEW	CoRe MODEL
Two external reviewers are selected by the editorial team to review the article.	An indefinite number of external reviewers are selected by the editorial team to review the article.
Each reviewer conducts the review separately, filling out a standard form developed by the editorial team.	In the initial stage, each reviewer conducts the review separately by inserting comments on the text. In the second stage, all the reviewers involved can read and reply to each other's comments on the article, initiating an interaction.
Reviews are conducted anonymously and reviewers cannot interact.	Reviews are open and transparent among all the reviewers, sparking conversation and interaction during the review phase.
Authors are not involved at this stage.	During the third and final stage of the review process, the editorial team grants access to the authors of the article. Authors can read the reviewers' comments and ask questions where comments are unclear or discordant. Authors are allowed to see the reviewers' identities.
Reviewers are required to provide a final recommendation: accept, major/minor revision, resubmit for review, or decline.	No final recommendations are requested. The editorial team is in charge of elaborating a final recommendation based on reviewers' comments.

REQUEST REVISIONS

TRADITIONAL PEER REVIEW	CoRe MODEL
Once reviews are completed the editorial team shares the reviews and reviewers' final recommendations.	Authors have direct access to reviewers' comments. It is the decision of the editorial team to request a revised article.

PUBLICATION ON PLATFORM

TRADITIONAL PEER REVIEW	CoRe MODEL
The revised article is published, along with the authors' identity.	The article is published –based on the editorial decision to revise or not– along with the authors' and reviewers' identity.
The reviews are not disclosed to the public.	The reviewers' comments are elaborated by the editorial team and published along with the article.
Reviews' content is not published and therefore not citable.	Reviews are assigned a DOI and published along with the article and therefore citable.

.4.2-Benefits of the Co.Re Model: a User-centered Approach

This section delves into the specific benefits of the Co.Re (Collaborative Revision) Model for each editorial persona, with a particular focus on enhancing the "Conversation Experience". The benefits highlighted in this section underscore the model's capacity to streamline workflows and elevate the quality of academic discourse, contributing to a more dynamic and effective peer review ecosystem.

Author

- Understanding/synthesis of what the reviewers' comment/suggest (especially with the help of the editorial manager) when there are differing opinions from the reviewers. This also gives the author the ability to interact with reviewers so the author can get clarity around the reviewers' comments.
- Do not receive a decision from the reviewers about publication. The subjectivity of the reviewers' opinion of major/minor is removed and thus forces reviewers to make comments rather than their high-level decision. This allows the author to engage with the comments themselves rather than reckoning with the "major" or "minor" revision label.
- Strengthens community relations amongst authors and reviewers. Especially compared to writing a paper, which oftentimes is collaborative, this format would invite that collaboration during the review process (same as reviewer).
- Because the interaction is published alongside the article, it forces the author to really consider what they are sharing initially and be intentional and meaningful about it. In the long run, this increases the quality of published articles (even though it may mean less papers overall or more time spent analyzing the data it improves the quality of scholarship generally). There may be a hesitation to say something provocative but the aim is to initiate conversation around the research.

Reviewer

- Strengthens community relations amongst authors and reviewers. Especially compared to writing a paper, which oftentimes is collaborative, this format would invite that collaboration during the review process.
- Offers a way to communicate with other reviewers about cutting edge research and new ideas within their field. It's a way reviewers can share their opinions and have a sway in the newest research because their comments are available to everyone.
- It's a chance for them to receive credit for the work that they normally do without recognition.
- It enhances the long-term impact of the reviewer's voice because their work is transparent and citable because it's another platform for them to share their opinion (such that they can say something via the reviews rather than using Twitter or a blog – because its citable means that it's indexed and easier to recall and find).
- Because reviews are transparent, it enforces/educates the reviewers to frame their reviews constructively and sensitively. It also eliminates the power of reviewers to make them less harsh or judgemental, also making the experience more interactive.
- It reduces the amount of work/time for reviewer 2 because they could agree with what reviewer 1 said (a risk of this is that reviewers become reviewers of the review, but then again this is the thing we are designing for a conversation).
- An editor can also re-invite a reviewer because the editor knows that the reviewer has some interesting points to share about a particular topic. This could be a confidence boost for the reviewer.

Editorial Manager

- Can moderate and be the arbiter of knowledge when there is a dispute. Increase engagement with readership because posting the review conversation invites more conversation from readers.
- When a good conversation happens on a paper then leads to another publication, the editor can re-invite the reviewer again because the editor knows who reviewed the first paper.
- Cons: have to be extra careful about who's invited to review (probably cannot invite a graduate student to review a tenured prof or vice versa), and they have to do more work initially with submitted articles because they are the ones accepting or rejecting papers.

Reader

- Having the reviews published gives the reader a learning experience. Because they can see what a reviewer is asking for or critiquing in a research article, the reader can anticipate the types of questions they'll be asked when they submit a research article.
- Especially for young researchers, they can learn how to conduct peer review.
- The comments on a video or social media post are just as interesting as the OP. Readers are inherently interested in likes-to-comment ratios and invested in watching others' conversations.

This is an example of how an article using the Co.Re Model could look like on a Journal's platform.

Fig. 3: Image showing the potential platform visualization of an article that has undergone a peer review using the Co.Re model.

As shown in the image (Fig. 3), the journal article viewing window is divided into two: on one side you can read the contents of the article through a standard view, typical of current journals, including title, authors, keywords, abstract, metrics, citation and other features. The other half of the screen is dedicated to the description of the review process, where you can identify the following information:

- How many reviews have been completed;
- How many reviewers have been invited;
- Who are the invited reviewers, identified by academic affiliation and ORCID code.

From this image it is not possible to visualize the process of accessibility to the review contents, which represents a subsequent step of the research to be implemented once the experimentation is implemented on a real-world scenario. This part of the visualization is very important, as it provides the reader the opportunity to access the comments of the reviewers as well as the summary of their dialogue over the article. However, the research has not yet designed this step of the process.

5 Implications for Open Peer Review Practices in Design Journals

The research argues that Open Peer Review is an alternative model, that should not substitute the traditional one, but should coexist with it (Boston, 2024). The proposal of this alternative model represents an opportunity for the design community to spark reflections and thoughts around the current assessment models used in design. Allowing reviews at different editorial stages could foster a more transparent and qualitative scientific debate. The mission of Open Peer Review is to broaden the inputs of research as well as recognise all the information that are put in the process, such as reviewers' comments and dialogue with the authors.

Design journals are an appropriate context for this application, in both full or hybrid mode, or they could even design new peer review types based on the needs of the editorial group (research team, journal, conference...). The repercussions of this process are multifaceted and could impact many areas:

Social inclusion: the limits and challenges of doing science in any Global South area are widely understood, especially among Global South researchers. Open peer review could be taken into consideration as a model for overcoming these barriers in increasing the accessibility of diverse practices into the domain of knowledge, thanks to a structured dialogue between reviewers and authors.

Cultural and behavioural: disrupting hierarchies of evaluation and re-imagining evaluation schemes for scientific papers that belong to design cultures and are horizontally developed in transdisciplinary domains.

Understanding and awareness: create a community-driven publishing process that takes into account not only traditional scientific frameworks but also disruptive and innovative variables with an intersectional approach.

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Conclusion and Future Research Directions

This chapter concludes and discusses all aspects of the thesis, as well as review the research findings and remark on their applications. Additionally, the study observes potential future research areas which might elaborate and capitalise on the findings of this thesis. The first section of this chapter elaborates on the content of this research by briefly summarizing the five chapters of the thesis; the second section presents the outcome of the research in relation to the research questions; and the third section discusses the implications for knowledge, the potential beneficiaries and limitations of this research. The fourth part includes future research objectives and recommendations for other researchers.

Concluding Research Content

After the general introduction to the research and its methodological framework (Introduction), the thesis started by proposing an extensive literature review of the historical evolution of design publishing, in **Chapter 1**. Starting from the concept of Design as a “Third Culture” and its characteristic of a communicative language different from the humanities and mathematics (the “modeling”), the research sets up a historical excursus on the evolution of scientific communication of design, starting with architecture magazines from the early 1900s, and arriving at the scientific debate of the 1970s that forced design to adapt to the traditional scientific dissemination languages and structures of other disciplines. Although the exploration of the concept of Design as a Third Culture is not the core topic of the thesis, yet was needed for the purpose of this research to contextualise the peculiarity of the language used by design to be communicated and disseminated, before heading into the historical evolution of design publishing, and further to understand some of the challenges that design encounter in the current publishing system. The aim of this chapter is to contextualise and provide a historical overview of the recent “scientification” of design and how it adapted to the traditional structures of publication to gain scientific recognition. In addition, the chapter reports on the current needs of the scientific community and how design publishing can serve the community to address these demands in the current state of the art of the design discipline. The outcomes were validated through two interviews conducted with two editors in chief of prominent design journals: Louise Valentine of *The Design Journal*, and Carl Di Salvo, of *Design Issues*.

Following this historical and present contextualisation, **Chapter 2** delves into a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the current trends and patterns of design journals, based on the selection of 92 contemporary design journals indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). This mapping (called the *Design Research Journal Database*) provides a landscape view of design dissemination today, focusing on how these journals meet the demands of scientific rigour, accessibility, inclusivity and assessment. Through comparative analysis (2.1) and by setting the traditional standards of design publishing, the chapter identifies key innovation trajectories and trends in design publishing, highlighting how design journals are incorporating new models or platforms of knowledge dissemination. The results collected in this phase of the research identify significant regional differences in the adoption of inclusive and transparent practices. Journals based in Europe (40) and South America (25) show higher levels of inclusivity (international scientific boards, absence of APCs, inclusion of underrepresented voices from peripheral areas of the globe). Especially in South America, the absence of Article Processing Charges (APCs), stands out as the main feature of accessibility and

inclusivity of design knowledge production in the continent. Asian journals (12) offer higher user interactivity of publishing platforms compared to the European and Latin journals, however, accessibility and inclusivity are very low (due to recurrent APCs and low inclusion of underrepresented voices). Regarding transparency in the assessment processes, none of the Journals analysed show notable progress, besides a few case studies for the adoption of platforms recognising reviewers' contributions or journals publishing the peer review forms. The limited number of journals identified through the DOAJ database in North America, Africa and Australia, does not allow for a constructive and final reflection about publishing patterns in these continents. Following this vertical focus on design publishing, the research widens the lens of the scientific publishing industry.

Chapter 3 is critical to fully understanding the issues that affect the current publishing ecosystem, on the economic and political level. This step of the research highlights how despite advances in technology, scholarly publishing is still dominated by traditional publishing paradigms and rigidity in publication formats and processes. By mapping all the stakeholders involved in the publishing industry, the research analyses the journals included in the *Design Research Journal Database* of Chapter 2, showing a direct connection between Journals affiliated with University Presses, Journals using full Open Access (OA) models and high accessibility. At the same time, it shows that Journals affiliated with commercial publishers use Hybrid models, which involve standard APCs for publishing in OA. The economic implications and power imbalances among the actors of the ecosystem, negatively impact the source of knowledge production: researchers. They suffer the negative consequences of the system in two ways: a) low inclusiveness and accessibility due to APCs and economic profits of commercial publishers; b) lack of recognition of reviewers and their work, as well as loss of peer review content (as unpublished and non-transparent). The chapter concludes by acknowledging that the current scientific publishing ecosystem shapes and limits the way design knowledge is produced, validated and shared. Thus, it is crucial to shape the future design discourse around the adaptations of the publishing models in order to address the specific evolving needs and outputs of the design community. The outcomes of this chapter were validated through a thorough literature review of case studies, data and feedback collected during the workshops organized by the PRO.DES (Italian Design Society) focus group and the three interviews conducted with Laura Hanscom (Head of the Department of Scholarly Communications and Collections Strategy at the MIT Libraries), Nick Lindsay (Director of Journals and Open Access at MIT Press) and Paolo Manghi (Chief Technology Officer of OpenAIRE¹).

¹ OpenAIRE is a pan-European research information system, which provides services to find, store, link and analyse research output from all disciplines, <https://www.openaire.eu/>

In Chapter 4, the investigation explores how principles of distributed leadership and accessibility can be applied to transform the current traditional, often exclusionary, structures of knowledge production in design publishing of the publishing ecosystem presented in Chapter 2. Grounded in the theory of pluriversality, which advocates for multiple and diverse representations of disciplinarity and practice, this chapter delves into the need for more inclusive frameworks within scholarly communication. The research argues that when adapted to the design publishing ecosystem, distributed leadership can foster more inclusive and transparent systems of knowledge assessment, allowing for broader participation and reducing the exclusionary tendencies of traditional scientific publishing. Based on the experimentation in the 8th Forum Design as a Process of the Latin Network, it demonstrates the potential of rethinking publishing workflows to enhance inclusivity and fairness in knowledge dissemination. The chapter concludes by offering a Manifesto of Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing, developed through a community-led and collaborative approach of a Publishing Alliance. These principles, which have served as a foundation for the development of the CoRe model presented in the following chapter, provide actionable strategies for creating more inclusive and accessible systems of knowledge production and assessment in design.

The reasoning about inclusive and transparent assessment processes culminated in **Chapter 5**. This chapter introduces and presents an alternative peer review model, called the Co.Re (Collaborative Revision) Model, that has been experimented at the nonprofit organisation Knowledge Futures² during the research semester abroad carried out in the US. Based on a comprehensive and technical study of already existing platforms and models of peer review, an alternative assessment model is prototyped. It is significant to highlight that this analysis has been possible thanks to the direct observation of the editorial operations carried out as Associate Editor at the Design Journal: *diid.disegno industriale industrial design*³ on the Open Journal System (OJS) platform. The Co.Re Model is characterised by collaborative and interactive elements of conversation experience between the reviewers, the authors and the editorial manager, which enhances transparency, engagement, and constructive feedback. The purpose of developing this prototype was to test the results and principles collected up to that point of the research and try to test them in an applied publishing model, specifically in the peer review process. Although there was no time to test or simulate the model in an application reality such as a Journal or to collect the results from the experimentation on the *Commonplace*⁴ publishing space, the study aims to encourage the reader to elaborate on the concept of methodological shift in the publishing sector, starting from specific

² <https://www.knowledgefutures.org/>

³ DIID Journal, www.diid.it

⁴ <https://commonplace.knowledgefutures.org/pub/r1e8gaa6/release/1>

objectives of transformation: increasing transparency and increasing inclusivity. Finally, the research draws attention to the repercussions and impact that this new model might spark in design publishing: a) increase understanding and awareness to create a community-driven publishing process that takes into account not only traditional scientific frameworks but also pluriversal approaches and formats to design scientific research. b) enhance academic inclusion, highlighting the limits and challenges of doing science in any Global South area. c) foster a cultural and behavioural shift, to disrupt hierarchies of evaluation and re-imagine evaluation schemes for scientific papers that belong to design cultures and are horizontally developed in transdisciplinary domains.

Research Questions Vs. Research Output

The main research question of the study is:

How can scientific publishing practices be re-designed to enhance transparency and inclusivity in design knowledge production?

The outputs to the research sub-questions are processed on two distinct levels:

a) **Theoretical**: this level explains how the research objectives have been reached through the development of theoretical frameworks and principles analysis, based on desk research, desk research, and interviews.

b) **Empirical**: the research objectives have been met through application, testing, particularly hands-on experimentation or data gathering.

Hereby the analysis of each research sub-question.

RQ01 | What are the global trends and patterns of OA design journals and design knowledge production?

OB01 | Analyze and comprehend the current state of OA design journals worldwide, identifying key trends, thematic focuses, and geographical disparities.

Theoretical level: This objective is tackled through the literature review presented in Chapter 1. It was addressed by reviewing scientific sources from design studies and design literature that focus on the evolution of design as a scientific discipline. Starting from the concept of Design as a “Third Culture” and its characteristic of being multi/inter/cross/un-disciplinary (Brockman,1995; Flusser, 2003; Bertola & Maffei, 2009), the research sets the framework that provides comprehensive insights into how design publishing has evolved in the XX century. This initial investigation, based on a literature review and interviews with Editors in Chief of *The Design*

Journal and Design Issues, denotes the adaptation of design dissemination to the traditional scientific communication structures used by soft sciences and hard sciences. This partially answers the first sub-question, providing a general picture of the design publishing landscape nowadays.

Empirical level: This level provides detailed answers to the question, through data gathering and comparative analysis. The *Design Research Journal Database* provides a landscape view of design dissemination today, focusing on how these journals meet the demands of scientific rigour, accessibility, inclusivity and assessment. The results reveal a fair amount of disparity in how different regions implement inclusive and transparent practices in design publishing. In general, some regions (Europe and South America) show greater efforts towards inclusivity, with journals featuring more internationally diverse editorial boards, and not imposing APCs, publishing voices from underrepresented communities. In terms of interactivity of publishing forms and platforms, a few platforms stand out for offering interactive user experiences, although the majority use standard platforms (OJS and commercial publisher platforms) and include only heavy-text articles. With regard to transparency, progress remains limited overall. While some journals are starting to adopt platforms that acknowledge reviewers' contributions or publish peer-review forms, such practices are very rare. In regions with fewer journals, establishing clear publication models remains a challenge of knowledge in publishing.

RQ02 | What are the key aspects and features of the current publishing industry that impact the design of scientific dissemination?

OB02 | To identify and analyze the key stakeholders, economic and power dynamics within the publishing ecosystem and to examine how these dynamics impact design knowledge dissemination.

Theoretical Level: This question is answered by a mix of research activities, which are desk research, interviews, direct observation and case studies. Starting from the review of recent publications analysing the scientific publishing industry in general (Mastroianni, 2023; International Science Council, 2021; Nurse, 2021) and the analysis of case studies which problematise the current ecosystem (Class Action Lawsuit in 2024, The Harvard Libraries case in 2012), the research identifies several issues and challenges of the current publishing industry that impact design dissemination as evidenced by the case-scandal of the design journal *Design Studies* in 2023. By first mapping and describing all the stakeholders involved in the publishing industry (supported by literature review and direct observation working with the Partnership Team at Knowledge Futures in the US), the research shows a direct connection in the design ecosystem between Journals affiliated with University Presses, Journals using full Open Access (OA) models and high accessibility. The economic implications and power imbalances among the actors of the ecosystem, negatively impact the source of knowledge production: researchers. They suffer the negative consequences of the system because of low inclusiveness and accessibility and lack of recognition of

reviewers. Therefore, the case study of the journal *Design Studies*, as well as the data gathered on the empirical level, the research acknowledges that the current scientific publishing ecosystem shapes and limits the way design knowledge is produced, validated and shared currently.

Empirical Level: The activities implemented on this level are fundamental to elaborate the perspectives of the researchers in the design community and of the actors of the publishing ecosystem. Through the participation in the focus group PRO.DES of the Italian Design Society and the attendance at the OASPA Conference, the research was able to gather feedback from the stakeholders (researchers, editors, commercial publishers, etc.) While acknowledging that the research is based on a limited number of people interviewed and researchers who were asked for feedback, the data collected and processed are fairly homogeneous in recognising criticalities in the current publishing ecosystem that consequentially affect design publishing. In the interviews, experts were asked how they saw the elements of criticality how these elements could be embedded in a project and how they saw their impacts. During the discussions and the keynote speeches, it was evident that the current ecosystem is still affected by low levels of inclusivity and transparency, specifically with regard to Global North/Global South disparities and peer-review imbalances.

RQ03 | What role can distributed leadership play in enhancing pluriversity and fostering inclusivity and accessibility in design knowledge production?

OB03 | To examine how adopting distributed leadership models can transform design publishing practices to support a more diverse and equitable representation of knowledge in design community.

Theoretical Level: On the theoretical level, this objective is achieved through the support of a thorough literature review on the concepts of pluriversity and distributed leadership in the design publishing ecosystem (Bolden, 2011; Perry and Soreira, 2023; Leitão & Noel, 2022). Grounded in the theory of pluriversity, which advocates for multiple and diverse representations of disciplinarity and practice, the research delves into the issue of applying inclusive frameworks within design scholarly communication. Although not claiming to solve this global challenge, the results of this theoretical analysis, largely based on the results elaborated for **RQ02**, suggest that when adapted to the design publishing ecosystem, distributed leadership can foster more inclusive and transparent systems of knowledge assessment, allowing for broader participation and reducing the exclusionary tendencies of traditional scientific publishing. It showcased the different points of view, different arguments, and discussions, by tackling these different interpretations from a theoretical point of view through the literature.

Empirical Level: In this objective, the activities implemented on the empirical level are very significant to answer this research question. Based on the data collected during the three experimentations (the 8th Forum Design as a Process of the Latin Network; the focus group PRO.DES; and the Publishing Alliance initiative), the research demonstrates the potential of

rethinking publishing workflows to enhance inclusivity and fairness in knowledge dissemination. The development of a Manifesto of Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing as a result of a collective brainstorming with a community of editors of design journals, evidences the need for design publishing to be supported by inclusive and pluriversal practices.

RQ04 | What alternative assessment models in the current publishing system can be used to align assessment practices in design journals?

OB04 | To identify and analyse existing alternative assessment models that align with the values of inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration within the design publishing ecosystem.

Theoretical Level: Through an in-depth analysis of 11 existing platforms and alternative peer review models, I developed a prototype of an alternative assessment model, the CORE (Collaborative Revision) model. This model embodies the values and principles of transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration that I identified as essential for transformative assessment in design publishing. The theoretical aim of this prototype is to encourage a methodological shift in publishing practices, particularly focusing on transparency and inclusivity. Specifically, this model seeks to a) raise awareness and foster a publishing environment that is community-driven, b) enhance academic inclusion, by highlighting challenges in global scholarly publishing, particularly for those in the Global South; c) attempt to drive a cultural and behavioural shift to reimagine evaluation schemes. The research acknowledges that while the theoretical framework is thorough, it did not have the time to implement the CO.RE model fully or collect empirical data on its impact. Future research could apply this prototype in a real-world context to better understand its effects on the design publishing ecosystem.

Empirical Level: The research analysis was further supported by hands-on experience as an Associate Editor for the journal *DIID. disegno industriale industrial design*, where I observed editorial practices and processes directly. Working within the Open Journal System (OJS), I gained insights into how collaborative and interactive elements, which are key features of the CORE model, can enhance transparency and inclusivity in publishing. Additionally, the collaboration with Knowledge Futures on the PubPub publishing platform defined the understanding of editorial workflow innovation from a technical point of view of the user-study. Presenting this work at the 2024 OASPA Conference, the research has gathered valuable feedback through stakeholder interviews, which provided significant comments on CORE's concepts and directions for future research and implementation. This mixed approach of real-world practice and platform experimentation has laid the foundation for shaping Co.Re as a model aligned with the values of transparency and inclusivity in design publishing.

Fig. 1: Diagram summarizing the methodological approach to address the research questions. By Author.

Contribution to Knowledge

Design scientific publishing should comply with the epistemological changes in knowledge production and cognition due to the digital revolution (Lupo, 2022) and the acknowledged necessity to increase inclusivity and transparency in publishing models. In calling on the design community for responsible systemic and cultural change in the publishing ecosystem, this research discusses the more relevant challenges within the process of publication that can enable the emergent diversities of knowledge in design production. The motivation of this research was to shed light and raise awareness among the design scholar community in regard to the impact that the current structures of scientific publishing have on design dissemination of scientific results and their scientific recognition. The contribution to knowledge can be concluded in three main facets:

1. Mapping and Analysis of OA Design Journals: The Design Research Journal Database (DRJD)

This research makes a significant contribution through the collection of a comprehensive database of 92 OA design journals indexed in DOAJ, offering an in-depth mapping and comparative analysis of design publishing practices across multiple regions. This database serves as a source for scholars, especially the early-career ones, providing a detailed list of design journals in Europe, America, Asia, Africa and Australia. By categorizing journals based on features such as open access policies, interdisciplinary scope, and inclusivity publishing patterns, the database aims to establish a foundation for future studies and comparative analyses in scholarly publishing.

2. Conceptual advancements in the design publishing ecosystem

By providing theoretical concepts on distributed leadership, pluriversality, inclusivity and transparency, the research aims at laying the foundations for a change in traditional publishing models in design, to be applied in editorial evaluation frameworks and peer review processes. The research proposes a shift towards more globally inclusive research practices that acknowledge diverse perspectives and epistemologies, aligning with the pluriversal approach.

3. Impact on inclusivity and transparency in Design Knowledge Assessment

The research encourages a shift in design knowledge assessment by tackling issues of underrepresentation, transparency and community-led approaches. The background investigation supporting the prototyping of the Co.Re model, emphasizes collaborative elements and interactive dialogues in the peer review process, as significant tools to increase accessibility, transparency, recognition and inclusivity; the model sets a precedent for implementing more inclusive, transparent, and adaptable review processes, potentially influencing publishing practices beyond design.

Beneficiaries:

The outcome of this research could be useful for four groups of beneficiaries in the design scientific community:

Scholars and researchers in Design Community

The Design Research Journal Database (DRJD) offers a significant tool for researchers seeking to publish or research in design. By providing detailed information on each of the journals selected, researchers are enabled to make more informed decisions on where to submit their research results. In addition, the analysis of alternative assessment models and the development of the Co.Re model contribute to an evolving discourse around peer review, transparency and inclusivity in scholarly publishing, offering alternative research approaches that could improve the quality and accessibility of their work.

Editorial teams and publishers of Design Journals

Editorial teams and publishers of Design Journals are direct beneficiaries of this research, which provides theoretical and technical suggestions on how to enhance editorial workflows toward more inclusive, transparent and collaborative approaches.

Global South researchers and generally underrepresented voices

The discussion around the current barriers in the publishing industry (APCs, editorial diversity, acceptance rate of global south researchers) benefits the researchers of peripheral regions of the design community. The Manifesto of Principles for Enhancing Equity and Inclusivity in Design Publishing aims to foster a more equitable platform for voices that have traditionally been marginalized in academic publishing, supporting a more pluriversal approach to design knowledge production.

Learned societies, commercial publishers and policymakers

Policymakers within academic and governmental institutions can benefit from the findings of this research, especially concerning the criticalities highlighted in the publishing ecosystem that affect researchers and university-led journals. The Co.Re Model represents an editorial proposal that can offer a potential framework to transform publishing policies and practices to support more transparent, inclusive publication of research results among the scientific community for university-led journals and commercial publishers.

Implications and Considerations of the Research Limitations

Even though this research has achieved substantial outcomes aligned with the objectives proposed by the research, limitations and critical considerations remain, especially concerning the reach and the actionability of its impact. First, the reach and engagement of this research and the feedback collected required to criticise and problematise the current publishing practices have been hindered by a limited sample of researchers and stakeholders actively involved.

While The Design Research Journal Database (DRJD) offers a valuable reference for researchers, its accessibility and usability could be enhanced by being published on a digital and open-access platform, outside the scientific traditional format of this doctoral thesis. This action would align with the research's ethical commitment to accessibility to design knowledge, allowing a broader audience from the design community to effectively benefit from the insights of this output. It is important to recognise that the adopted methodology had certain limitations, particularly related to its reliance on qualitative and manually-driven analysis. In contrast to the limitations faced by large-scale quantitative bibliometric

analyses (Perry & Pereira, 2023), the primary limitation of this research lies in its manual and qualitative nature. While qualitative methods provide in-depth insights, the main challenge arises from the subjective interpretation of the data and the time-intensive nature of manual analysis. Many journals, especially those not indexed in Scopus or Clarivate, lack sufficient scoring or data. Also, it should be considered that not all design-relevant journals are indexed in DOAJ. Although DOAJ is an inclusive and widely used platform, there are other, lesser-known but equally important databases that may contain journals not found in DOAJ.

Due to time constraints, the potential impact of the Co.Re model has not been assessed and validated in real-world scenarios yet, strongly limiting the analysis of the impact of the model and potential adoption among design journals. Although the implications identified from the potential application of this collaborative model, such as achieving a behavioural shift and raising awareness about the necessity to increase inclusive approaches, have been mentioned as potential, the research is fully aware that these goals require further practical tools and case studies to achieve them across diverse contexts.

Acknowledging these limitations is relevant to ensure that the outputs of this research remain coherent with the ethical principles of transparency and inclusivity underlying the investigation. This assessment serves as a first step toward future research directions.

Future Research Directions

Future research is needed to develop some areas that are not discussed in this doctoral research. These areas could be identified as follows.

- i. **The implications of artificial intelligence in scientific publishing:** although briefly mentioned during the interview with Nick Lindsay of MIT Press, the transformative role of AI in academic publishing requires deeper exploration. As outlined in Chapter 5, AI has transitioned from a speculative concept to an actively implemented tool, influencing various editorial processes, from pre-peer review quality checks to data-driven trend analysis. While AI holds the potential to enhance efficiency and address challenges such as reviewer scarcity, concerns persist regarding transparency, accountability, and the integrity of AI-generated content. The publishing ecosystem recognizes both the opportunities and risks of AI integration but continues to navigate its ethical and operational complexities
- ii. **Increase design community engagement in the research phase:** building on the efforts carried out by this research, a future investigation should rely on broader feedback from researchers to understand which represents the best way to

serve the design community (Valentine & Mehmeti, 2022). An increased engagement will contribute to how publishing initiatives can best meet the evolving needs of the design community, ensuring the outputs are relevant and impactful.

- iii. **Application of the CO.RE Model in real-world scenarios:** finally, future research directions should involve experimenting the Co.Re Model within active design journals or platforms. By analysing data from the real application or simulation of the model, it will be possible to effectively assess the model's capability to foster collaboration, dialogue, inclusivity, transparency and recognition. This experimentation could be scalable and improved to be used as an alternative peer review model in design publishing practices. These research directions could advance the future strategies of design publishing practices, aligning it more closely with the values of transparency and inclusivity.

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Appendix

/ 1

Interviewee Profile Sheets

01.

Louise Valentine, Editor in Chief of The Design Journal

Professor Valentine is a writer, academic and practitioner with over 25 years of experience researching change with design for business innovation. Louise has committed her career to developing Global Design Research Culture, and her research focuses on communicating design, its processes, and methods for enabling growth through innovation in business. Professor Valentine is Editor-in-Chief of *The Design Journal*, Taylor and Francis' flagship design journal, and Emeritus President of the Biennale International Design Research Conference, the European Academy of Design, having served as President and Vice Present between 2013–2023.

02.

Carl DiSalvo, Co-Editor of Design Issues Journal

Professor DiSalvo is Associate Professor in the College of Computing at the Georgia Institute of Technology. He teaches design, theory, and methods courses and advises students in the Human-Centered Computing program and the Digital Media program. He draws upon design and ethnographic methods in my research, and much of his work is participatory and community-based. His background in the arts and humanities shapes his teaching, advising, and research. He is also co-editor of the MIT Press journal *Design Issues*.

03.

Laura Hanscom, Head of Scholarly Communications and Collections Strategy at MIT Library

Laura Hanscom was named the department head for Scholarly Communications and Collections Strategy in the MIT Libraries in April 2021 and is the leader of their Negotiations Team. Prior to that, she was their Scholarly Communications and Licensing Librarian from 2016. She started her library career in interlibrary loan at the London School of Economics and was Digital Repository Administrator at City University London Library. Prior to coming to MIT, she served as Scholarly Communications Librarian at Salisbury University in Maryland, USA.

04.

Nick Lindsay, Director of Journals and OA at The MIT Press, Inc.

Nick Lindsay has over two decades of experience in the publishing industry, primarily at The MIT Press, where roles have included Director of Journals and Open Access, Journals Director, and Journals Manager since March 2008. Previous positions include Journals Marketing & Circulation Manager at University of California Press and Telecom Research Analyst at ESRI. Engagements in professional organizations include serving as a Publications Committee Member for the Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography, a Board Member of the Open Access Network, and an Advisory Council Member for RedLink Network.

05.

Rebecca McLeod, Managing Director at Harvard Data Science Review

Rebecca comes to HDSR with decades of experience in scholarly publishing, having worked in marketing, editorial development, operations, and relationship management roles for both nonprofit and commercial organizations. A substantial part of her career was spent at The MIT Press where she worked in various positions supporting the Journals program including 8 years as the Journals Director where she was responsible for overseeing all functions of the MIT Press Journals division including the publication, marketing and sales of 35+ scholarly journals.

06.

Prachee Avasthi, Co-founder & CSO at Arcadia Science

Professor of Anatomy and Cell Biology and Science Communicator at Dartmouth College and a co-founder and incoming CSO at Arcadia Science in Berkeley, California. Avasthi is enthusiastic about reforming scientific research culture, and helping early career researchers set up their own laboratories. She launched New PI Slack, an online space for over a thousand new Principal investigators to share notes and ideas. Avasthi supports preprints and the reform of scientific publishing and is on the Board of Directors of eLife and ASAPbio. In her laboratory, she leads a preprint journal club.

07.

Sarah Kember, Professor of New Technologies of Communication at Goldsmiths University of London and Director of *Goldsmiths Press*

Director of Goldsmiths Press and her research focuses on the future of publishing, digital media, smart media, questions of mediation and feminist science and technology studies. She has investigated the possibilities of life after new media (studies), and has engaged in debates on artificial life and other aspects of the convergence between biology and computer science. She also works on imaging technologies and the relationship between photography and the digital.

Appendix

/ 2

**The Design
Research
Journal
Database**

00.

TEMPLATE
Criteria Methodology Description

Affiliation:	Publisher (University Press, Association, University Department, etc.)
Funding date:	From when the Journal is active.
Language:	What languages are published/accepted for publication.
Scope and relevance:	Assess whether the journal's scope aligns with the field of design and its sub-disciplines and determine the relevance of the journal's content to current trends and issues in design.
Design and layout:	Assess the visual design, readability, and overall presentation of the journal and the digital presence (functionality of the journal's website and digital archives).
Publication frequency:	Look at how often the journal is published (monthly, quarterly, etc.).
Accessibility:	Check if the journal is open access or subscription-based and its digital accessibility to the global design community (open access or not).
Journal impact and reputation:	Consider the journal's reputation within the design community and academia.
Impact score:	Measure the journal's impact factor and other citation metrics.
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Assess the research quality and significance of the published research. Consider the citation rates and the influence of individual articles on the field.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	Based on 1. Geographic diversity (examine the diversity of the authorship in terms of geographic representation); 2. Topic diversity (assess the range of topics covered by the journal within the design discipline) 3. Inclusivity (evaluate the journal's efforts to include diverse perspectives and underrepresented voices in design).
Editorial composition:	Evaluate the expertise and diversity of the editorial board members.
Review process:	Evaluate how the review process is conducted.
Ethical standards:	Check for adherence to ethical guidelines in publishing, such as COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) standards.
Innovative practices and experimentation:	If it incorporates interactive articles and multimedia content or publishes experimental methodologies and design practices.
Networking activities:	Organizes conferences/workshops and sponsors major design conferences; does it facilitates collaborations between academia and industry.
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Publishes significant interdisciplinary research integrating design with fields like engineering, social sciences, and technology.
Interdisciplinary impact:	Articles frequently cited in other scientific disciplines.

Europe

01.	Además de Revista Online de Artes Decorativas y Diseño
Affiliation	Asociación de Amigos del Museo Nacional de Artes Decorativas, Spain
Funding date	2015
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Industrial design, Visual design
Design and layout:	Easy to access and navigate; archives fully digital and accessible. OJS platform of submission
Publication frequency:	One issue per year
Accessibility:	Open access, no publication fees (APC)
Journal impact and reputation:	Low indexing (EBSCO and Latin databases). Only spanish language, low international impact. Titles not translated, but abstracts also in english.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Low: average of 10 to 20 visits per month per article from 2021 to 2023.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Percentage of International authors very low (1-2%). 2. Topics very traditional. 3. Low level of inclusion of underrepresented researchers and projects
Editorial composition:	Scientific Board international.
Review process:	Double Blind peer review. List of reviewers published.
Ethical standards:	Yes, COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Only visual arts, performative arts and humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	None

02.	Architecture Papers of the Faculty of Architecture and Design STU ALFA
Affiliation	Slovak University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture and Design , Slovakia
Funding date	1996
Language:	English and Slovak
Scope and relevance:	Interior design, social design
Design and layout:	Attractive website, easy to navigate. Submission managed through Editorial Manager
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access, digital accessibility. No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Very wide international Indexing (NO Scopus or WOS) Asian Science Citation index (ASCI), Baidu Scholar, CNKI Scholar (China National Knowledge Infrastructure) CNPIEC – cnpLINKer,Crossref,Dimensions, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ),EBSCO, ERIH PLUS (European Reference Index for the Humanities and Social Sciences), Google Scholar, J-Gate, JournalsPedia, KESLI-NDSL (Korean National Discovery for Science Leaders), MyScienceWork, Naver Academic, Naviga (Softweco), Primo Central (ExLibris), ReadCube, Sciendo, SCILIT,Scite
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Good impact on central european region and global south countries. Citation rates not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High representation of global south countries. 2. Very wide range of topics at the intersection between architecture and design. 3. Good representation of voices and case studies from underrepresented regions of Global South
Editorial composition:	International, but only European origins
Review process:	Single-blind review. The journal uses ReviewerCredits certification
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Elsevier
Innovative practices and experimentation:	The journal uses ReviewerCredits certification Publication of a Section dedicated to PhD summaries
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

03.	Arte, Diseño e Ingeniería ArDIn
Affiliation	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid , Spain Ingeniería Mecánica, Química y Diseño Industrial. ETSIDI. UPM
Funding date	2012
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Industrial design
Design and layout:	OJS system, easy to navigate
Publication frequency:	One issue per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing on major databases, not SCOPUS but WOS and ErihPlus and Latin indexes. Fair Impact factor on WOS (0,63)
Impact score:	WOS: 0,63 (fair)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Good citations in 2023 (double rate in comparison to 2022)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Only spanish speaking countries; mainly Spain. 2. High interdisciplinarity; 3. Very low level of inclusivity
Editorial composition:	23% international
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes, COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural heritage, gender studies, informatics
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

04.

Artifact_ Journal of Design Practice

Affiliation	Publisher: Intellect , United Kingdom. Other organisation: The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts; Design School Kolding
Funding date	2007
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Product design and visual communication, user experience, interface, and service design as well as design management and organization
Design and layout:	The Journal platform is managed within the Publisher's website. Therefore it is not easy to distinguish which features belong to the Journal and which are the "buttons" concerning the Publisher. Moreover, clicking on "Journal Information" there is a systematic error on the website. However, archives are fully accessible. Metrics are very transparent.
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good indexing: OPEN Access, SCOPUS and SCIMAGO
Impact score:	H index: 2
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citescore medium: 0,5 Metrics of each article are published
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Highly international (mainly Western and European affiliations). 2. Very wide range of design topics. 3. Very low level of inclusivity (voices and case studies) of underrepresented regions
Editorial composition:	Not published
Review process:	Double-blind peer review, but not explained.
Ethical standards:	Not published.
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Collaboration with the Nordic Design Research Society (NORDES); publication of Special Issues and Conference proceedings
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Computer Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Arts and Humanities: #214/667 Computer Science: #99/106

05.	CoDesign International Journal of CoCreation in Design and the Arts
Affiliation	Taylor and Francis, Affiliated with the Design Society
Funding date	2005
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Collaborative design, including collaborative design theory, methods, tools, innovations, practical experience and handling design issues
Design and layout:	Publisher's platform. Easy to navigate. Archives accessible
Publication frequency:	4 issues per year
Accessibility:	CoDesign is a hybrid open access journal. If you choose to publish open access in this journal you may be asked to pay an Article Publishing Charge (APC) – EUR 3170
Journal impact and reputation:	Highly relevant journal for the design community worldwide
Impact score:	43K annual downloads/views 2.0 (2023) Impact Factor
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 6,1
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographical diversity. 2. Very wide coverage of design topics. 3. Several case studies from the Global South. Considering APCs representation from the Global South is low.
Editorial composition:	Fully international, mainly from Global North
Review process:	Double-blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Taylor and Francis Ethical Guidelines
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Members of the following societies are eligible for discounted personal print subscription to CoDesign: The Design Society / The Design Research Society / Computers in Art and Design Education (CADE)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Engineering; Computer Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Arts and Humanities: #5/667 Engineering: #12/189 Computer Science: #19/106

06.

Convergências - Revista de Investigação e Ensino das Artes

Affiliation	Politécnico de Castelo Branco , Portugal Escola Superior de Artes Aplicadas, Portugal
Funding date	2008
Language:	English, Spanish, Portuguese
Scope and relevance:	All fields of design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. English, Spanish, Portuguese language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APCs
Journal impact and reputation:	Low Impact Factor on international design community. Good indexing: Open Access Indexing: SCIELO, DOAJ, SHERPAROMEQ, ERIHPLUS, Google Scholar, Dimensions, BASE. Indexed also in SCOPUS. Italian indexing - ANVUR. Broad Latin Indexing: Qualis Capes, MIAR, LatinIndex, CIRC, REDIB, LIVRE
Impact score:	Scimago H Index: 1
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 0.0
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity, especially from Ukraine. 2. Limited scope of design discipline, limited to visual arts. 3. Good representation of diverse perspectives of design discipline.
Editorial composition:	66% international
Review process:	Double-blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes, COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Arts and Humanities: #164/173

07.	DATE Design and Technology Education_ An International Journal
Affiliation	The Design and Technology Association, United Kingdom Liverpool John Moores University
Funding date	1997
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Theories and practices of Design and Technology Education
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Very easy to navigate. Archives digitally accessible starting from 2005 (Vol.10)
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APCs
Journal impact and reputation:	Not available, indexing not published. The Journal has been published three times a year since 1997, providing a wide range of leading research into Design and Technology to D&T Association members to reflect the changing face of modern design and technology education. Main impact: the Association network.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very international authorship. 2. Design topics only intersecting with educational field. 3. Fair representation of researchers from underrepresented countries.
Editorial composition:	20% international - only Global north affiliations
Review process:	Not explicit
Ethical standards:	Not explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Close collaboration with the activities of the Association: conferences, events and meetings
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Pedagogy; Technology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

08.

Demiurge_ Ideas, Technologies, Perspectives of Design

Affiliation	Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Ukraine
Funding date	2018
Language:	English and Ukraine
Scope and relevance:	Design of the environment; visual communication design; design of clothes, accessories, image; art studies
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, easy to navigate. English and Ukrainian version. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APCs
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact is national, considering prevalence of articles are published in national language. Indexing not available
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Prevalence of articles are published in national language; titles and abstracts in english (on the pdf)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity very low. 2. Wide design topics covered, especially intersecting arts and cultural heritage. 3. Low inclusivity levels.
Editorial composition:	25% international (2 out of 8)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE bu ethics of publication published
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Arts; Cultural Heritage
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

09.	DEPARCH Journal of Design Planning and Aesthetics Research
Affiliation	Selçuk University , Türkiye
Funding date	2022
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Industrial design, spatial design, virtual reality, design technology
Design and layout:	ULAKBİM Journal Systems, easy to navigate. English Language, Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APCs
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access indexes: EBSCO and DOAJ; impact and reputation not assessable; young journal
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not Available. Articles in English language.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity. 2. Low coverage of design topics. 3. Low inclusivity, prevalence of national case studies. But inclusion of young researchers.
Editorial composition:	100% international, from both Global North and Global South.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA)
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture, Urban Studies, Cultural Heritage
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>10.</h1>	<h2>Design and Culture</h2>
Affiliation	Taylor and Francis
Funding date	2009
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design Cultures
Design and layout:	Publisher's layout. Easy to navigate. English. Archives accessible (Open access articles). The platform shows "Related research" along each article.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Hybrid; not full open access. If authors choose to publish open access in this journal you may be asked to pay an Article Publishing Charge (APC): 3000 EUR
Journal impact and reputation:	Very relevant journal for the Design Community, especially in the Western scholar debate. Main scholar indexing: Scopus, WOS
Impact score:	Usage: 68K annual downloads/views 0.7 (2023) Impact Factor 1.4 (2023) 5 year IF
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	1.8 (2023) CiteScore (Scopus)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity. 2. Very broad range of topics from design cultures. 3. Fair representation of researchers from underrepresented areas of the Global South. Initiative: Emerging Scholars Workshop for young researchers.
Editorial composition:	88% international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Taylor & Francis/Routledge Journal Editor Code of Conduct
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Emerging Scholars Workshop Images can be displayed full size
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural Studies Visual Arts and Performing Arts
Interdisciplinary impact:	Cultural Studies: #197/1304 Visual Arts and Performing Arts: #38/667

11.	Design Science
Affiliation	Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom Other organisation: The Design Society
Funding date	2015
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Art history; interior design furniture; interior decoration
Design and layout:	Cambridge University Press website. English language. Easy to navigate. Articles can be read on the website (not only pdf download)
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC: 3450 USD; 2320 GBP
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact on design community: Web of Science; EBSCOhost; Biotechnology Source; STM Source; Scopus; ProQuest
Impact score:	Scimago: SJR 2023 - 0.662 H-INDEXT: 25
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus: Citescore 2023 - 4,8 (513 citations/107 documents); mid-high impact
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very high geographic diversity. 2. Wide range of topics related to design discipline. 3. Mid-low inclusivity, low representation of Global South case studies or researchers.
Editorial composition:	86% International (mainly western countries from developed regions)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Thematic collections; Design Practice Briefs (Case studies authors from Global South)
Networking activities:	Collaborates with The Design Society
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities Mathematics Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS_ Arts and Humanities: #11/667 Mathematics: #77/324 Engineering: #79/307

12.	designs
Affiliation	MDPI (Publisher), Switzerland
Funding date	2017
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Product design; Industrial design; Design theory, methodology and management; Open source design; Design innovation
Design and layout:	MDPI Platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Bimonthly
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC - 1600 CHF
Journal impact and reputation:	The journal has a very high impact scientific impact, especially for Engineering and Mechanical fields. According to SCOPUS the Citescore is 3,9. The journal is indexed in the most relevant scientific databases: BibCnrs, CNKI, CNPIEC, Dimensions, DOAJ, EBSCO, Scopus, Engineering Village, Ei Compendex, Gale, Inspec, J-Gate, OpenAIRE, OSTI (U.S. Department of Energy), ProQuest, SCIMAGO Best Travel Award 2024.
Impact score:	H-INDEX: 23
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	High citescore: 3.9
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity. 2. Very low range of design topics, mainly intersected with engineering. 3. Represents researchers and authors from all over the world.
Editorial composition:	International, divided per Sub-field of Engineering discipline. No representative of Design Discipline.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Special Issue
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	None
Interdisciplinary impact:	None

13.	DISCERN - International Journal of Design for Social Change, Sustainable Innovation and Entrepreneurship
Affiliation	Art + Design: elearning lab – design for social change, Cyprus University of Technolog , Cyprus
Funding date	2020
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Product design, Social Design, Design innovation
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	The Good Open Access Indexing: DOAJ, ROAD, ERIHPlus, OpenAire , NO SCOPUS or WOS
Impact score:	Not Impact Factor available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available, neither statistics of visualization or download per paper
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authorship very diverse and international. 2. Very wide representation of design topics. 3. High geographical inclusivity of researchers from Global South
Editorial composition:	International, representing countries from Global North and 5 countries from Global South
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Special Issue
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available.

14.	Eme_ Experimental Illustration, Art & Design
Affiliation	Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain
Funding date	2011
Language:	Spanish (prevalence) and English
Scope and relevance:	Graphic Design; Visual Design; Design history; Typography
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible. Only Spanish language
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access, No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	The Open Access indexing and Latin region indexing: DOAJ, Google Scholar, ERIHPlus, Sherpa Romeo; Latindex, REDIB, MIAR; NO Scopus or WOS
Impact score:	Not available. Most of the articles are in Spanish language, limiting impact.
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available. Statistics of downloads available. Diversification of articles (research articles, reportages, interviews)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low, mainly researchers from latin area. 2. Wide range of design topics at the intersection with fine arts. 3. Inclusion of researchers from South American regions
Editorial composition:	63% from Spain; the international members of the Board are from Portugal, Mexico, Colombia, France
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review; Reviewers list published
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Art
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available.

15.	Grafica_ Documents de Disseny Gràfic
Affiliation	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Funding date	2013
Language:	English, Spanish, Catalan
Scope and relevance:	Graphic Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible. Platform available in all three languages
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, No APC (Micro-sponsorship: With the objective of obtaining the necessary financing to cover the costs of the journal's editing processes, different modalities of sponsorship and crowdfunding are deployed.)
Journal impact and reputation:	The grafica is an international journal of Design and Communication published in Open Access by the UAB in collaboration with the Department of Advertising, Public Relations and Audiovisual Communication of the UAB. Indexed in: DOAJ Latindex Dialnet; REBIUN; Dulcinea; CIRC; Google Scholar. Also SCOPUS. High impact on design community in Europe and latin areas
Impact score:	H-index: 3
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citescore: 0,7 Most of the articles is in Spanish or Portuguese language. Impact limited
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors mainly from the Latin/Spanish region. 2. The diversity of topics within design discipline is very high. 3. Inclusivity is good, many case studies from the global south region
Editorial composition:	43% international – only from latin American countries. The journal has a Gender Policy
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Gender Policy
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Original sections: Opinion, Expertia, Research, Essays, Description
Networking activities:	SYMPOSIUM GRAFICA
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Computer Graphics and Computer-Aided Design
Interdisciplinary impact:	Articles frequently cited in other scientific disciplines Computer Graphics and Computer-Aided Design: #91/106

16.	i-com Journal of Interactive Media
Affiliation	DE GRUYTER German Association for Informatics
Funding date	2001
Language:	English from 2015; 2001–2015 German
Scope and relevance:	Media Design; Human–Computer interaction; User– Centered Design Experience
Design and layout:	De Gruyter platform. Easy to navigate; archive fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; YES APC (750€)
Journal impact and reputation:	The Journal is indexes in SCOPUS and Scimago. Main audience from Western Europe (prevalence Germany)
Impact score:	SCOPUS 2023 CiteScore: 3.8 Scimago H-Index: 12
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scimago statistic: 143 document citation in 2023; 2023 index: 0.335
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Between 2021 and 2023 the international collaboration has decreased from 21% to 5%; prevalence of European researchers. 2-Fair range of topics covered in design, mainly at the intersection between computer science and design. 3-Low inclusivity of global south case studies and researchers. Inclusion of female authors about 40%
Editorial composition:	Fully German
Review process:	Single-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Special Issues
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Computer science; Computers Network and Communications; Psychology; Business and Management
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCIMAGO: Business and Management: Q3 (Q1 is the highest) Communication: Q3 Social Psychology: Q4 Computer Science: Q4

<h1>17.</h1>	i+Diseño_ Revista Científico-Académica Internacional de Innovación, Investigación y Desarrollo en Diseño
Affiliation	Universidad de Málaga, Spain
Funding date	2009
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Industrial, product, graphic, strategic, methodological, environmental, spaces and services
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. Spanish and English versions of the website. Archive full accessible
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Especially centered in the Ibero-Italo-American exchange like global alternative to an Anglo-Saxon line, already existing and very consolidated. It is a question of retaking the Spanish-Italian-Portuguese focus, which transcends the Ibero-American consideration. Indexing: Open Access and Latin indexing (DOAJ, Latindex, Dialnet)
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available, however Download statistics displayed per each article
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. International coverage, mainly Latin and Mediterranean countries. 2. Very wide spectrum of design topics. 3. High level of case studies from underrepresented regions.
Editorial composition:	Very international, with 95% of international members from Italy and South American countries. 2 members from the US
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review; list of reviewers publishes
Ethical standards:	No COPE; but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

18.	IDA_ International Design and Art Journal
Affiliation	Nilay ÖZSAVAŞ ULUÇAY, Professor at Muğla Sıtkı Koçman Üniversitesi, Türkiye
Funding date	2019
Language:	English and Turkish (mainly English)
Scope and relevance:	Interdisciplinary articles on design and art
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. English and Turkish versions. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	EBSCO, Copernicus International, TR Dizin, DOAJ, ERIH Plus, MIAR, BASE, Advanced Science Index (ASI), Directory of Research Journals Indexing (DRJI), ASOS Index, Cite Factor. No SCOPUS or WOS. Impact of the journal not assessable: mainly national audience
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. International coverage very low. mainly Turkish authors. 2. Main topics in product and industrial design. 3-several case studies from underrepresented countries of the Middle-eastern region
Editorial composition:	60% International; both from Global North and Global South Countries.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture, Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

19.	InMaterial
Affiliation	Bau, Centro Universitario de Diseño, Spain
Funding date	2016
Language:	Spanish, Catalan, English
Scope and relevance:	Design cultures
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good level of indexing in international and latin indexes: SCOPUS, CARHUS PLUS+ (accepted in 2023, pending publication on the web), ANVUR (Italian Database),CIRC, DIALNET, DOAJ, DULCINEA, EBSCO Art and Architecture Source, ERIHPlus, LATINDEX, MIAR, REDIB, SHERPA/ROMEO. Good impact on Latin and Mediterranean region
Impact score:	Low impact factors: Scimago: Q3 – 0,107
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citescore low: 0,4 in 2023
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Prevalence of authors from latin region. 2. Wide range of topics within design cultures. 3. High number of case studies from underrepresented regions of the Global South
Editorial composition:	Editorial Board: 30% international; Scientific Committee: 50% international (mainly latin countries and Europe)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Arts
Interdisciplinary impact:	Low: Arts and Humanities field (#518/667)

20.

International Journal of Food Design

Affiliation	Intellect, United Kingdom
Funding date	2016
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Food design research and practice
Design and layout:	Publisher's platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good level of indexing: ANVUR, British Humanities Index (BHI), China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), EBSCO, Food Science Technology Abstracts (FSTA), Norwegian Publication Indicator (NPI), Scopus, Ulrich's Periodicals Directory
Impact score:	Scimago H-INDEX: 11
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 3,7
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity very high. 2. Good coverage of design topics especially for packaging and health design 3. Medium level of case studies from Global South
Editorial composition:	92% international (only Global North)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Agricultural and Biological Sciences Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Agricultural and Biological Sciences: #16/667 Arts and Humanities: #172/389

21.

International Journal of Games and Social Impact IJGSI

Affiliation	Edições Universitárias Lusófonas , Portugal
Funding date	2023
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Game Design
Design and layout:	OJS platform; easy to navigate, English language. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	The Journal is quite young, open access indexing: DOAJ; CROSSREF. Reputation not assessable
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; downloads statistics displayed per article.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity good. 2. Design topics related to wellness, disability and gaming. 3. Good inclusivity of underrepresented topics and researches.
Editorial composition:	65% international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social Sciences; Psychology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

22.

Journal of Computational Design and Engineering

Affiliation	Oxford University Press , United Kingdom Society for Computational Design and Engineering, Republic of Korea
Funding date	2014
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Computational advancement for design and engineering; Development of a computational framework to support large scale design and engineering; Interaction issues among human, designed artefacts, and systems; Knowledge-intensive technologies for intelligent and sustainable systems; Emerging technology and convergence of technology fields presented with convincing design examples; Educational issues for academia, practitioners, and future generation
Design and layout:	Oxford Press Journals' Platform (ScholarOne submission system). Easy to navigate. Archives accessible
Publication frequency:	6 issues per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; APC: US\$2,050 The corresponding author based in one of the developing countries and regions listed in the APC waiver policy is eligible for a full waiver of APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Very high impact; indexed in SCOPUS and WOS
Impact score:	H-Index: 45
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	SCOPUS Citation score high: 7,7 (2023)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity medium (2021: 31.31%; 2022: 35.25%; 2023: 32.80%); 2. Low diversity of topics from design disciplines mainly at the intersection with computer interface and engineering technologies. 3. Low inclusivity of global south areas or case studies from underrepresented voices.
Editorial composition:	62% international, predominantly from Global North countries
Review process:	Single-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Graphical Abstracts – Accepted manuscripts. PDF versions of the author's final manuscript, as accepted for publication by the journal but prior to copyediting or typesetting. They can be cited using the author(s), article title, journal title, year of online publication, and DOI. They will be replaced by the final typeset articles, which may therefore contain changes. The DOI will remain the same throughout.
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering; Mathematics
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Mathematics: #14/189 Engineering: #10/89 Computer Science: #13/106

23.

Journal of Creative Industries and Cultural Studies JOCIS

Affiliation	MediaXXI/ Formalpress in partnership with several international entities, such as International Media Management Academic Association (IMMAA), and also with the collaboration of the Centre for Research in Communication, Information and Digital Culture (CIC. Digital) of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities of the University of Porto and the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences of the University Nova of Lisbon, Portugal
Funding date	2017
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design and social innovation, Creative and cultural industries; Arts and cultural economy; Marketing in creative and cultural industries; Creative and cultural industries' management; Communication; Visual communication and interactive media; Culture and development
Design and layout:	Website easy to access, however digital archives start from 2022. Volumes are not categorized. Authors not displayed with title; PDF standard. Submission platform through a website form
Publication frequency:	Not clear
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexed in DOAJ, EBSCOhost, ERIH Plus, e-LIS, Dialnet, Latindex, Google Scholar Citations, MIAR. Impact on academic community not available.impact; indexed in SCOPUS and WOS
Impact score:	Not available; seems to have major impact on the mediterranean area
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors mainly from European region. 2. High diversity of topics. 3. Low representation of diverse perspectives
Editorial composition:	Highly international; competencies not displayed
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Many authors are professionals from industry and sector
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Business and marketing; AI and technologies; Media Studies
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

24.

Journal of Design for Resilience in Architecture and Planning

Affiliation	Istanbul Teknik Üniversitesi Konya, Turchia
Funding date	2020
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Architectural Design, Urban Design, Industrial design, Interior design, 3D Virtual design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. English version. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly + Annual Special Issue
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access Insexing: DOAJ, EBSCO, ERIHPlus, BASE, Core – Collection of open-access research papers, Dimensions, EAAE – Architectural periodicals database, EZB: Electronic Journals Library, Google Scholar – Academic search engine, ICONDA®Bibliographic – The International CONstruction Database, IdealOnline, JUFO Portal – Federation of Finnish Learned Societies KOAR: Korea Open Access platform for Researchers, OpenAIRE – Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe, Scilit, Sherpa Romeo, ROAD (ISSN) National Index: TRDZIN (Turkish National Evaluation Index)
Impact score:	Low Impact according to National Index TRDZIN Citation Average: 0,07 Main impact on the Mediterranean area (North Africa, South Eastern Balkans and Turkey)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation average 0,07 Download statistics displayed for each article.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors mainly from Turkish affiliations and Mediterranean countries such as Albania, Algeria and south-eastern countries. 2. Very limited topics from design discipline, mainly at the intersection with architectural and urban planning. 3. Very high level of inclusivity of underrepresented researchers from the global south countries.
Editorial composition:	38% international, representing both perspectives from Global North and Global South
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review; Very good explanation of the editorial process
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural Heritage, Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

25.

Journal of Design Research

Affiliation	Inderscience Enterprises Ltd
Funding date	2001
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Expertise in design; Design learning strategies and design pedagogy; Design as a social process; Gaming and simulation in design; Designing user interfaces; The role of visual techniques in the design process; Design tools; Sustainability
Design and layout:	Publisher's Platform; Easy to navigate; Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Not fully Open access; only some issues. Gold Open Access offered to authors for: USD \$3000 for each article accepted
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact on EU design community and broad indexing level: Scopus (Elsevier), Academic OneFile (Gale), cnpLINKer (CNPIEC), DAAI: Design and Applied Arts Index Expanded Academic ASAP (Gale), OneFile Business (Gale), General OneFile (Gale) Google Scholar, Info Trac (Gale), Inspec (Institution of Engineering and Technology) J-Gate, ProQuest Advanced Technologies Database with Aerospace, JDR is listed in: Italian National System (Anvur), The BFI lists, UGC (University Grants Commission) ICI World of Journals (Copernicus), JUFO (Finnish), Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers
Impact score:	Scimago H-Index: 23
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 0,6
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Good international diversity(25–30%). 2. Broad and interdisciplinary topics of design research. 3. Low level of inclusivity of diverse perspectives and peripheral areas
Editorial composition:	85% International
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering; Computer Graphics and Computer-Aided Design
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Engineering: #174/204 Computer Graphics and Computer-Aided Design: #93/106

26.

Journal of Graphic Engineering and Design_JGED

Affiliation	University of Novi Sad; Serbia
Funding date	2010
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Graphic design, Industrial and product design, Typography
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main international indexes: SCOPUS (Elsevier), DOAJ, EBSCO, WorldCat, Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
Impact score:	Medium-low CiteScore on SCOPUS: 1,4SJR: 0,4Low-medium ranking on Scopus: #58/89
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Medium CiteScore on SCOPUS: 1,4 (87 citations over 60 documents published between 2020 and 2023)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Good international collaboration, mainly eastern Europe and south-eastern Asia. 2. Wide coverage of design topics. 3. High representation of global south countries.
Editorial composition:	Prevalence of international affiliation; women under represented.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering; Computer Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Engineering: #58/89 Computer Science: #74/106

27.

Journal of Industrial Design and Engineering Graphics_JIDEG

Affiliation	Societatea Română de Grafică Inginerească (Romanian Association of Engineering graphics)
Funding date	2006
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Industrial design and graphic design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Semestral, 2 issues per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; Yes APC (50€)
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact on romanian design community. Good indexing (DOAJ, Google Scholar, EBSCO), no SCOPUS or WOS
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rate not available, but number of download of each article displayed. Low impact (less 30 downloads per paper per month)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity, only romanian authors. 2. Low disciplinary diversity. 3. Local case studies
Editorial composition:	Scientific board not displayed
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	No COPE; ethics standards not explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	They publish proceedings of Conference on Engineering Graphics and Design ICEGD (organised by the same association)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

28.

Journal of Technology in Architecture Design and Planning

Affiliation	Istanbul University Press , Türkiye
Funding date	2023
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Knowledge in the fields of architecture, design and planning with a focus on technology dimension
Design and layout:	Publisher's Platform; easy to navigate, English language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Young Journal. Main indexing: Open Access – ErihPlus, DOAJ
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity, mainly national. 2. Broad range of design topics. 3. Interesting level of case studies of design practice from underrepresented peripheral areas
Editorial composition:	50% international (Global North countries)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), the Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA), and the World Association of Medical Editors (WAME)
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Each article has a QRCode for sharing options. Early View Articles (Pre-Print).
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural Heritage
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

29.

Proyecta 56_ An Industrial Design Journal

Affiliation	2020–2023: Universidad de Cádiz 2023–present: Universidad de Málaga, Spain
Funding date	2021
Language:	Spanish, English
Scope and relevance:	Industrial design user experience product innovation sustainable design aesthetic and history new product development
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. Also English and Italian versions of the website. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	NATIONAL IMPACT and LATIN COUNTRIES. The Journal received the 2014 Young Creation award from the Youth Institute. Thanks to this award, the Journal became a print publication. This journal also participates in the “La hora del Diseño” (Design Time) exhibition (an international travelling exhibition in Madrid–San Salvador–Tegucigalpa–Managua) and “Outside the Box” exhibition (a national exhibition at the National Museum of Decoration Arts and Design).
Impact score:	Indexing not available on the website. Presumably, OPEN ACCESS indexing and Redalyc databases (Latin countries)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very international, authors main origins are Spain, Italy and South America. 2. Very wide range of design topics. 3. Several case studies from underrepresented regions of South America.
Editorial composition:	60% international (Europe and South America; 1 member from US)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review. List of reviewers published
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Some years before, from 2013 to 2015, this journal presented articles of an informative nature, and at that time collaborated with more than 100 national and international professionals and lecturers, always in the field of Industrial Design. During this first stage of the journal, Proyecta56, hosted by La Térmica Centre of Cultural Creation and Production (Málaga).
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Not available
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

30.

Res Mobilis_ International Research Journal of Furniture and Decorative Objects

Affiliation	Rediuno, Publicaciones Universidad de Oviedo, Spain
Funding date	2012
Language:	French, Spanish, English, Portuguese (Articles prevalently in Spanish)
Scope and relevance:	Art history interior design furniture interior decoration
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Website accessible in English, Spanish and Portuguese. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual or quarterly (not standard)
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexed in Scopus, Web of Science. Indexed in Open access indexes: Google Scholar, ERIHPlus, DOAJ, Academic Journals Data; Base; Also Latin indexes: Latindex, Dialnet, Cecies, REDIB, CIRC, Dulcinea, MIAR; Main impact on Latin regions, considering that articles are prevalently in Spanish language (title and abstracts also in english)
Impact score:	H Index (Scimago): 2 (low)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Medium-low Citescore: 0,2
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium geographic diversity, mostly from Iberian region, Mediterranean area and South America. 2. Very wide coverage of design topics. 3. Good level of case studies from global south countries
Editorial composition:	85% international; W and M balanced.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review. List of reviewers published
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Elsevier
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social Sciences; Anthropology
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS: Social Sciences: #1155/1760 Anthropology: #440/502

31.

Research in Arts and Education

Affiliation	Aalto University , Finland
Funding date	2004
Language:	English and Finnish
Scope and relevance:	Design practice
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Website accessible in English. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact national; Indexing not published. Presumably Open Access. National Indexing: JUFO portal (Finnish Academic Database)
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. high international diversity in terms of authorship. 2. Very broad range of topics in design discipline. 3. High number of case studies and researchers from the Global South
Editorial composition:	68% international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Not published
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Proceedings from The Art of Research Conference
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

32.

Revista de Expresión Gráfica en la Edificación

Affiliation	Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain Asociación de Profesores de Expresión Gráfica Aplicada a la Edificación – APEGA, Spain
Funding date	2001
Language:	Spanish and English
Scope and relevance:	Architectural Graphic Expression and Graphic Engineering
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Website accessible in English and Spanish. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access since 2020; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Impact on European and Latin regions. Indexed in: ESCI (Emerging Sources Citation Index, WoS database), ANVUR (Italy), Dialnet, MIAR, Google Scholar Profile; DOAJ , ERIH PLUS , REDIB , Sherpa Romeo, Ulrichsweb
Impact score:	Clarivate: Journal Impact Factor 2023: 0.5
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Clarivate Citescore 2023: 0,60 (fair)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity. 2. Design topics limited to architecture design. 3. Fair amount of underrepresented areas of Global South. Good inclusivity of Young reserachers (<i>Reseñas de libros y tesis doctorales</i>)
Editorial composition:	24% international (mainly Global North)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Reseñas de libros y tesis doctorales
Networking activities:	Inclusivity of Practitioners
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

33.

Technology and Technique of Typography

Affiliation	National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute
Funding date	2003
Language:	Ukrainian
Scope and relevance:	Publishing; printing; editing design
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate; archives fully accessible from 2008 issues. Also PRINTED
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access since 2020; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Digital indexing not published (DOAJ); PRINT stored in the main libraries of the country. Main impact on national community.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low. prevalence of researchers from Ukraine. 3. Topics within design discipline cover mainly publishing and visual communication branches. 3-very low level of inclusivity from the rest of the world.
Editorial composition:	25% international (Poland, Sweden, India)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	No COPE, but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine arts; Technology; Media studies
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

34.	Tekstilec
Affiliation	University of Ljubljana Press (Založba Univerze v Ljubljani) , Slovenia University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, Slovenia
Funding date	2000
Language:	Slovenian and English
Scope and relevance:	Fashion Design, material design
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate; Archives fully accessible. However, a bit confusing because two different websites for 2021–2023 and before 2020.
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexed in SCOPUS and WOS; good regional impact on Western Balkans and Middle-Eastern Europe
Impact score:	Good impact score; H-Index 15
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citescore 2023: 1,3 (medium)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. high geographic diversity, especially Global South (Western Balkans and Middle-East Asia) 2. Design topics only within the realm of fashion 3. High number of case studies from underrepresented countries.
Editorial composition:	64% international (mainly from GLOBAL SOUTH)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Sponsorship: Association of Slovene Textile Engineers and Technicians Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia – Textiles, Clothing and Leather Processing Industry
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Business, Management and Accounting Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Materials Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	Business, Management and Accounting #157/218 Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering #257/384 Materials Science #123/161

35.	Temes de Disseny
Affiliation	Elisava Barcelona School of Design and Engineering, Spain
Funding date	1986 Peer reviewed and open access: 2018
Language:	Slovenian, English and Catalan
Scope and relevance:	Design Cultures
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate; Archives fully accessible. English, Spanish, Catalan language. Archives fully accessible since 2005
Publication frequency:	Annual - until 2024 Biannual - 2024 on
Accessibility:	Open Access, NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Relevant for the design community internationally. Indexed in SCOPUS, Open Access Indexes and Latin Indexes: academia.edu, Carhus Plus+ 2018: D, CiteFactor, CrossRef, Dialnet, Dimensions, DOAJ, Dulcinea, ERIH PLUS, Google Scholar (h-index: 9) , Latindex (Catalog v2.0), Lens, MIAR, (ICDS: 4), OpenAlex, RACO , Rebiun , REDIB, Semantic Scholar, Sherpa Romeo, WorldCat
Impact score:	Scimago H-Index: 3
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 1,0
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity, very international. 2. Very broad range of topics within design realm. 3. Good representation of underrepresented case studies.
Editorial composition:	27% International
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE, and PERK
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Video presentation of each issue by the Guest Editors describing the issue
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social Sciences Engineering Computer Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	Social Sciences: #358/1304 Engineering: #75/189 Computer Science: #84/106

36.

The Design Journal

Affiliation	Taylor and Francis The Design Journal is the official journal of the European Academy of Design.
Funding date	1997
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design management, theory, education, and practice in both cultural and commercial contexts, with direct impact on design knowledge
Design and layout:	Publisher's platform. Easy to navigate. Archives accessible
Publication frequency:	5/6 Issues per year
Accessibility:	The Design Journal is a hybrid open access journal. If you choose to publish open access in this journal you may be asked to pay an Article Publishing Charge (APC). EUR 3170
Journal impact and reputation:	The Design Journal is Taylor & Francis' flagship design journal. 270K annual downloads/views
Impact score:	Scimago H-Index: 29
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 2.0
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity. 2. Very broad range of design topics. 3. Low inclusiveness of underrepresented researchers
Editorial composition:	70% International
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Taylor and Francis Ethical Guidelines
Innovative practices and experimentation:	PhD Study Article: Article reporting on doctoral studies with specific methods, findings, and results
Networking activities:	The Design Journal is the official journal of the European Academy of Design
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities Computer Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Arts and Humanities: #163/552 Computer Graphics and Computer-Aided Design: #64/106

37.	Theory and Practice of Design
Affiliation	National Aviation University , Ukraine
Funding date	2012
Language:	Russian, Ukrainian, English
Scope and relevance:	Theory and practice of design and its theoretical part – an industrial art (technical aesthetics), of urban design, history and theory of architecture and research of current problems of art criticism.
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, easy to navigate. English language platform. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; Yes APC: The publication fee is 1000 UAH (for 16 pages). Each extra page is 40 UAH.
Journal impact and reputation:	National impact and national indexing. Prevalence of articles in Ukrainian language. Open access indexing: DOAJ, Crossref, Index Copernicus.
Impact score:	Not Available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Prevalence of articles in Ukrainian language; titles and abstracts in English.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity. 2. Broad range of design topics. 3. Low inclusivity
Editorial composition:	10% international (only Poland)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture; Urban Studies
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not Available

38.	Urban Izziv
Affiliation	Urban planning institute of the Republic of Slovenija
Funding date	1989
Language:	Slovenian, English
Scope and relevance:	Spatial planning urban planning and design regional development landscape planning and design housing studies traffic studies
Design and layout:	Digital archive. Website easy to navigate. Submission managed via email
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Relevant journal for researchers and professional from central and eastern Europe. Not specifically relevant for the design community. Indexed in Scopus, Clarivate, SCImago.
Impact score:	Scimago: H-index 21 SCOPUS Citation score 2023: 1.3 Fairly low; however the journal is indexed in the major academic database
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	108 citations between 2020–2023; low impact. Standard research and experimentation articles
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Mainly authors from Central and Eastern Europe, cases of latin america. 2. Very broad spectrum of topics in architecture, urban planning, design and governance. 3. Inclusivity is preserved through young researchers from underrepresented countries
Editorial composition:	75% international; W and M balanced. Diverse skills and competences
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	No COPE; not explicit.
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Yes, thematic and special issues. Issues for professionals that serve as professional assistance to all actors involved in various processes or spatial planning activities at all decision-making levels (local, municipal, regional and national)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Urban planning and architecture; governance
Interdisciplinary impact:	Highest citations in journals of: Social Sciences and cultural studies Engineering Geography

39.

User Experience & Urban Creativity UXUC

Affiliation	AP2 - Open Access Journals No profit Scientific Association and Publisher Associated with the Faculty of Fine Arts of the University of Lisbon, Research Unit CIEBA and and Interactive Technologies Institute (ITI/LARSyS)
Funding date	2019
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	User Experience (UX) in relation to built environment, urban planning, public space, urban design, and other environmental applications
Design and layout:	OJS platform standard
Publication frequency:	1/2 Issues per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; APC: 250\$ publication rate
Journal impact and reputation:	Main indexing databases, waiting for SCOPUS and WOS. Good reputation considering it is a young journal
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available, but statics on the most red articles are present (fair)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Mostly authors from Portuguese universities. Many voices from under represented countries (Turkey). 2. Topic diversity highly encouraged
Editorial composition:	Highly international; some voices also from global south (Malaysia, Romania, Turkey)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	No COPE; ethical standards not explicit.
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Informatics, Digital technologies and Social sciences.
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

40.

Agathón

Affiliation	Palermo University Press DEMETRA Ce.Ri.Med. (Euro-Mediterranean Documentation and Research Center), Italy
Funding date	2017
Language:	Italian and English
Scope and relevance:	"Design" (for industry, crafts and communication)
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; YES APC €450,00
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact; good indexing in Open Access: SCOPUS, CLASS A National Indexing; Google Scholar; DOAJ; BASE; OPENAIRE; INDEX Copernicus; ROAD; EBSCO; ElektronischeZeitSchriftenBibliothek; ErihPLus; OAJI
Impact score:	Scimago H-INDEXT: 3 Main impact: national
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 1,3 Articles metrics displayed per each article; all articles are both in Italian and English language.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic coverage, mainly Italy. 2. Design topics intersecting architecture and urbanism. 3. Low inclusivity of underrepresented voices. To encourage the publication of contributions by Authors with primary affiliation to Universities and Research Institutions in countries defined by the World Bank as low-income and lower-middle income economies, AGATHÓN selects a maximum of two Authors to publish their contributions for free, subject to the positive outcome of the double-blind peer-review process.
Editorial composition:	43% from EU countries
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Proceedings and conferences
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Engineering: #64/189 Social Sciences: #143/279

41.

AND

Affiliation	Association DNA (editrice) Associazione Culturale (Firenze)
Funding date	2003
Language:	Main language Italian - with English translation.
Scope and relevance:	Design and Architecture
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	OAJI - Open Academic Journal Index; ResearchBib - Academic Resource Index; EBSCO Publishing; LivRe - Revistas de livre acesso; ERIH PLUS - European Reference Index for the Humanities and the Social Sciences; ULRICH'S - Global Serials Directory; IPIndexing - Indexing Portal; EuroPub - Directory of Academic and Scientific Journals; Google Scholar; APeJ - Academic Publications eJournal; BASE - Bielefeld Academic Search Engine; JURN - Search tool for open-access content
Impact score:	Low impact factor. No indexing in major databases for journal ranking
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Prevalence of authors of Italian affiliation. 2. Medium coverage of topics within design discipline - mainly related to architecture, sustainability and planning. 3. Low diversity in perspectives and under-represented voices
Editorial composition:	65% Italian, 35% international. 1 member from Global South country
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Mainly with architecture
Interdisciplinary impact:	Citation rates not available

42.

diid.disegno industriale industrial design

Affiliation	BUP, Bologna, Italy Advanced Design Unit (Università di Bologna)
Funding date	2002; open access and digital since 2021
Language:	Since 2021 only English
Scope and relevance:	Design cultures, theories, methods and practices; advanced design and anticipation; product design, communication design, fashion design, service design, strategic design; design strategies and management; interaction design, experience design, behavioural design; sustainable design; design education; manufacturing, digital manufacturing, cultural and creative industries
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access Indexing: Ebsco and ErihPLUS- NO SCOPUS or WOS. Class A in national indexing. High national impact and EU impact
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Articles in English language. Citescore not available.
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium geographic diversity. 2. Very wide range of topics within design cultures. 3. High inclusivity of Global South, especially Latin region.
Editorial composition:	41% international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	QRCode in pdf file
Networking activities:	Special Issues; Conference Proceedings with the Latin Network; Promoter of international initiatives
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Art and Humanities; Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

43.

Fashion Highlight

Affiliation	Firenze University Press , Italy
Funding date	2023
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Fashion Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible. Platform in English language.
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing not published. Only national authors: main impact national.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low. Only national authors. 2. Limited scope of design topics; mainly intersecting fashion and consumers' behavior. 3. Low inclusivity levels
Editorial composition:	28% international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Conferences (Prosperity Fashion 2025)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Technology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

44.

Interaction Design and Architecture(s) IxD&A

Affiliation	ASLERD Association for Smart Learning Ecosystems and Regional Development, Italy
Funding date	2005
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design education; design interaction; experience design; systemic design
Design and layout:	Wordpress website; easy to navigate. Readability low because of black background. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Semestral
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Q1 level journal in the Design/Architecture field and, as well, the first Italian journal in the rankings of all sectors of reference: Design/Architecture, Media Technology, Social Science, Human-Computer Interaction, Computer Science Application, Education.
Impact score:	Indexed in SCOPUS and WOS Scopus Citescore: 2,5 SJR (2023) = 0.295
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Medium level of citation from 2020-2023 (370 citations)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors from all the world, authorship very international. 2. Wide range of topics. 3. High level of representation from Global south countries
Editorial composition:	Highly international
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Elsevier policies and COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	InIxD&A adopts the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) Video introduction (published on youtube) to describe each issuee
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Media Technology, Human-Computer Interaction and Computer Science Application — Social Science — Education
Interdisciplinary impact:	High level of citations in different disciplines as reported by Scopus citescore

45.	MD Journal
Affiliation	Media MD, University of Ferrara
Funding date	2016
Language:	Italian and English
Scope and relevance:	Design practice, research innovation, industrial design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. Slightly different from standard scientific journal websites Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access Indexing; Very relevant in the Italian design community – Classe A Anvur (Highest ranking for Italian Journals). However articles are prevalent in Italian language, limiting considerably the international impact of the journal
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. No geographic diversity. Only Italian authors. 2. Very broad scope of design discipline. 3. No examples of inclusivity
Editorial composition:	Not available: NO affiliations of the editorial board or scientific board are displayed
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Humanities; Social Sciences; Urban Planning; Ecology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

46.

PAD Journal

Affiliation	Associazione Italiana Design della Comunicazione Visiva, Italy (Ed. AIAP)
Funding date	2005
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Fine arts, Design and architecture
Design and layout:	Website design innovative, archives accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact on the Mediterranean area and Global south countries
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium – 1 to 3 international authors per issue. 2. Broad coverage of topics in design cultures. 3. High level of inclusivity, publishing many researchers from global south areas
Editorial composition:	Large editorial board with experts from both Global North and Global South. Very good representation of competences. W and M balanced.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None. However the internal sections appear to welcome different types of articles, such as visual essays
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and art history, Cultural heritage and fashion
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

47.	Techne_ Journal of Technology for Architecture and Environment
Affiliation	Firenze University Press , Italy Other organisation Italian Society of Architectural Technology, Italy
Funding date	2011
Language:	Italian and English
Scope and relevance:	Design practice intersecting Architecture and Urban Spaces
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, Easy to navigate. English Language. Archives fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; Yes APCs: € 400, if at least one of the Authors is a SITdA Member; € 500, if none of the Authors is a SITdA Member
Journal impact and reputation:	Good national Impact. Open Access Indexing: BASE, DOAJ, EBSCO, ESCI, EZB – Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek – Universitätsbibliothek Regensburg, JournalTOCs, Proquest. Indexed: SCOPUS
Impact score:	Scimago H-INDEX: 13
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 0,6
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low international diversity (only national authorship). 2. Design topics at the intersection with architecture and technologies. 3. Very low inclusivity
Editorial composition:	0% International
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	PRE-PRINT: Just accepted
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Engineering: #108/170 Social Sciences: #1291/1469

48.

Zonemoda Journal

Affiliation	University of Bologna (Dipartimento delle Arti)
Funding date	2009
Language:	Italian and English
Scope and relevance:	Fashion design, material design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, Easy to navigate
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Not available, not indexed on Scopus or WOS. Mainly impact on european and italian scientific community; most of the articles in Italian language
Impact score:	Not available, not indexed on Scopus or WOS
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available, not indexed on Scopus or WOS
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. 2 to 3 international authors per issue. 2. Medium topic coverage. 3 Low inclusion of underrepresented voices or projects from global south
Editorial composition:	25% international; W and M balanced
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural Heritage; Cultural Studies; Digital studies; Gender Studies
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

South America

49.	[re]Design
Affiliation	Editora IFMA , Brazil Other organisation: Center for Design and Information and Communication Technologies, linked to Editora IFMA Instituto Federal do Maranhão, Brazil
Funding date	2022
Language:	Portuguese, Spanish and English
Scope and relevance:	Visual Arts, Graphic Design, visual and digital culture; Human Centered Design, Universal Design and Inclusive Design; Education and cultures in the field of architecture, arts and design; Codesign, creative innovation and new technologies; Social innovation and sustainability; Design and craft processes; Fashion and textile technologies; Methodologies, tools and design techniques applied to the fields of Architecture, Arts
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. English and Portuguese language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Broad indexing: Mainly Open Access and Latin indexing: Crossref LatinRev Livre ROAD Google Scholar Latindex-Directorio Sumários Diadorim Aura SciJoln ResearchBib Base DRJI DOAJ Index Copernicus Oasisbr University of Saskatchewan Sherpa Romeo Miguilim Mirabel MIAR Dialnet
Impact score:	Young Journal; impact not assessable
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available. Most of the article is in Portuguese language, limited impact. Titles and Abstract in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity. 2. Wide coverage of design topics, mainly intersecting arts. 3. Considering the affiliation, represents a case of academic journal from Global South. However, low representation of other geographic areas.
Editorial composition:	6% international (only Portugal)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Financing Source IFMA Publisher – Federal Institute of Maranhão
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>50.</h1>	<h2>A3MANOS</h2>
Affiliation	SDI, Instituto Superior de Disegno de Universidad de La Habana
Funding date	2014
Language:	Spanish and English
Scope and relevance:	Design, Design of visual communication, Design in its relationship with other disciplines, Theory and pedagogy of design, Sustainable design, Design and society, New technologies for design and History of design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. English and Spanish language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access and Lating indexes: DOAJ, ROAD, ERIPLUS, Latindex Catalog 2.0, Latindex Directory, AmeliCA, SUDOC, RedCien, Revistas UH, MIAR, LatinREV NO SCOPUS or WOS; Statistics of country visits published: 55% from Cuba, 9,57% from Mexico, 7,20% from USA, 4,20% from Perù, 3,80% from Colombia, 3,45% Spain, >3% from Ecuador, Chile, Argentina, >1% Costa Rica, Venezuela, Bolivia.t
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; Views per articles displayed. Articles mainly in spanish language; international impact limited
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity, mainly authors from journal's affiliation and latin region. 2. Wide coverage of topics within design discipline. 3-good inclusivity of underrepresented case studies from Global South, considering that the Journals is based in a developing country. However low geographical inclusivity of other GS countries
Editorial composition:	Editorial Board affiliation mainly from Latin region (82%); 2 Italy, 1 Germany and 1 Russia
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	They declare to be in favour of PREPRINTS
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Art history; Informatics; Pedagogy
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

51.	ACTIO Journal of Technology in Design, Film Arts and Visual Communication
Affiliation	Universidad Nacional de Colombia , Colombia
Funding date	2017
Language:	English, Spanish and other Romance languages (Portuguese, French, Italian)
Scope and relevance:	Design (architectural, graphic, industrial)
Design and layout:	OJS platform, but within the general portal of all the University's Journals; it might look a bit confusing. Spanish and English language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access and Lating indexes: Red de Investigadores en Diseño – Universidad de Palermo; Directorio Latindex; Revista Ciencias y Humanidades; Manifiesto ALAEC por el uso responsable de métricas en las evaluaciones de la ciencia; realizadas en América Latina y en el Caribe; and DOAJ. Impact mainly regional.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Most of the articles are in Spanish language; however all abstracts and titles are translated in English, Spanish, Portuguese, French, Italian
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Latin countries diversity. 2. Wide range of design topics. 3. Good inclusivity of underrepresented case studies from Latin countries, considering that the Journals is based in South America. However low geographical inclusivity of other GS countries
Editorial composition:	75% international, but mainly from neighbor countries of the continent and Spain
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but ethical standards explicit in detail
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Use of QR codes in the PDF files
Networking activities:	Proceedings and networking with Conferences (e.g. IDEA)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine arts; Technology; Multimedia
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>52.</h1>	ACTIO Journal of Technology in Design, Film Arts and Visual Communication
Affiliation	Universidad Nacional de Colombia , Colombia
Funding date	2017
Language:	English, Spanish and other Romance languages (Portuguese, French, Italian)
Scope and relevance:	Design (architectural, graphic, industrial)
Design and layout:	OJS platform, but within the general portal of all the University's Journals; it might look a bit confusing. Spanish and English language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access and Lating indexes: Red de Investigadores en Diseño – Universidad de Palermo; Directorio Latindex; Revista Ciencias y Humanidades; Manifiesto ALAEC por el uso responsable de métricas en las evaluaciones de la ciencia; realizadas en América Latina y en el Caribe; and DOAJ. Impact mainly regional.
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Most of the articles are in Spanish language; however all abstracts and titles are translated in English, Spanish, Portuguese, French, Italian
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Latin countries diversity. 2. Wide range of design topics. 3. Good inclusivity of underrepresented case studies from Latin countries, considering that the Journals is based in South America. However low geographical inclusivity of other GS countries
Editorial composition:	75% international, but mainly from neighbor countries of the continent and Spain
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but ethical standards explicit in detail
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Use of QR codes in the PDF files
Networking activities:	Proceedings and networking with Conferences (e.g. IDEA)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine arts; Technology; Multimedia
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>53.</h1>	Area Area, Agenda de Reflexión en Arquitectura, Diseño y Urbanismo
Affiliation	Universidad de Buenos Aires. Facultad de Arquitectura, Diseño y Urbanismo, Argentina
Funding date	Digital Archives from 2006; but first publication 1992
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Architecture, urban planning, graphic, industrial, product, clothing, textile and multimedia, design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. Only Spanish language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; from 2018 published in open access. NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing in Open access and Latin Indexing: Latindex, DOAJ, Núcleo básico de revistas científicas argentinas, REDIB red iberoamericana de innovación y conocimiento científico, DIALNET, REDSARA portal bibliográfico de literatura científica hispánica y nacional de portales de revistas científicas. The Journal publishes only in Spanish language (not even the abstracts and titles), limiting the impact
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity within the South American region. 2. Low coverage of design topics; mainly with visual design and multimedia. 3-good inclusivity of underrepresented case studies from Global South, considering that the Journals is based in a developing country. However low geographical inclusivity of other GS countries.
Editorial composition:	54% international, but mainly latin countries (1 Australian affiliation)_ good representation of design researchers.
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Thematic Dossier; Debates (not peer reviewed): is intended to publish articles that represent proactive, polemical, and urgent positions on the various fields of our disciplines. Outside the rules of refereeing and/or by editorial invitation, texts that promote current reflection on the ways of being of the city, its history, its inhabitants, and the multiple expressions of design that shape it will be included
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Cultural Heritage; Urbanism; Ecology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>54.</h1>	<h2>DAPesquisa</h2>
Affiliation	Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina , Brazil
Funding date	2006
Language:	Portugues (main) – Spanish– English
Scope and relevance:	Performing arts, visual arts, music, design and fashion
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. English translation included.
Publication frequency:	Four-mothly publication, however in the last 4 years 2-1 publication per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputa-tion:	Most of articles are in Portuguese language. Title and abstract in english. Main impact on the design community of the latin continent
Impact score:	Not indexed in SCOPUS, WOS or EBSCO; main indexation in latin databases such as LIVRE, LATINREV, Periodicos, RED IBEROAMERICANA, Sumarios
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Articles respond to basic traditional scientific requirements (abstracts, introduction, methodology, conclusion, references). Low citation of articles but considerable levels of downloads of articles (between 10 –30 per article each month
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Mainly Brazilian authors. 2. Broad spectrum of topics in design discipline. 3. Only brazilian perspective
Editorial composition:	15 Brazil, 1 Perù, 1 UK (low level of diversity in editorial composition)
Review process:	Double-blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Not mentioned, but ethical standards and transparency of process disclosed
Innovative practices and ex-perimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine arts sector, sociology and politcs
Interdisciplinary impact:	Low level of citations, however the number of downloads is considerably high

<h1>55.</h1>	<h2>DATJournal</h2>
Affiliation	Universidade Anhembi Morumbi, Brazil
Funding date	2016
Language:	Portuguese – Spanish– English
Scope and relevance:	Interdisciplinary between design, art and technology (very broad)
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexed Open Access databases (DOAJ, Google Scholar, ERIHPlus) Very good indexing in regional databases: LATindex, Redalyc, Diadorim, MIAR, Periodicos, REDIB, Sumarios. NO SCOPUS OR WOS. Articles mainly in Portuguese language limiting global impact
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity, mainly authors from the country and region; 2. Very broad range of design topics; 3–considering the affiliation of the journal inclusivity of researchers from GS is intrinsic. However there is no representation of other voices or case studies from other underrepresented area
Editorial composition:	23% international (mainly from Global North countries)
Review process:	Not specified
Ethical standards:	Not mentioned, but ethical standards and transparency of process disclosed
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Each issue is published with a DOSSIER: special sections edited by Guest editors on specific topics
Networking activities:	They publish Proceedings of Conferences and Simposia
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Arts, Digital Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

56.	DAYA, Diseño, Arte y Arquitectura
Affiliation	Universidad del Azuay, Ecuador
Funding date	2016
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Interior design, product design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible. Platform in Spanish and English (not fully translated)
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Revista DAYA está indexada en las siguientes bases de datos: Latindex Catálogo 2.0, DOAJ, ROAD, RRAAE, ResarchBib, Google Scholar y REDIB. Main impact on the latin american region
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; statistics of download per each article displayed. Articles in spanish language, however all abstracts and titles are translated in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity low, mainly from Latino American continent. 2-broad range of topics in design discipline and intersection with arts and architecture. 3-good representation of underrepresented case studies and researchers
Editorial composition:	100% international only from latin countries
Review process:	Double Blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Networking ith research groups and thematic investigations, e.g.: Red Académica de Diseño y Emociones
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences and architecture
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>57.</h1>	<h2>Design e Tecnologia</h2>
Affiliation	GDesign/UFRGS , Brazil
Funding date	2010
Language:	Portuguese and English
Scope and relevance:	Design and its relationships with technology
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible. Platform only in Portuguese Language
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact: Latin region. Latin indexing: Periodicos, Latindex, Diadorim, Sumarios, MIAR, Dialnet, Redib. Open Access: ErihPlus, DOAJ
Impact score:	Not available; Prevalence of Portuguese language
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Prevalence of Portuguese language; titles and abstracts in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographical diversity. 2. Wide range of design topics. 3. Affiliation in Latin American, intrinsic representation of underrepresented voices and case studies from Latino America
Editorial composition:	2/7 international, from Portugal and Croatia
Review process:	Not explicit
Ethical standards:	Not explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Not explicit
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

58.	Designio. Investigación en Diseño Gráfico y Estudios de la Imagen
Affiliation	Editorial Universitaria San Mateo and Fundación Universitaria San Mateo, Colombia
Funding date	2019
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Design management and marketing; design cultures; culture and creative sector
Design and layout:	OJS platform; archive fully accessible; website in spanish and english language
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good open access indexing (DOAJ, Google, ERhPlus, Base, OAJI); Good Latin indexing (REDIB, Latindex, LatinRev, Dialnet); Impact on the region and latin countries NO SCOPUS or WOS
Impact score:	Not available, but Visitors rate published
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available. Standard traditional scientific articles
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Considering that the journal publishes only in Spanish, diversity is limited. Authors mainly from latin countries. 2–Topics at the intersection of design and art.However low range of topics within design discipline. 3–Considering the Journal is based in a country of the Global South, inclusivity is intrinsecal. However, it publishes authors and case studies only from the Latin continent
Editorial composition:	Only from Latin–American countries
Review process:	Peer Review process, but not stated if blind and how many reviewers involved. Peer review criteria published
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine arts, Art history, Literature
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>59.</h1>	<h2>Diseña</h2>
Affiliation	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile
Funding date	2016 (Open Access)
Language:	English and Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Design Cultures – all areas
Design and layout:	OJS platform; archive fully accessible; website in Spanish and English language. Archives accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Regional indexing: Latindex-Catálogo 2.0; REDIB; Open Access: DOAJ. Also SCOPUS indexed.
Impact score:	Scimago H-INDEX: 4
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	SCOPUS Citescore 2023 Low: 0,7
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium-high geographic diversity (23%). 2. Broad range of topics within design discipline. 3. High coverage of diverse perspective and case studies, especially from Latin America
Editorial composition:	60% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Engineering: #169/204 Social Sciences: #415/604

<h1>60.</h1>	<h2>Ergodesign & HCI</h2>
Affiliation	Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro , Brazil
Funding date	2013
Language:	Portuguese and English
Scope and relevance:	Ergodesign de Produtos e Processos do Design; Ergodesign de Sistemas de Informação; Ergodesign da Interação Humano-Computador; Ergodesign do Espaço Construído; Ergodesign de Sistemas de Transportes
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Only Portuguese language. Archives accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact regional; Articles only in Portuguese language. Latin indexing: Periodicos; Diadorim; Capes Open access Indexing: DOAJ; CrossRef
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available. Articles in Portuguese language; titles and abstracts translated in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity; mainly Brazil. 2. Wide range of design topics within product design and user interface area. 3. Inclusivity of case studies from peripheral areas of the Southern American region
Editorial composition:	18% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Elsevier's Publishing Ethics for Editors
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Computer science
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

61.	Estudos em Design
Affiliation	Associação Estudos em Design, Brazil Support: Programa de Pós-graduação em Design da PUC-Rio
Funding date	1993, Open access since 2007
Language:	Portuguese and English
Scope and relevance:	Design and technology: User Experience Design (UX); Information Design; Interaction design; Interface design Game design; Sound design; Design and society: Public policies in design; Representation and social participation; Social innovation; Design and cultural practices; Design and education: Pedagogical approaches; Procedures and tools; Technological applications; Design teaching theories and practices; Service design; Design management; Strategic Design; Design and Innovation; Graphic design and product design: Packaging design; Editorial design; Signage design; Furniture design, Lighting design; Fashion Design; Jewelry Design; Print Design; Ergonomics applied to Design; Ecodesign; Sustainability
Design and layout:	Old version of OJS System. Easy to navigate, Archives accessible from 2007. Most of the website content is published in Portuguese language
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	National Impact: Qualis CAPES A1 (Qualis is a Brazilian official system to classify scientific production. It is maintained by the Coordenadoria de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES), a government agency linked to the Brazilian Ministry of Education Open Access Indexing
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Research and experimentation Articles. Titles, Abstracts, and Keywords of articles in Portuguese are available in English. No Citescore available or download statistics
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low, mainly authors from Brazilian universities and regions. 2. Very wide spectrum of design topics. 3. Representation of academic research from the Latin countries, considering the journal is based in the Global South
Editorial composition:	11 members in the International Scientific Board, 10 of them from Europe, 1 from Singapore
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	The Journal publishes a section called: Scientific initiation is a type of academic research developed by undergraduate students at Brazilian universities in various areas of knowledge
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Humanities and Ecology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

62.

InfoDesign_ Brazilian Journal of Information Design

Affiliation	Brazilian Information Design Society (SBDI), Brazil
Funding date	2004
Language:	Portuguese and English
Scope and relevance:	Information Design, Data visualization, Graphic Design, Typography
Design and layout:	OJS platform, Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Latin indexes: LATINdex, GALE, Sumarios Open access indexes: DOAJ, EBSCO Articles are in Portuguese and English; impact not assessable, however
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not Available. Statistics of downloads available in each article
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Prevalence of authors from Latin countries. 2. Very interdisciplinary topics within design cultures. 3. High coverage of case studies and projects from global south areas
Editorial composition:	Scientific Board not published. Editorial Team prevalence from Brazil and Portugal
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Inclusion of a section dedicated to Undergraduate Research
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Very interdisciplinary. Health and wellbeing, Urbanism, Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

63.

Iniciacao

Affiliation	Revista de Iniciação Científica, Tecnológica e Artística Centro Universitário Senac , Brazil
Funding date	2010
Language:	Portuguese
Scope and relevance:	Technology communication design fashion sustenaibility
Design and layout:	Easy to navigate, but the platform only in Portuguese. Title and abstract in english
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexed only in major latin batabases
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Traditional research and experimentation articles. Citation rates not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low-only Brazil. 2. Broad spectrum of topics in fine arts sector. 3. Mainly voices from Brazil
Editorial composition:	No diversity - only members from Brazil from sam University of affiliation. W and M balanced
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Not explicated
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Arts
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

64.

KEPES

Affiliation	Universidad de Caldas, Colombia
Funding date	2004
Language:	Portuguese, English, Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Design communication, image, visual arts, digital media, image theory
Design and layout:	Easy to navigate, very clear functions. Digital archives easy to access. OJS portal for submissions
Publication frequency:	Semestral
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	High impact for the design community in the latin region. It is indexed in SCOPUS and the major latin databases. H-index Scimago: 6 Most of the articles in Spanish language
Impact score:	SCOPUS Citescore low: 0,5 for 2023
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Main language of the articles is Spanish. Citation rate of the articles in Scopus Journals is low (60 citations between 2020–2023). However statics of visualization and downloads of the articles on the website is higher (since 2020 visits and downloads have reached 3000 visitors)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Since 2020 the percentage of international authors according to Scimago is about 12% to 20%. 2. Topics are mainly from the field of arts, art history, visual arts, industrial design. 3.inclusion of authors from latin countries
Editorial composition:	Editorial board very limited or not explicit: 60% from Colombia, 40% from Ecuador and Spain
Review process:	Double Blind peer review. Peer review FORM accessible on the website
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social Sciences, Psychology and behaviour
Interdisciplinary impact:	Impact on Visual Art and performative Art journals

<h1>65.</h1>	<h2>Legado de Arquitectura y Diseño</h2>
Affiliation	Universidad Autonoma del Estado de México , Mexico
Funding date	2013
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Urban Design, Design Research and methodologies
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. English and Spanish language. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good regional impact, considering it's published only in Spanish language. Main Open Access Indexing: ErihPlus, DOAJ, CLASE, SherpaRomeo, EBSCO. Good Latin Indexing: ARLA, BIBLAT, LATINDEX, LATINREV, MIAR, REDIB, CIRC. Also SCOPUS indexed; but low international impact
Impact score:	H Index: 2 (Scimago)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore low: 0,1 Articles are in spanish language, but titles and abstracts also in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low international collaboration. 2-low, predominance of design topics intersecting with architecture and urban studies. 3- high number of case studies of underrepresented regions of Latin American, but low coverage of other areas of the GS
Editorial composition:	44% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering and Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Engineering: #168/189 Social Sciences: #263/279

66.	MADGU Mundo, Arquitectura, Diseño Gráfico y Urbanismo
Affiliation	Universidad de Sonora, Mexico
Funding date	2018
Language:	Spanish and English
Scope and relevance:	Design for architecture and urbanism, field of social sciences as well. DOAJ: Architecture graphic design urbanism industrial design
Design and layout:	Easy to navigate, Archives open access. Only Spanish language
Publication frequency:	Semestral
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	The Journal is relatively young; from 2021 the number of visits have increased over 150 per year and articles' download 1000. However it is not possible to identify the countries of the users to determine the impact of the Journal. Authors are mainly from Latin American continent
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation rates not available, however medium statistics in download and access of articles. Standard research and experimentation articles
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors from Latin American countries. 2. Diversity of topic, very interdisciplinary. 3. Good representation of researchers and projects of under developed areas
Editorial composition:	No international members, only Mexican, except for 1 Argentinian. W and M balanced
Review process:	Double Blind peer review and Publication of the PEER REVIEW FORM
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards clearly explained
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Governance and Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

67.	Ñawi_ Arte, Diseño y Comunicación
Affiliation	FADCOM, Facultad de Arte, Diseño y Comunicación Audiovisual, Ecuador
Funding date	2017
Language:	Spanish and English
Scope and relevance:	Design and Visual Communication
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Digital archive fully accessible. English version
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Good indexing (Google Scholar, Ebsco, DOAJ, Ulrichsweb), liLatin indexing (Latin Index, Red Iberoamerican, SClelo Ecuador). Articles are mainly in Spanish language
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	The journal aims to become a reference in the Ecuadorian and Latin American academic world. No citation rates available, but downloads' number per each paper per month.Rates of downloads (20-60 per month per paper)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Mainly authors from Latin America region. 2. Low diversity of topics within design discipline. 3. Inclusion strongly promoted, underrepresented researchers and case studies
Editorial composition:	International, but latin region.
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards clearly explained
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine art; audio-visual and media studies; cultural heritage
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

68.	Pós_ Revista do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Arquitetura e Urbanismo da FAUUSP
Affiliation	Universidade de São Paulo (USP) , Brazil
Funding date	2002
Language:	Spanish, Portuguese, English
Scope and relevance:	Urban design urban planning architecture architectural heritage architecture design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform. Easy to navigate. In English, Spanish and Portuguese language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open access databases (Google Scholar; DOAJ; Getty) and Latin American indexes: LATINDEX, Diadorim, Periodicos. Main impact on south american continent. Most of the articles are in Portuguese language; impact limited. Title and abstracts in English
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; download statistics shown in each article
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity (mainly from the University of affiliation). 2–design topics at the intersection with architecture and urbanism. 3–considering the journal is affiliated in the Global South, representation is high for researchers (especially young) from the Latin American countries and indigenous case studies
Editorial composition:	45% International; W and M balanced
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards clearly explained
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Thematic Dossier
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences; Economics
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

69.

Projetica

Affiliation	Universidade Estadual de Londrina (UEL), Brazil
Funding date	2010
Language:	Portoguese
Scope and relevance:	Industrial Design, Ergonomics, product design, design cultures, fashion design, communication design
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate
Publication frequency:	Quartely
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main OA indexing: google scholar, DOAJ, ERIHPlus. Yes latin indexing (LatinIndex, Periodicos,OasisBR, CAPES) But NO SCOPUS OR WOS
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low diversity, mainly Brazilian authors. 2. Very borad range of topics within design spectrum. 3. Considering it is based in the GS intrinsically publishes underrepresented researchers, however just from the latin region
Editorial composition:	Low diversity, mainly from Brazil and latin countries
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards clearly explained
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Yes, the journal publishes Conference proceedings (e.g. 14º Congresso Brasileiro de Pesquisa e Desenvolvimento em Design – P&D Design realizado no Rio de Janeiro de 26 à 29 de Outubro de 2022 pela ESDI/RJ e ESPM/RJ)
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences; Technology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

70.

RChD_ Creación y Pensamiento

Affiliation	Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Departamento de Diseño, Universidad de Chile
Funding date	2006
Language:	Spanish, English, and Portuguese
Scope and relevance:	Transdisciplinary knowledge around design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. English and Spanish language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing not displayed. Impact on the latin area
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium, mainly from Latin American continent. 2-Wide perspectives of design cultures, mainly at intersection with social sciences. 3-high level of representation of case studies from peripheral areas
Editorial composition:	91% international (latin countries)
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE; but ethical standards clearly explained
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Social sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

71.	Revista de Ensino em Artes, Moda e Design REAMD
Affiliation	University of the State Santa Catarina, Brazil
Funding date	2017
Language:	Portuguese, French, Italian, English
Scope and relevance:	Design Cultures; Fashion Design; Product Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible. All languages.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact national and regional. Latin indexing: sumarios.org , Latindex, REDIB, DIADORIM, LIVRE, LatinRev; OasisBR, Open Access indexing: DOAJ; CROSSREF; ERIHPLUS; INDEX COPERNICUS
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not assessable, however all articles have title and abstract in english. 40-50% of articles translated in English language
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity. 2- wide range of topics covered within the design discipline, mainly intersecting arts and humanities. 3-medium representation level of case studies from the Global South
Editorial composition:	13% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>72.</h1>	<h2>Revista Projetar</h2>
Affiliation	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil
Funding date	2016
Language:	Portuguese
Scope and relevance:	Urban Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact is national (most of articles are in portuguese language). Regional indexing: Actualidad Iberoamericana, Latindex; Diadorim; Open Access indexing: DOAJ and Google Scholar; One EU index: Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not assessable. Most of article in Portuguese language, Title and abstract in English. Most read articles displayed on the side column of the homepage
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity low, mainly authors from the region. 2. Design topics limited at the intersection with architecture and urbanism. 3. High representation of undercover case studies from global south regions
Editorial composition:	28% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	PROJETAR Seminar, founded by the UFRN Research Group
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architetture and Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>73.</h1>	<h2>Revista Projotar</h2>
Affiliation	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil
Funding date	2016
Language:	Portuguese
Scope and relevance:	Urban Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform; easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact is national (most of articles are in portuguese language). Regional indexing: Actualidad Iberoamericana, Latindex; Diadorim; Open Access indexing: DOAJ and Google Scholar; One EU index: Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not assessable. Most of article in Portuguese language, Title and abstract in English. Most read articles displayed on the side column of the homepage
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity low, mainly authors from the region. 2. Design topics limited at the intersection with architecture and urbanism. 3. High representation of undercover case studies from global south regions
Editorial composition:	28% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	PROJETAR Seminar, founded by the UFRN Research Group
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture and Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

<h1>74.</h1>	<h2>Strategic Design Research Journal SDRJ</h2>
Affiliation	Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos (UNISINOS) , Brazil
Funding date	2008 – Archives from 2010
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design theory and Design practice
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate, English language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Quarterly/Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	High international Impact; Wide coverage of international databases (Open access and regional): SCOPUS (Elsevier), EbscoHost, Proquest, Google Scholar, REDIB, DOAJ – Directory of Open Access Journals, SHERPA/RoMEO, Livre – Revistas de livre acess, JournalTOCs, ExLibris, Sumários, WorldCat, ResearchGate, Microsoft Academic, Periódicos Capes, Journals for Free, Latindex,, CLASSE A Anvur (Italian National Index)
Impact score:	SCIMAGo Journal Ranking: 1,83 H-index: 10
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	High article impact: 2023 – Scopus Citescore: 1,6 (182 citations/113 documents) 2024 – Scopus Citescore: 1,8 (143 citations/80 documents)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High international diversity (more then 30%). 2. Very wide coverage of design topics. 3. Very high level of inclusivity
Editorial composition:	49% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	No COPE; ethical standards not explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Proceedings of Conferences
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Engineering; Modeling and Simulation
Interdisciplinary impact:	Arts and Humanities: #14/173 Engineering: #187/307 Modeling and Simulation: #239/324

75.	UCES D.G. _Enseñanza y Aprendizaje del Diseño
Affiliation	Universidad de Ciencias Empresariales y Sociales, Argentina
Funding date	2011
Language:	Spanish
Scope and relevance:	Design and visual communication; design and advertising management and strategies. Creative industries. Art research; Representation systems, morphology, typography; User experience and interactive design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate, only Spanish language. Archives fully accessible but not chronological; not user friendly
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	The journal is published in spanish language, regional impact. Latin indexing: Latindex, LatinREV, MIAR, MALENA, CONEICC,REBIUN, SIUBDU; and open access indexing: DOAJ, ROAD, CORE
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available, articles in Spanish language. Titles and Abstracts of the Research articles translated in English. Download statistics displayed per each article
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Diversity is low, mainly from the Latin region. 2. Broad range of design topics intersecting with arts and humanities. 3-good level of representation of global south researchers and case studies from the region, considering affiliation of the journal, but no representation of other areas
Editorial composition:	The Editorial Committee prevalently from Argentina and Mexico
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	They have started using PRE-PRINTS since 2024
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Social sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

Asia

76.

ANDHARUPA_ Jurnal Desain Komunikasi Visual & Multimedia

Affiliation	Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, Indonesia
Funding date	2015
Language:	English and Indonesian
Scope and relevance:	Graphic design, visual communication, visual culture, audio visual, web design, advertising, photography, videography, animation, multimedia, and game design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate. English language; archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	4 Issues per year
Accessibility:	Open Access; The APC price is 500.000 IDR for the review process which is requested at the beginning after the article is declared according to the scope and guidelines. Then, the Author is charged 1.000.000 IDR for publication
Journal impact and reputation:	National Ranking: SINTA 2. Open access indexing: DOAJ and Google Scholar and INDEX Copernicus GARUDA (South Asian regional indexing); main national and regional impact, considering that most of articles are publishes in Indonesian language
Impact score:	Not available. Visitors statistics displayed
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; most of articles are in Indonesian language
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low geographic diversity (mainly Indonesian universities). 2. Wide coverage on topics in design discipline. 3. Considering affiliation in Global South regions, good representation of researchers from GS and case studies from the area
Editorial composition:	Editorial board is fully national
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but Ethical Standards explicit in detail
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Multimedia; Fashion
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

77.

Archives of Design Research (ADR)

Affiliation	Korean Society of Design Science
Funding date	2007
Language:	English and Korean with an English abstract
Scope and relevance:	Design Theory and its Methodology, Design Philosophy, Ethics, Values, and Issues; Design Education, Design Management and Strategy; Sustainability, Culture, History, and Societal Design, Human Behaviors; Perception, and Emotion, Semantics, Aesthetics and Experience in Design; Interaction and Interface Design; Design Tools and New Media, Universal Design/Inclusive Design; Design Creativity, Design Projects and Case Studies
Design and layout:	Specific website promoted by the Korean Design Society. Easy to navigate. Only English language. Archives accessible from 2012 (Vol. 25)
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; Yes APCs: KRW 300,000 / 4,500 words + 100 KRW / per word (in English); KRW 300,000 / 4,000 words + 100 KRW / per word (in Korean)
Journal impact and reputation:	Good international reputation; ranked in the best 5 journal of Korea. Main indexing: Scopus
Impact score:	Scimago H-Index: 8, Good international reputation.
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus Citescore 2023: 0,6
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low geographic diversity (5% according to Scimago). 2. Wide range of design topics. 3. Low level of inclusivity of case studies and researchers from Global South
Editorial composition:	12/14 international
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but Ethical Standards explicit in detail
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Images are clickable and can be enlarged for a detailed view
Networking activities:	KSDS Conference Proceeding; KSDS International Invitational Exhibition; sigforum
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Engineering; Computer Science;
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

78.

Cubic Journal

Affiliation	Cubic Society, Hong Kong within The Hong Kong Polytechnic University's School of Design (PolyU Design) Publisher: Jap Sam Books, Netherlands
Funding date	2018
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Social Design and Management Design
Design and layout:	OJS Platform, very easy and pleasant to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access, NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access indexes (Google Scholar and DOAJ); Indexed in SCOPUS
Impact score:	Very low, Scimago: H-index 2 Scopus Citescore: 0,2
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citescore 2023 very low: 0,2
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very international, but only researchers from Global North. 2. Very wide range of design topics of design. 3. Low inclusivity of geographical representation; but inclusion of non-academic practitioners. Low case studies of underrepresented regions
Editorial composition:	Advisory board fully international, only Global North countries
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Many authors are non-academic practitioners of the design sector
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Architecture
Interdisciplinary impact:	Arts and Humanities: #466/667 Architecture: #163/169

79.

Indonesian Journal of Computing, Engineering and Design

Affiliation	Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Sampoerna University, Indonesia
Funding date	2019
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Visual Communication Design, Digital Art, Photography, Graphics, Art, and Design, Advertising; Design, Communication Technologies, Theory of Perception, Human-Computer Interaction, User Experience, User-based Design
Design and layout:	OJS platform. Easy to navigate, English language
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main indexing in open access databases (DOAJ, ROAD, BASE, Google Scholar) and Asian indexes (such as SINTA and Garuda). Main impact on asian region. NO SCOPUS or WOS. Main countries of visits: Indonesia (34%), US (14%), Singapore (7%), Philippines (6,8%), Nigeria (4%), India (4%), Malaysia (4%)
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available. Standard research and experimentation articles
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very diverse nationalities, mainly from Asian and Middle-Eastern countries. 2. Topics leveraging all aspects of Computing, Engineering, and Design, and their cross-disciplinary applications; 3. Good inclusivity levels, high numbers of authors and case studies from Global South (considering also journal's affiliation)
Editorial composition:	Scientific board very international: 70% international- 43% from Global North countries
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Computing; Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

80.

International Journal of Arts Architecture & Design_JAARD

Affiliation	World University of Design, India
Funding date	2023
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Interior Design; Industrial Design; Fashion Design; Textile Design; Product Design; Graphic Communication Design; Game Design; User Experience Design
Design and layout:	Website, easy to navigate. Archives digitally accessible. Submissions managed via email
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC (3000INR)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very young Journal; based in a Global South region. Indexing not displayed
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Main impact on Indian region as the articles present mainly local case studies. Citation rates not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Authors diversity very low. Indian authors mainly. 2. Topics within design discipline are broad. 3. Good representation of underrepresented area and voices from the Indian region
Editorial composition:	Editorial board is about 7 experts, 3 of them international
Review process:	Peer reviewed; not explicit if double and anonymous
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts; Ecology; Technology
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

81.

International Journal of Design_IJDesign

Affiliation	Chinese Institute of Design, Taiwan and Eindhoven University of Technology, Netherlands
Funding date	2007
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Social-Cultural Aspects of Design; Globalization and Localization Approaches to Design; Design Strategy and Management; Ergonomics and Perceptions in Design; Design Theories and Methodologies; Computer Applications in Design
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC (1000 \$)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very good reputation; Indexing in Scopus, WOS, Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-E), Social Science Citation Index (SSCI), Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI), EBSCO
Impact score:	Impact factor and citation reports published and fully transparent: SCOPUS: 4.0 Journal Citation Report: 2-Year Impact Factor: 1.806; 5-Year Impact Factor: 2.269 Web of Science: Average Citations per Article: 15.6 / 14.3 (without self-citations)
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Good Citation Score: 4.0 Number of Downloads per Article: 40,180
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. International authors. 2. Very wide range of topics of design discipline. 3. Even though based in Asia and in a Global South region, the authors affiliations are mainly from the Global North, justified by the high APC fees. Low inclusivity
Editorial composition:	Fully international, but main origin in the Global North
Review process:	Double-blind peer review process
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Special Issues (Call for special issues)
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Computer Science, Social Science, Engineering
Interdisciplinary impact:	Medium impact: Social Sciences: #53/275 percentile 80th Engineering: #90/307 percentile 70th Computer Science: #395/817 percentile #53/275

82.

JADECS (Journal of Art, Design, Art Education & Cultural Studies)

Affiliation	Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia
Funding date	2016
Language:	English and Indonesian
Scope and relevance:	Design cultures
Design and layout:	OJS platform; easy to navigate, also in English language. Archives accessible.
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact regional; Open access Indexing: DOAJ, GOOGLE SCHOLAR; CROSSREF; DIMENSIONS and regional indexing: SINTRA, GARUDA
Impact score:	Not assessable; 1,100 visitors in the last 12 months (2024); Indonesia: 87.2% Malaysia: 4.0% Kazakhstan: 1.8% United States: 1.6% Thailand: 1.0%
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; articles have titles and abstracts in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium geographic diversity, mainly from asian area. 2. Wide range of design topics. 3. Considering the geographical coverage, high inclusivity of underrepresented case studies and researchers
Editorial composition:	Members only from Indonesia and Malaysia
Review process:	Double-blind peer review process
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

83.

Jurnal Desain

Affiliation	Universitas Indraprasta PGRI, Indonesia
Funding date	2013
Language:	Indonesian
Scope and relevance:	Design and Visual Communications, Interior Design, Fashion Design, Product Design
Design and layout:	OJS platform; easy to navigate. English language.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access Indexing: DOAJ, BASE Regional indexing: SINTA, GARUDA, ONE Search NO SCOPUS or WOS
Impact score:	Not available; Most of the articles is published in Indonesian language, limiting international impact. However analytics published on the website declare that since 2019 the website has collected in Total Pageviews: 482,604 views; of which 86,921 in 2024. Main impact on South-East Asia countries and Europe
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available; Most of the articles is published in Indonesian language, limiting international impact. Downloads statics not available. Title and abstracts NOT available in English
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Low diversity, mainly Indonesia and South-Eastern Asia countries. 2. Very wide range of topics within the design discipline; high interdisciplinary. 3. Inclusion is intrinsically, considering the journal's geographical affiliation. However, low inclusion of other geographical areas
Editorial composition:	Section editors: fully Indonesian affiliations
Review process:	Double-blind peer review process
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Fine Arts
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

84.

Nirmana Jurnal Desain Komunikasi Visual

Affiliation	Petra Christian University , Indonesia
Funding date	2009
Language:	English and Indonesian
Scope and relevance:	Design knowledge and information, Visual Communication Design, Design practices
Design and layout:	OJS platform; easy to navigate - English language. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; No APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main Open Access Indexes and regional Indexing (Asian): Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ); Index Copernicus International (ICI); Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE); CrossRef; Asian Science Citation Index; OCLC WorldCat; Dimensions; Google Scholar; Sinta; Garuda; Main impact is regional, considering predominance of articles in Indonesian language
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Limited impact considering articles in Indonesian language. Abstract in english
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low geograohic diversity (mainly Indonesia). 2. Very wide range of topics from design cultures.3. high inclusivity however only from Asian continent
Editorial composition:	30% international
Review process:	Not explicit
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

85.

Paragraphs Environmental Design

Affiliation	Paragraphs is part of Media Publikasi Karya Riset Ilmiah an not for profit foundation. As a pioneering independent publisher
Funding date	2023
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Environmental design
Design and layout:	Easy to navigate, archives fully digitally accessible. Submission managed through JAMS Journal Management System
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Gold Open Access; YES APC (not published the amount)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very young, only national impact considering authorship geographical diversity. No indexing published
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Mainly national authors. 2. Topics at the intersection between interior design and architecture. 3. Inclusivity is intrinsically guaranteed as the journal is based in a underrepresented country of the Global South
Editorial composition:	Only national; W and M balanced
Review process:	Yes peer review process, but not stated if single or double and if anonymous or open
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Architecture
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

86.

She Ji_ The Journal of Design, Economics and Innovation

Affiliation	Tongji University – ELSEVIER Publisher
Funding date	2015
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design thinking, Social Design, Design Innovation, Design Management, Computational Design, Design Economics, Design Cultures
Design and layout:	Elsevier platform. Easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC (up to 1500\$)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very high reputation in the international design community, especially for topics intersecting between Design and Business management. Indexing: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) Scopus
Impact score:	IMPACT FACTOR: 1,8 Citescore: 6.2
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	High citation score: 559 article citations from 2020 to 2023
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Wide international representation. 2. Broad topic diversity within design discipline 3. Low inclusivity levels. Case studies and affiliation mainly from Western cultures
Editorial composition:	Low inclusivity: very international, but only Global North and China affiliations
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Elsevier
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Calls for Special Issues; collaboration with practitioners outside academia
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Economics, Business and Management; Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS Citescore: Arts and Humanities: #4/667 Economics: #23/288 Social Sciences (Education): #185/1543 Business, Management and Accounting: #80/289

87.

Theoretical Principles of Visual Arts! مب. (نظری ه) های تجس

Affiliation	Iranian Scientific Association of Visual Arts , Iran Al-Zahra University
Funding date	2016
Language:	English and Persian
Scope and relevance:	Industrial Design
Design and layout:	Platform entirely in Persian language; impact highly limited
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; YES APC (7,000,000 IRR = 150€)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very high reputation in the international design community, especially for topics intersecting between Design and Business management. Indexing: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) Scopus
Impact score:	National impact
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low geographic diversity. 2. Design topics only related to visual studies. 3. Representation only of the Arabic area
Editorial composition:	20% international
Review process:	Double Blind peer review Reviewers published along with their affiliation, competences and PUBLONS profile
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

North America

86.	She Ji_ The Journal of Design, Economics and Innovation
Affiliation	Tongji University – ELSEVIER Publisher
Funding date	2015
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design thinking, Social Design, Design Innovation, Design Management, Computational Design, Design Economics, Design Cultures
Design and layout:	Elsevier platform. Easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible.
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Open Access, YES APC (up to 1500\$)
Journal impact and reputation:	Very high reputation in the international design community, especially for topics intersecting between Design and Business management. Indexing: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) Scopus
Impact score:	IMPACT FACTOR: 1,8 Citescore: 6.2
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	High citation score: 559 article citations from 2020 to 2023
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Wide international representation. 2. Broad topic diversity within design discipline 3. Low inclusivity levels. Case studies and affiliation mainly from Western cultures
Editorial composition:	Low inclusivity: very international, but only Global North and China affiliations
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and Elsevier
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	Calls for Special Issues; collaboration with practitioners outside academia
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Economics, Business and Management; Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS Citescore: Arts and Humanities: #4/667 Economics: #23/288 Social Sciences (Education): #185/1543 Business, Management and Accounting: #80/289

87.	Design Issues
Affiliation	MIT Press // MIT University
Funding date	1984 - Digital since 2000
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Regular features include theoretical and critical articles by professional and scholarly contributors, extensive book and exhibition reviews, and visual sequences. Special guest-edited issues concentrate on particular themes, such as design history, human-computer interface, service design, organization design, design for development, and product design methodology
Design and layout:	Publisher's platform. Easy to navigate, Archives fully accessible. The preferred method of submission is by email to: designissues@case.edu .
Publication frequency:	Quarterly
Accessibility:	Hybrid open access. OA conversion fee is \$1,800.00 per article
Journal impact and reputation:	The first American academic journal to examine design history, theory, and criticism, Design Issues provokes inquiry into the cultural and intellectual issues surrounding design
Impact score:	Scimago H-Index 43
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Scopus CiteScore 2023: 1.6
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High level of geographical diversity. 2. Broad range of design topics. 3. Inclusivity of diverse perspectives, voices and underrepresented topics from peripheral areas of the world
Editorial composition:	60% international (mainly Anglo-Saxon world)
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and and International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE)
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Design Issues invites submission of visual projects of a theoretical or experimental nature. The primary criteria for selection are that the work be provocative and of high visual quality. (See above for graphic standards)
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Arts and Humanities; Computer Science
Interdisciplinary impact:	SCOPUS Citescore: Arts and Humanities #182/552 Computer Science #71/106/289

88.	DIALECTIC
Affiliation	AIGA, the professional association for design Official journal of the AIGA Design Educators Community (DEC) Michigan Publishing
Funding date	2017
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Education and practice in the discipline of visual communication design
Design and layout:	Easy to navigate; Publisher's website. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing not published. The journal has an high impact on the community; very prominent design researchers published
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity very low (no international authors). 2. Very wide range of design topics. 3. No global south
Editorial composition:	Only national
Review process:	Double Blind peer review
Ethical standards:	Yes COPE and the AIGA Standards of Professional Practice
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	AIGA Association
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Education and Social Sciences
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

89.	International Journal of Designs for Learning
Affiliation	Association for Educational Communications and Technology, United States Indiana University Bloomington, United States
Funding date	2010
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design Education
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Indexing not published; prevalence of United States affiliation. Impact of the journal not assessable
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Citation score non available. Statistics of downloads per each article displayed
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low, prevalence of North American researchers. 2. Topics covering only design education and pedagogy sector. 3. Very low level of inclusivity of underrepresented researchers or case studies
Editorial composition:	27% international (mainly Global North)
Review process:	Anonymous peer-review process (not specified if double or single)
Ethical standards:	No COPE; but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	IJDL publishes text and hybrid text/multimedia scholarly cases; Cases typically include primarily text, but image and multimedia assets embedded in the document (which will later be stored in archival form by IU Libraries, if the article is accepted) are permitted. The Journal's ARCHIVE publishes only PDF documents
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Pedagogy
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

Africa

90.	Africa Design Review Journal
Affiliation	Journal of the Department of Art and Design, University of Nairobi, Kenya
Funding date	2019
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design Research
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. English language. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Yearly/Biannual not clear
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Main impact regional. Indexing not published
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Very low geographic diversity (mainly national). 2. Fair range of design topics. 3. Low inclusivity, if we consider that the journal is based in the Global South
Editorial composition:	Fully national
Review process:	Not declared
Ethical standards:	Not declared
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Not available
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

91.	Image & Text
Affiliation	School of the Arts, University of Pretoria
Funding date	2019
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Design in Visual Cultures. The emphasis of the journal is on the Global South and also on encouraging emerging scholars and emerging fields
Design and layout:	OJS platform, easy to navigate. English language. Archive fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Annual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access indexing and regional: African Journal Archive Social Sciences and Humanities The Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) Very good impact on research for the Global South (international)
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Medium geographic diversity; high number of national authors, but good number of international authors. 2. Design topics related to design research. 3. High level of inclusivity, also case studies from other regions of GS
Editorial composition:	46% international (but from Western countries)
Review process:	Double Blind Peer Review
Ethical standards:	NO COPE but ethical standards explicit
Innovative practices and experimentation:	None
Networking activities:	None
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Visual studies; Fine arts
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

Australia

Affiliation	Elsevier
Funding date	1979
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Wide range of design domains, including but not limited to engineering design, industrial design, product design, systems design, innovation, and current design thinking paradigms within the overarching research context
Design and layout:	Elsevier Platform. Easy to navigate. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	6 Issues per year
Accessibility:	Almost all articles are Open Access mode for readers; To provide gold open access, this journal has a publication fee (Article Publishing Charge, APC): USD 4330
Journal impact and reputation:	The Journal has a very relevant reputation, as one of the most historical design journals for the community. Indexing: Scopus Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) SNIP
Impact score:	3.2
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	8.6 CitationScore (SCOPUS)
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. High geographic diversity. 2. Wide range of topics within the design realm.
Editorial composition:	12 editors and editorial board members in 6 countries/regions (Global North)
Review process:	Double Peer Review
Ethical standards:	Elsevier's Publishing Ethics Policy
Innovative practices and experimentation:	There is a section about: Videos and Audioslides but it's empty
Networking activities:	Thematic special issues
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Engineering; Arts and Humanities; Social Sciences; Computer science
Interdisciplinary impact:	Engineering (Architecture): #3/189 Arts and Humanities: #14/552 Social Sciences: #10/275 Computer science: #143/817

Affiliation	Archetype Health Pty Ltd , Australia Patient and Physician Advocacy Alliance
Funding date	2019
Language:	English
Scope and relevance:	Health Design, Medical Design
Design and layout:	Sage Website Solutions Inc. Easy to navigate as a platform. Archives fully accessible
Publication frequency:	Biannual
Accessibility:	Open Access; NO APC
Journal impact and reputation:	Open Access Indexing (DOAJ; Google Scholar; IOI Journals)
Impact score:	Not available
Articles impact and quality of published articles:	Not available
Diversity and inclusiveness:	1. Geographic diversity high. 2. Design topics related to medical and health realm; practitioners publishing. 3. Medium representation of researchers from global south
Editorial composition:	80% International – only UK and US
Review process:	Double blind peer review
Ethical standards:	No COPE, But Publishing Ethics Resource Kit (PERK) While the Journal of Health Design (JHD) does not inherently forbid the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in research manuscripts, it imposes expectations on authors to adhere to principles of responsibility, transparency, and specificity in their disclosure of AI utilization. Authors must explicitly acknowledge and elucidate the role of AI in their research within the "Acknowledgements" section of their submission
Innovative practices and experimentation:	Consider any files generated by your research as constituting relevant data. This may be raw or processed data. Examples include (but are not limited to): Individual-level de-identified patient data; Survey results; Interview transcripts; Statistical code; Images; Videos; Spreadsheets; Audio files; Text files; Imaging and scan files; They Use also INFOGRAPHICS; Each ARTICLE PRODUCES A VIDEO + PODCASTS in addition to the PDF
Networking activities:	This platform is now freely available and is resourced by the Patient and Physician Advocacy Alliance. The JHD offers advertising space on the right hand bar of our homepage
Pervasiveness with other scientific disciplines:	Not available
Interdisciplinary impact:	Not available

**“Whatever it is you're seeking,
won't come in the form you're expecting.”**

Kafka on the Shore, Haruki Murakami

Le Fin

